

A question i asked in Physics ?

i appreciate what you are recognized for in the field of Physics, HOWEVER . . . Has ANYONE of you EVER in LIFE, . . . EXPERIENCED an ATOM *Aṇu* (Pali / Sanskrit) in your PHYSICAL BODY *Kāya* (Pali / Sanskrit) and MIND *Citta* (Pali / Sanskrit) ?

if you ASK me how ??? the ANSWER is . . .

∅ IN the STILLNESS of AWARENESS, as the BODY and MIND sat STIL for LONG . . . Beloved Mother NATURE . . . REVEALED the EXPERIENCE of ATOM with my BODY-MIND complex!

The EXPEREINCE

∅ It cannot be PUT in WORDS . . . NEVERTHELESS . . . SUCH was the LEVEL of STILLNESS in those moments, that the ATOM itself REVEALED or CAME TO AWARENESS in FULL FORCE . . . with ENERGY RADIATING from it . . . that i COULD FEEL my WHOLE MIND being FOCUSED WITHOUT EFFORT . . . on ONE ATOM in the WHOLE PHYSICAL BODY . . . for a FRACTION of A SECOND or so . . .

∅ The ATOM CAME . . . INTO AWARENESS, . . . *Udaya* (Pali / Sanskrit) PERSISTED for SOMETIME . . . and THEN MOVED AWAY . . . *Vyaya* (Pali / Sanskrit)

∅ i **DID NOT HOLD ON** . . . to the ATOM . . . i **LET it GO** . . . Because **HOLDING ON** i.e *Upadana* (Pali) leads to **MISERY** i.e *Dukkha* (Pali / Sanskrit) and its **REALIZATION** *Pañña* (Pali) leads to **RELEASE or LIBERATION** *Vimutti* (Pali) . . . as my **BELOVED Mother Nature WORKS** by **HER WILL in full COMMAND in SILENCE!**

shriprakash sinha

sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com

independent researcher

Postal Address : 104 - Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai - 490006, Chhattisgarh, India

*Orcid id : 0000-0001-7027-5788, *

Tree structure : <https://linktr.ee/sinha.shriprakash>

Personal webpage : <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinha>

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Abstract

∅ **Physics** in Sanskrit is *padarthavignyanam, bhoutikashastram, sakarapadarthavignyanam, sakara-padarthavidya, sakarapadarthashastram, siddhapadarthavignyanam and sthulpadarthavignyanam*, as per **Moiner-William (1851)** and

∅ **Aṇu** is small, minute, atomic, subtle, as per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by **Dauids and Stede (1921-1925)** OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago.

In this article, i will share my insights, about the synergy of Physics and the teachings of my Beloved Teacher Shanyamuni Buddha, the limited, that i could grasp in meditations that have spanned over a period of 24 years, of which the *Āṇāpana* and *Vipassanā / vipaśyanā*, in line with the Beloved Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings, were done and are continuing since 2014 onwards! **This interweaving of the technical and spiritual knowledge, might help present aspects of reality in, may be simplified terms, that could help readers assimilate the interconnectedness between Physics and the Buddha's teachings and later on build on and write similar articles, IF they wish to, imbued with the salmagundi / macédoine / gallimaufry / concoction / conglomeration of spiritual knowledge and principles of physics.**

Nevertheless, hope the monograph will be of help to some . . . **HOWEVER, not because i have said so, but you as a meditator, by your own experiential knowledge confirm the reality of life as-it-is, i.e yatha-bhūta! So, for this to happen**, though long is the journey, you NEED to move from *pariyatti* (theory), to *pattipatti* (practice) to *paṭivedha* (attainment), as the three stages of knowledge will settle in *Suta-maya-pañña*, *Cintā-maya-pañña* and *Bhāvanā-maya-pañña*.

Finally, **in this manuscript**, is **presented first** the Buddhist teachings, **followed by** presentation of technical aspects of modern era Physics. Now, **it is not possible to just say a few words** about **Aṇu** or the atom; . . . **i need to view** the same **Aṇu** **from multiple perspectives, to build** a somewhat comprehensive and a holistic **view of the subject which incorporates**, theoretical knowledge, insights, and experiential knowledge! Further, **for experiential knowledge to happen, one needs to meditate** and i have for **completeness, reiterated** the *Āṇāpana* and *Vipassanā / vipaśyanā*, meditations, which i have practised since 2013! Thus the **style of presentation** is that i will **weave through** the **exposition with images** where needed, **terminologies in Pali, my limited insights** of that which i grasp, **with topics ranging from and IN-ORDER ABOUT, Saṃsāra** or transmigration in cycles, **Buddhist Cosmology, Bhūta** or matter in general, **Dhātu** or the elements, **(s)Khandha** or the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense / the elements or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form, detailed aspects of **Paṭcca-Samuppāda** or causal genesis / dependent origination, the **Jhāna** or the absorptions, **atoms in the study through modern era physics**, the inception of which starts from **Ernest-Rutherford Scattering** experiments, **Neils-Henrik-David-Bohr** experiments, **Geiger-and-Marsden Scattering** theory model, the **Mathematics of Conic section and Hyperbola(s)**. **Succintly, in my limited grasp, we have an elucidation that sheds light on synergy of Physics in modern lingua and the Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings in Pali!** Additionally, i have used translations which are NOT mine, under the standard licenses available, due to **paucity of time**, **HOWEVER**, one can find one of my translations in <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinha/shriprakashsinha/karaniya-metta-sutta>. It is recommended that one NEEDS to EVALUATE and then proceed with whichever translations, that FACILITATES in your GRASPING of the matter under consideration!

Keywords: Aṇu, pariyatti (theory), pattipatti (practice), paṭivedha (attainment), Suta-maya-pañña, Cintā-maya-pañña and Bhāvanā-maya-pañña.

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1 Someone enquired me . . .

- Someone enquired me long time back -

Φ what are **your experiments**?

Φ what is **your instrument**? and

Φ what is **your subject**? and . . .

Φ on which . . . **you will claim or will your points**?

- i said -

Φ the **experiments are** . . . the Āṇāpana and Vipassanā / vipaśyanā meditations,

Φ the **instrument is** . . . this body-mind-being complex of human being and . . .

Φ the **subject is** . . . i myself . . . on which i MIGHT claim my points!

Φ **COMMUNICATION was LOST for ever after this! And i don't remember with whom it was!**

2 Etymology

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by **Davids and Stede (1921-1925)** OR the link to online Pali dictionary @ University of Chicago, atom is -

- **Aṇu** Aṇu (adj.) [Sk. aṇu; as to etym. see Walde Lat. Wtb. under ulna. See also āṇi] small, minute, atomic, subtle (opp. thūla, q. v.) D i.223; S i.136; v.96 (°bīja); Sn 299 (anuto aṇum gradually); J iii.12 (= appamattaka); iv.203; Dhs 230, 617 (= kisa); ThA 173; Miln 361. Note aṇu is freq. spelt anu, thus usually in cpd. °matta.

Also, from the English-Pali dictionary by **Buddhadatta (1989)**, one finds for atom -

- **atom** : (m.) paramāṇu.
- **atomic** : (adj.) paramāṇuvisayaka.
- **atomism** : (m.) paramāṇuvāda.
- **atomise** : (v.t.) paramāṇubhāvaṃ pāpeti. (pp.) paramāṇubhāvaṃ papita.
- **atomy** : (m.) 1. kisadeha; 2. aṭṭhikaṅkala; 3. aṇuppamāṇajīvī.

3 Atom :: Aṇu in *Dhammapada*

In the *Dhammapada* in *Khuddakanikāya* or the Minor Collection in *Suttapiṭaka*, we find in -

Appamādavaggo # 2 -

a company, section, group, party, heaped up of . . .
thoughtfulness, carefulness, conscientiousness, watchfulness, vigilance, earnestness, zeal

Appamādarato bhikkhu, pamāde bhayadassivā,

delighting in, intent on, devoted to . . .

thoughtfulness, carefulness, conscientiousness, watchfulness, vigilance, earnestness, zeal . . .

monks, . . .

in carelessness, negligence, indolence, remissness . . .

seeing or realising an object of fear, i. e. danger!

fear, fright, dread . . .

saṃyojanam aṇum-thūlam ḍhammaggāva gacchati. [31]

in conjunction & completeness . . .

like the yoke of a carriage / a measure of length: as much as can be travelled with one yoke (of oxen), a distance of about 7 miles . . .

small, minute, atomic, subtle / fine and coarse, small & large . . .

one goes, to be in motion, to move, to go on / to go, to walk / to go away, to go out, to go forth / with acc. or substitute: to go to, to have access to, to arrive or get at / to go as a stronger expression for to be, i.e. to behave, to have existence, to fare . . .

to burn, consume, torment . . .

in the fire, flames, sparks; conflagration / the sacrificial fire / (ethical, always) the fire of burning, consuming, feverish sensations.

Maggavaggo # 20 -

a company, section, group, party, heaped up . . .

a road (usually high road), way, foot - path the road of moral & good living, the path of righteousness, with ref. to the moral standard & the way to salvation

Yāva hi vanatho na chijjati

up to (a point), as far as, how far, so far that (cp. tāva I), both temporal and local . . .

underwood, brushwood, thicket / lust, desire, . . .

if NOT . . .

to cut off, to destroy, to remove . . .

aṇumatto pi narassa nārisu,

Even in small, minute, atomic, subtle - of small size, atomic, least

of a man / male for a woman / female AND vice versa, . . .

is in shortness, reduction of the determination

paṭibaddhamano va tāva so,

bound to, in fetters or bonds, attracted to or by, dependent on . . .

is the intellectual functioning of consciousness

so much, so long; usually correl. with yāva how long, how much; in all meanings to be understood out of elliptical application of this correlation

vaccho khīrapako va mātari. [284]

as a calf . . .

drinking . . .

milk, milky fluid, milky juice . . .

of its mother!

4 Glimpses of the Specturm of Beloved Mother Nature through Pali

4.1 Realms of Existence :: Loka

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago](#), the realms of existence of loka is -

- **Loka** [cp. Vedic loka in its oldest meaning "space, open space." For etym. see **rocati**. To the etym. feeling of the Pāli hearer loka is closely related in quality to **ruppati** (as in pop. etym. of **rūpa**) and **rujati**. As regards the latter the etym. runs "lujjati kho loko ti vuccati" S iv.52, cp. Nd2 550, and loka=lujjana DhsA 47, 308: see lujjana. The Dhṭp 531 gives root **lok** (**loc**) in sense of **dassana**] world, primarily "visible world," then in general as "space or sphere of creation," with var. degrees of substantiality. Often (unspecified) in the comprehensive sense of "universe." Sometimes the term is applied collectively to the creatures inhabiting this or var. other worlds, thus, "man, mankind, people, beings." - **Loka** is not a fixed & def. term. It comprises immateriality as well as materiality and emphasizes either one or the other meaning according to the view applied to the object or category in question. Thus a trsltn of "sphere, plane, division, order" interchanges with "world." Whenever the spatial element prevails we speak of its "regional" meaning as contrasted with "applied" meaning. The fundamental notion however is that of substantiality, to which is closely related the specific Buddhist notion of impermanence (loka=lujjati). - **1.** Universe: the distinctions between the universe (cp. cakkavāḷa) as a larger whole and the world as a smaller unit are fluctuating & not definite. A somewhat wider sphere is perhaps indicated by **sabba-loka** (e. g. S i.12; iv.127, 312; v.132; It 122; Mhvs 1, 44; cp. **sabbāvanta** loka D i.251; iii.224), otherwise even the smaller loka comprises var. realms of creation. Another larger division is that of loka as **sadevaka**, **samāraka**, **sabrahmaka**, or the world with its devas, its Māra and its Brahmā, e. g. S i.160, 168, 207; ii.170; iii.28, 59; iv.158; v.204; A i.259 sq.; ii.24 sq.; iii.341; iv.56, 173; v.50; It 121; Nd1 447 (on Sn 956), to which is usually added **sassamaṇa-brāhmaṇī pajā** (e. g. D i.250, see loci s. v. pajā). With this cp. Dh 45, where the divisions are **paṭhavī**, **Yamaloka**, **sadevaka** (loka), which are expld at DhA i.334 by paṭhavī=attabhāva; Yamaloka=catubbidha apāyaloka; sadevaka=manussaloka devalokena saddhim. - The universe has its evolutionary periods: **saṃvattati** and **vivattati** D ii.109 sq. The Buddha has mastered it by his enlightenment: loko Tathāgatena abhisambuddho It 121. On loka, lokadhātu (=cosmos) and cakkavāḷa cp. Kirfel, Kosmographie p. 180, 181. - **2.** Regional meaning. - (a) in general. Referring to this world, the character of evanescence is inherent in it; referring to the universe in a wider sense, it implies infinity, though not in definite terms. There is mention of the different metaphysical theories as regards cosmogony at many places of the Canon. The **antānantikā** (contending for the finitude or otherwise of the world) are mentioned as a sect at D i.22 sq. Discussions as to whether loka is **sassata** or **antavā** are found e. g. at M i.426, 484; ii.233; S iii.182, 204; iv.286 sq.; A ii.41; v.31, 186 sq.; Ps i.123, 151 sq.; Vbh 340; Dhs 1117. Views on consistency of the world (eternal or finite; created or evolved etc.) at D iii.137; cp. S ii.19 sq. Cp. also the long and interesting discussion of loka as **suñña** at S iv.54 sq.; Ps ii.177 sq.; Nd2 680; - as well as M ii.68 (upanīyati loko addhuvo, and "attāṇo loko, assakoloko" etc.); "lokassa anto" is lit. unattainable: A ii.50=S i.62; iv.93; but the Arahant is "lok'antagū," cp. A iv.430. - As regards their order in space (or "plane") there are var. groupings of var. worlds, the evidently popular one being that the world of the **devas** is above and the **nirayas** below

the world of man (which is "tīriyaṃ vāpi majjhe"): Nd2 550. The world of men is as **ayaṃ loko** contrasted with the beyond, or **paro loko**: D iii.181; S iv.348 sq.; A i.269; iv.226; Sn 779 (n'āsimsati lokam imam paraṃ ca); or as **idhaloka** D iii.105. The defn of **ayaṃ loko** at Nd1 60 is given as: sak'attabhāva, saka - rūpa - vedanā etc., ajjhatt' āyatanāni, manussa - loka, kāmadhātu; with which is contrasted **paro loko** as: parattabhāva, para - rūpavedanā, bāhir'āyatanāni, devaloka, rūpa - & arūpadhātu. - The rise and decay of this world is referred to as **samudaya** and **atthangama** at S ii.73; iii.135; iv.86; A v.107. - Cp. D iii.33 (attā ca loko ca); Mhvs 1, 5 (lokam dukkhā pamocetum); 28, 4 (loko 'yam pīlito); PvA 1 (vijjā - caraṇa - sampannaṃ yena nīyanti lokato). - Other divisions of var. kinds of "planes" are e. g. **deva**° A i.115, 153; iii.414 sq.; **Brahma**° Vbh 421; Mhvs 19, 45; **Yama**° Dh 44; S i.34; **nara**° Mhvs 5, 282. See also each sep. head - word, also **petā**° & **manussa**°. - The division at Nd1 550 is as follows: niraya°, tiracchāna°, pīttivīsayā°, manussa°, deva° (=material); upon which follow khandha°, dhātu°, āyatana° (=immaterial). Similarly at Nd¹ 29, where **apāya**° takes the place of niraya°, tiracchāna°, pīttivīsayā°. - Another threefold division is **sankhāra**°, **satta**°, **okāsa**° at Vism 204, with explns: "sabbe sattā āhāra - t̄hītikā" ti= sankhāraloka; "sassato loko ti vā asassato loko" ti= sattaloka; "yāvātā candima - suriyā parihaaranti disā 'bhanti virocamaṇā" etc. (=M i.328; A i.227; cp. J i.132) =okāsaloka. The same expln in detail at SnA 442. - Another as **kāma**°, **rūpa**°, **arūpa**°: see under rūpa; another as **kilesa**°, **bhava**°, **indriya**° at Nett 11, 19. Cp. sankhāra - loka VbhA 456; dasa lokadhātuyo (see below) S i.26. - 3. Ordinary & applied meaning. - (a) division of the world, worldly things S i.1, 24 (loke visattikā attachment to this world; opp. sabba - loka anabhirati S v.132). - **loke** in this world, among men, here D iii.196 (ye nibbutā loka); It 78 (loke uppajjati); DA i.173 (id.); Vbh 101 (yam loka piya - rūpaṃ etc.); Pv ii.113 (=idaṃ C.); KhA 15, 215. See also the diff. defns of loka at Nd2 552. - **loka** collectively "one, man": kiccam loko āpanno jāyati ca jīyati ca, etc. D ii.30. Also "people": Lanka - loka people of Ceylon Mhvs 19, 85; cp. **jana** in similar meaning. Derived from this meaning is the use in cpds. (°-) as "usual, every day, popular, common": see e. g. °āyata, °vajja, °vohāra. - (b) "thing of the world," material element, physical or worldly quality, sphere or category (of "materiality"). This category of **loka** is referred to at Vbh 193, which is expld at VbhA 220 as follows: "ettha yo ayaṃ ajjhatt' ādi bhedo kāyo pariggahīto, so eva idha - loko nāma." In this sense 13 groups are classified according to the number of constituents in each group (1 - 12 and No. 18); they are given at Nd² 551 (under lokantagū Sn 1133) as follows: (1) bhavaloka; (2) sampatti bhavaloka, vipatti bhavaloka; (3) vedanā; (4) āhāra; (5) upādāna - kkhandhā; (6) ajjhattikāni āyatanāni (their rise & decay as "lokassa samudaya & atthangama" at S iv.87); (7) viññāṇaṭṭhītiyo; (8) loka - dhammā; (9) satt'āvāsā; (10) upakkilesā; (11) kāmabhavā; (12) āyatanāni; (18) dhātuyo. They are repeated at Ps i.122=174, with (1) as "sabbe sattā āhāra - t̄hītikā; (2) nāmaṃ ca rūpaṃ ca; and the remainder the same. Also at Vism 205 and at SnA 442 as at Ps i.122. Cp. the similar view at S iv.95: one perceives the world ("materiality": loka - saññin and loka - mānin, proud of the world) with the six senses. This is called the "loka" in the logic (vinaya) of the ariyā. - A few similes with loka see J.P.T.S. 1907, 131. **-akkhāyikā** (f., scil. **kathā**) talk or speculation about (origin etc. of) the world, popular philosophy (see **lokāyata** and cp. Dialogues i.14) Vin i.188; D i.8; M i.513; Miln 316; DA i.90. **-agga** chief of the world. Ep. of the Buddha ThA 69 (Ap. v.11). **-anta** the end (spatial) of the world A ii.49 (na ca appatvā lokantaṃ dukkhā atthi pamocanaṃ). **-antagū** one who has reached the end of the world (and of all things worldly), Ep. of an Arahant A ii.6, 49 sq.; It 115, Sn 1133; Nd2

551. **-antara** the space between the single worlds J i.44 (v.253: Avīcimhi na uppajjanti, tathā lokantaresu ca). **-antarika** (scil. Niraya) a group of Nirayas or Purgatories situated in the lokantara (i. e. cakkavāl, antaresu J i.76), 8,000 yojanas in extent, pitch dark, which were filled with light when Gotama became the Buddha J i.76; VbhA 4; Vism 207 (lokantariya°); SnA 59 (°vāsa life in the l. niraya); cp. BSk. lokāntarikā Divy 204 (andhās tamaso ’ndhakāra - tamisrā). **-ādhipa** lord or ruler of the world A i.150. **-ādhipateyya** "rule of the world," dependence on public opinion, influence of material things on man, one of the 3 ādhipateyyas (atta°, loka°, dhamma°) D iii.220; Vism 14. **-ānukampā** sympathy with the world of men [cp. BSk. lokānugraha Divy 124 sq.] D iii.211; It 79. **-āmisa** worldly gain, bait of the flesh M i.156; ii.253; Th 2, 356. **-āyata** what pertains to the ordinary view (of the world), common or popular philosophy, or as Rhys Davids (Dial. i.171) puts it: "name of a branch of Brahman learning, probably Nature - lore"; later worked into a quāsi system of "casuistry, sophistry." Franke, Dīgha trsln 19, trsls as "logisch beweisende Naturerklärung" (see the long note on this page, and cp. Dial. i.166 - 172 for detail of lokāyata). It is much the same as **lok-akkhāy(ika)** or popular philosophy. - D i.11, 88; Vin ii.139; Sn p. 105 (=vitaṇḍa - vādasattha SnA 447, as at DA i.247); Miln 4, 10, 178; A i.163, 166; iii.223. Cp. BSk. lokāyata Divy 630, 633, and **lokāyatika** ibid. 619. See also Kern's remarks at Toev. s. v. **-āyatika** (brāhmaṇa) one who holds the view of lokāyata or popular philosophy S ii.77 (trsln K.S. 53: a Brahmin "wise in world - lore"); Miln 178; J vi.486 (na seve lokāyatikaṃ; expld as "anattanissitaṃ . . . vitaṇḍa - sallāpaṃ lokāyatika - vādaṃ na seveyya," thus more like "sophistry" or casuistry). **-issara** lord of the world Sdhp 348. **-uttara** see under lokiya. **-cintā** thinking about the world, worldphilosophy or speculation S v.447; A ii.80 (as one of the 4 acinteyyāni or thoughts not to be thought out: buddha - visaya, jhāna - visaya, kamma - vipāka, l - c.). Cp. BSk. laukika citta Divy 63, 77 etc. **-dhammā** (pl.) common practice, things of the world, worldly conditions S iii.139 sq.; Sn 268 (expln loke dhammā; yāva lokappavatti tāva - anivattikā dhammā ti vuttaṃ hoti KhA 153, cp. J iii.468); Miln 146. Usually comprising a set of eight, viz. lābha, alābha, yaso, ayaso, nindā, pasamsā, sukhaṃ, dukkhaṃ D iii.260; A iv.156 sq.; v.53; Nd2 55; Ps i.22, 122; Vbh 387; Nett 162; DhA ii.157. **-dhātu** constituent or unit of the Universe, "world - element"; a world, sphere; another name for **cakkavāla**. Dasa - sahasi - lokadhātu the system of the 10,000 worlds Vin i.12; A i.227. - D iii.114; Pv ii.961; Kvu 476; Vism 206 sq.; Vbh 336; Nd1 356 (with the stages from one to fifty lokadhātu's, upon which follow: sahasi cūḷanikā l - dh.; dvisahasī majjhimikā; tisahasī; mahāsahasī); J i.63, 212; Miln 237; VbhA 430, 436. See also cūḷanikā. **-nātha** saviour of the world, Ep. of the Buddha Sn 995; Vism 201, 234; VvA 165; PvA 42, 287. **-nāyaka** guide or leader of the world (said of the Buddha) Sn 991; Ap 20; Mhvs 7, 1; Miln 222. **-nirodha** destruction of the world It 121 (opp. °samudaya). **-pāla** (°devatā) guardian (governor) of the world, which are usually sepcified as four, viz. Kuvera (=Vessavaṇa), Dhataratṭha, Virūpakkha, Virūḷhaka, alias the 4 **mahārājāno** Pv i.42; J i.48 (announce the future birth of a Buddha). **-byūha** "world - array," pl. byūhā (devā) N. of a class of devas J i.47; Vism 415 (kāmvācara - deva's). **-mariyādā** the boundary of the world VvA 72. -vajja common sins Miln 266; KhA 190. **-vaṭṭa** "world - round," i. e. saṃsāra (opp. vivaṭṭa =nibbāna) Nett 113, 119. See also vaṭṭa. **-vidu** knowing the universe, Lp. of the Buddha D iii.76; S i.62; v.197, 343; A ii.48; Sn p. 103; Vv 3426; Pug 57; expld in full at SnA 442 and Vism 204 sq. **-vivarana** unveiling of the universe, apocalypse, revelation Vism 392 (when humans see the devas etc.). **-vohāra** common or general distinction, popular logic, ordinary way of speaking SnA 383, 466; VbhA 164.

In simple terms, *lokas* are the realms of existence in the changing configuration of the cosmos, in the dimension of time and space, in Beloved Mother Nature!

According to Buddhist cosmology, Sadakata (1997)'s work summarises *Loka* into the *Hīnayāna* school centers on (1) the realm of Mount Sumeru, (2) dharmas (the Buddha's teachings), and (3) the notion that the Shakyamuni Buddha is a historical person, while the *Mahāyāna* school centers on, (1) the various "buddha-realms" are more prominent than Mount Sumeru, (2) the Buddha (or buddhas) takes precedence over dharmas, and (3) the Buddha is a suprahuman cosmological existence.

A brief deflection, *ONE NEEDS to know about Mahāyāna and Hīnayāna* by, first studying the article titled - **Chapter # 2 : From hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha • The journey of a thousand li commenced with a single step : 千里之行始于足下- 老子, Lao Tzu • A journey of four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons @ <http://osf.io/8hn5e/files/g8bdc>.**

Sadakata (1997), further continues with the aspects of *aṇu*, with reference to it as *paramāṇu*s as the smallest indivisible part of matter. In Dhammajoti (2002)'s work on *Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma*, Bhikkhu K.L. Dhammajoti quotes *Abhidharma-mahā-vibhāṣa-śāstra* regarding *atom*, on page 260 the following -

An atom (*paramāṇu*) is the smallest *rūpa*. It cannot be cut, broken, penetrated; it cannot be taken up, abandoned, ridden on, stepped on, struck or dragged. It is neither long nor short, square nor round, regular nor irregular, convex nor concave. It has no smaller parts; it cannot be decomposed, cannot be seen, heard, smelled, touched. It is thus that the *paramāṇu* is said to be the finest (*sarva-sūkṣma*) of all *rūpa-s*.

Seven of these *paramāṇu-s* constitute an *aṇu* - the finest among all *rūpa-s* perceivable by the eye and visual consciousness. *[However,] this [aṇu] can be seen by only three types of eyes: 1. the divya-cakṣus, 2. the eye of a Universal Monarch (cakravartin), 3. the eye of a bodhisattva in his last birth. Seven aṇu-s constitute a tāmra-rajās . . . Seven tāmra-rajās-s constitute an ap-rajās . . . Seven ap-rajās-s constitute a śāśa-rajās; . . . Seven śāśa-rajās-s constitute a eḍaka-rajās . . . Seven eḍaka-rajās-s constitute a go-rajās . . . Seven go-rajās-s constitute a vātāy ana-rajās . . . [in this way, the whole universe is composed].*⁴⁹

Now, the *existence of the four elements*, which is widely known and otherwise in Pali, termed as *cattāro mahābhūtā(ni)*, i.e. *paṭhavī* or earth, *āpo* or water, *tejo* or fire and *vāyo* wind, *are not only elements are not only visible in GROSS, but also remain SUBTLE in the invisible!* Further, these *elements constitute a paramāṇu*. In short, *paṭhavī* or earth, *by its nature provides DENSE GROSS STABILITY and carries the property of COHESION*, *āpo* or water, *by its nature provides COOLNESS and HUMIDITY and carries the property of FLUIDITY and the flow is from HIGH to LOW*, *tejo* or fire, *by its nature provides HEAT and carries the property of BURNING and is always going UP from BELOW*, and *vāyo* wind, *by its nature provides MOVES and carries the property of SCATTERING or DISSIPATES. In their subtle proportions and mixtures, these four elements make up an atom or paramāṇu*. These elements are called *Dhātu* in Pali. Additionally, Dhammajoti (2002) in his work on *Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma*, on page 42, has depicted the 18 elements or *aṣṭadaśa dhātu* as represented in figure 1.

Further, *there is this term loka-dhātu which refers to constituent or unit of the Universe, "world - element"*; a world, sphere; another name for *cakkavāla*. Then *there is a term Dasa-sahassi-lokadhātu or the system of the 10,000 worlds*.

Correlation between the 5 categories, 5 *skandha*-s, 12 *āyatana*-s and 18 *dhātu*-s

Diagram Text Abbreviations

sk = *skandha*

āy = *āyatana*

dh = *dhātu*

vij = *vijñāna*

Figure 1: From Dhammajoti (2002) on *Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharma1bhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Now, *time has different gradations according to systems of study and in Buddhist teachings*, as shown by Sadakata (1997), in ascending order, one finds the gradations of time as follows -

1. *kṣaṇa* ($\frac{1}{75}$ second)
2. *tat-kṣaṇa*; equals 120 *kṣaṇa* ($1\frac{3}{5}$ seconds)
3. *lava*; equals 60 *tat-kṣaṇa* (1 minute 36 seconds)
4. *muhūrta*; equals 30 lavas (48 minutes)
5. *aho-rātra*; equals 30 *muhūartas* (24 hours, day)
6. *mūsa*; equals 30 *aho-rātras* (month)
7. *saṃwatsara* (year)

So, if i use this measurement of one *kṣaṇa*, the entire configuration of the cosmos has changed, in the dimension of time and space! Now, can you see the entire change in the cosmos, that has happened in that one *kṣaṇa* ? How much deep is your awareness ?

To reiterate, in simple terms, Lokas are the realms of existence in the changing configuration of the cosmos, in the dimension of time and space, in Beloved Mother Nature! Thus, based on the above gradations of time, one can measure the events at a particular level of granularity. Also, as the configuration of the cosmos changes in the dimension of time and space, there are diiferent realms of existence in cosmos. *Sadakata (1997)* studies about the cosmology and depicts a few images which i have curated here in a particuluar order. i will not explain these images and will get present this order and the intention to do is that the reader just sees these images and searches for deeper meaning from sources available!

In line with the description of the cosmology in *Sadakata (1997)*, below are the **first five images pertaining to the cosmos** which includes Φ the composition of the world or *saṃsāra*, Φ a bird's eye view of **Mount Sumeru realm or loka**, Φ the depiction of **Mount Sumeru in Square**, Φ the **different sizes of Mount Sumeru and the surrounding mountains** and lastly Φ the depiction of *Jambudvīpa*, according to *Abhidharma kosa*. These are depicted in figs. 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

Fig. 21. Composition of a World
Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.

Figure 2: The composition of the world or *saṃsāra*, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 5. Bird's-Eye View of the Mount Sumeru Realm
Dimensions are given in *yojanas*. (1 *yojana* is approximately 7 kilometers.)

Figure 3: a bird's eye view of Mount Sumeru realm or *loka*, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 6. Mount Sumeru as a Square
The *Abhidharmakośa* says, "The width of the first of the seven seas [that between Sumeru and Yugandhara] is 80,000 *yojanas*. The length [of the sea] is three times [80,000 *yojanas*]. When measuring [one of the four sides that are] the seashores of Yugandhara, it becomes 240,000 *yojanas*" (*Abhidharmakośa*, lines 13–15, *Taiśhō Tripitaka*, vol. 29, p. 57c). Cf. Leo M. Pruden, *Abhidharmakośabhāṣyam* by Louis de la Vallée Poussin, vol. 2 (Berkeley, Calif.: Asian Humanities Press, 1989), p. 454. (Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.)

Figure 4: the depiction of Mount Sumeru in Square, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 7. Sizes of Mount Sumeru and Surrounding Mountains and Seas

1) Yugandhara (40,000); 2) Īṣādhāra (20,000); 3) Khadiraka (10,000); 4) Sudarśana (5,000); 5) Aśvakaṛṇa (2,500); 6) Vinataka (1,250); 7) Nimindhara (625); 8) Cakravāḍa (312.5). (Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.)

Figure 5: the different sizes of Mount Sumeru and the surrounding mountains, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 11. Jambudvīpa according to the Abhidharmakośa
Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.

Figure 6: depiction of *Jambudvīpa*, according to Abhidharma kosa, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

A QUESTION I ASKED IN PHYSICS ?

Figure 7: Mount Meru of *Jambudvīpa* according to Buddhism, as represented in Commons (2026m)

Figure 8: *Jambudvīpa* according to Jainism, as represented in Commons (2026n)

Figure 9: *Jambudvīpa* according to Hinduism, as represented in Commons (2026j)

Further, i have adopted images from Wikipedia regarding the depiction of *Samsāra* and *Jambudvīpa* in Buddhist, Jain and Hindu systems. See these three images below in figs. 4.1, 4.1 and 4.1.

Fig. 23. Cycle of the Universe

Figure 10: the cycle of the universe within Beloved Mother nature (Part a), from [Sadakata \(1997\)](#) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmalbhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Next, we look at the **images of realms of existence** or the *lokas*, in the following **eight images in serial order** which depict Φ the **cycle of the universe within Beloved Mother nature** [in two images], Φ the **6 types of beings in existence** and the **6 paths**, Φ the **relationship between realms of desire and form** [in two images], Φ the **placement of the 8 hot hells** according to the **2nd** interpretation in the **Great Commentary** and Φ the **abode of the 33 gods** and finally Φ the **extent of the 1st Dhyāna-Heavens**. These are depicted in figs. 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 , 15, 16 and 17.

Lastly, fig. 18 points to the **31 realms of existence in accordance with the Theravada School of Buddhist teachings**.

Figure 11: the cycle of the universe within Beloved Mother nature (Part b), from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 14. The Six Paths of Transmigration

Figure 12: the 6 types of beings in existence and the 6 paths, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

			DISTANCE FROM THE WATER SURFACE OF THE GOLDEN EARTH LAYER	
heavenly leities	Realm of form	Fourth Dhyāna	Akaniṣṭha Sudarśana Sudrśa Atapa Abṛha Bṛhatphala Puṇyaprasava Anabhraka	(yojanas) 167,772,160,000 83,886,080,000 41,943,040,000 20,971,520,000 10,485,760,000 5,242,880,000 2,621,440,000 1,310,720,000
		Third Dhyāna	Śubhākṛtsna Apramāṇaśubha Parittaśubha	(yojanas) 655,360,000 327,680,000 163,840,000
		Second Dhyāna	Ābhāsvara Apramāṇābha Parittābha	(yojanas) 81,920,000 40,960,000 20,480,000
		First Dhyāna	Mahābrahmā Brahma-purohita Brahma-kāyika	(yojanas) 10,240,000 5,120,000 2,560,000
earth- welling eities	Realm of desire	Six Heavens of the realm of desire	Para-nirmita-vaśavartin heaven Nirmāṇa-rati heaven Tuṣita heaven Yama heaven	(yojanas) 1,280,000 640,000 320,000 160,000
			Heaven of the thirty-three gods Heaven of the Four Great Kings and their subordinates	(yojanas) 80,000 40,000
above the round	Realm of desire		Uttarakuru Aparagodāniya Pūrvavideha Jambudvīpa	(yojanas) 0 0 0 0
			Realm of the animals Realm of the spirits of the dead	(yojanas) 0 500
below the earth			Samjīva Kālasūtra Samghāta Raurava Mahāraurava Tāpana Pratāpana Avici	(yojanas) 1,000 unclear unclear unclear unclear unclear unclear 20,000

Fig. 17. Relationship of the Realms of Desire and Form

One *krośa* is a bit less than a kilometer. One *hasta* is the length of a forearm. One *kalpa* is an incalculably long period of time. One great *kalpa* equals eighty *kalpas*.

Figure 13: relationship between realms of desire and form (Part a), from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

A QUESTION I ASKED IN PHYSICS ?

AREA		HUMAN HEIGHT		HUMAN LIFE SPAN	
one great-thousand-world		(yojanas) 16,000.0		(one great kalpa)	16,000.0
one great-thousand-world		8,000.0			8,000.0
one great-thousand-world		4,000.0			4,000.0
one great-thousand-world		2,000.0			2,000.0
one great-thousand-world		1,000.0			1,000.0
one great-thousand-world		500.0			500.0
one great-thousand-world		250.0			250.0
one great-thousand-world		125.0			125.0
one medium-thousand-world		(yojanas) 64.0		(one great kalpa)	64.0
one medium-thousand-world		32.0			32.0
one medium-thousand-world		16.0			16.0
one small-thousand-world		(yojanas) 8.0		(one great kalpa)	8.0
one small-thousand-world		4.0			4.0
one small-thousand-world		2.0			2.0
area as broad as the four landmasses		(yojanas) 1.5		(half a great kalpa)	1.5
area as broad as the four landmasses		1.0			1.0
area as broad as the four landmasses		0.5			0.5
(yojanas)	80,000 ²	(krośas) 1.50	(years)	16,000 × 1,600 × 30 × 12	
	80,000 ²	1.25		8,000 × 800 × 30 × 12	
	80,000 ²	1.00		4,000 × 400 × 30 × 12	
	80,000 ²	0.75		2,000 × 200 × 30 × 12	
(yojanas)	80,000 ²	(krośas) 0.50	(years)	1,000 × 100 × 30 × 12	
	various	0.25		500 × 50 × 30 × 12	
(yojanas)	2,000 ²	(hastas) 32	(years)	1,000	
	1,250 ² π	16		500	
	about 2,000,000	8		250	
	about 2,000,000	4		infinite-10	
	unclear	unclear		at most, one kalpa	
	unclear	unclear		500 × 30	
(yojanas)	unclear	unclear	(years)	500 × 30 × 12 × (500 × 50 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		1,000 × 30 × 12 × (1,000 × 100 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		2,000 × 30 × 12 × (2,000 × 200 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		4,000 × 30 × 12 × (4,000 × 400 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		8,000 × 30 × 12 × (8,000 × 800 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		16,000 × 30 × 12 × (16,000 × 1,600 × 30 × 12)	
	unclear	unclear		half a kalpa	
	20,000 ²	unclear		one kalpa	

Figure 14: relationship between realms of desire and form (Part b), from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharmaibhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 15. Placement of the Eight Hot Hells according to the Second Interpretation in the Great Commentary

Note that Jambudvīpa is pyramidal in shape. Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.

Figure 15: placement of the 8 hot hells according to the 2nd interpretation in the Great Commentary, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharma1bhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 18. Dwellings of the Thirty-Three Gods
 Dimensions are given in *yojanas*.

Figure 16: the abode of the 33 gods, from [Sadakata \(1997\)](#) on [Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins](#) under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharma1bhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

Fig. 20. Extent of the First Dhyāna Heavens
The broken line shows one possible meaning of "an area as broad as the four landmasses."

Figure 17: extent of the 1st Dhyāna-Heavens, from Sadakata (1997) on *Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins* under CC0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available @ https://archive.org/details/sarvastivadaabhidharma1bhikkhudhammajotik.1._961_k.

31 Realms of Existence in Theravāda Buddhism

Figure 18: A PICTORIAL representations of 31 realms of existence in accordance with Theravada Buddhist School. Source from Commons (2024e)

4.2 Transmigration & moving in circles :: Saṃsāra

The word transmigration or *Saṃsāra* has deep meaning! i reiterate the two statements below for continuity purpose.

- In simple terms, *lokas* are the realms of existence in the changing configuration of the cosmos, in the dimension of time and space, in Beloved Mother Nature!
- So, if i use this measurement of one *kṣaṇa*, i.e $\frac{1}{75}$ second, the entire configuration of the cosmos has changed, in the dimension of time and space! Now, can you see the entire change in the cosmos, that has happened in that one *kṣaṇa* ? How much deep is your awareness ?

Before we dive deeper into the aspects of transmigration or *Saṃsāra*, here, i present the existing words in Pali which contain the word transmigration and then from there on i will build and elucidate what i could grasp about the same!

As per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in Pali for **transmigration** have been found or contain the same -

- **Ara** [Vedic ara fr. ṛ, ṛṇoti; see etym. under appeti & cp. more esp. Lat. artus limb, Gr. α' ρ μ α chariot, also P. aṇṇava] the spoke of a wheel D ii.17 (sahass āra adj. with thousand spokes), cp. Miln 285; J iv.209; vi.261; Miln 238; DhA ii.142; VvA 106 (in allegorical etym. of arahant = saṃsāra - **cakkassa arānamhatattā** "breaker of the spokes of the wheel of transmigration") = PvA 7 (has saṃsāra - vaṭṭassa); VvA 277.
- **Āvattin** (adj. - n.) [fr. āvatta, cp. āvaṭṭin in diff. meaning] **returning, coming back, one who returns, in spec. meaning of one who comes back in transmigration**, syn. with āgāmin (an°), only in neg. anāvattin not returning, a non returner, with °dhamma not liable to return at D i. 156; iii.132; S v.346, 357, 376, 406; M i.91; DA i.313.
- **Khandha** [Sk. skandha] - I. Crude meaning: bulk, massiveness (gross) substance. A. esp. used (a) of an elephant: the bulk of the body, i. e. its back S i.95; vāraṇassa J iii.392; hatthi - khandha - vara - gata on the back of the state elephant J i.325; PvA 75. Also with ref. to an elephant (hatthināga) sañjāta° "to whom has grown bulk=a large back" Sn 53, expl. SnA 103 by susaṅṅhitakkhandho "well endowed with bulk." - (b) of a person: the shoulder or back: nangalaṃ khandhe karitvā S i.115 appl. to Māra; Vism 100; DhA iv.168 (ohita° - bhāra the load lifted off his shoulder). - - (c) of a tree: the trunk. rukkhassa PvA 114, also as rukkha° J i.324; tāla° the stem of a palm PvA 56; nigrodhassa khandhaja (see cpds.) S i.207=Sn 272; mūlaṃ atikkamma kh° ṃ sāraṃ pariye- sitabbaṃ "one must go beyond the root and search the trunk for sweetness" S iv.94. - (d) as t.t. in exegetical literature: section, chapter, lit. material as collected into uniform bulk; freq. in postscripts to Texts and Commentaries. See also khandhaka. - B. More general as denoting bulk (-°); e. g. aggi° a great mass of fire M ii.34, 41; J iv.139; udaka° a mass of water (i. e. ocean) A iii.336; S iv.179; J i.324; PvA 62; puñña° a great accumulation of merit A iii.336=S v.400; bhoga° a store of wealth A v.84; J i.6; maṇi° an extraordinarily large jewel (possessing magic power) J ii.102 sq. - II. Applied meaning. - A. (-°) the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense "all that is comprised under"; forming the substance of. - (a) dukkha° all that

is comprised under "dukkha," all that goes to make up or forms the substance, the idea of "ill." Most prominent in phrase ke- valassa dukkhakhandhassa samudaya and nirodha (the origin & destruction of all that is suffering) with ref. to the paṭi- casamuppāda, the chain of causal existence (q. v.) Vin i.1; S ii.95; iii.14; A i.177; v. 184 & passim. Similarly: samu- daya Vbh 135 sq. nirodha Nett 64; antakiriyā A i.147; vyādhi- maraṇatunnānaṃ dukkhakhandhaṃ vyapānudi Th 2, 162. - (b) lobha° dosa° moha° the three ingredients or integrations of greed, suffering and bewilderment, lit. "the big bulk or mass of greed" (see also under padāleti), S v.88 (nibbijhāti through the satta bojjhangā). - (c) vayo° a division of age, part of age, as threefold: purima°, majjhima°, pacchima° Nd2 in def. of sadā. - (d) sīla (etc.) kh° the 3 (or 5) groups or parts which constitute the factors of right living (dhamma), viz. (1) sīla° the group dealing with the practice of morality; (2) samādhi° that dealing with the development of concentration; (3) paññā° that dealing with the development of true wisdom. They are also known under the terms of sīla - sampadā, citta°, paññā° D i.172 sq.; see sīla. - D i.206; Nett 64 sq.; 126. tīhi dham- mehi samannāgato "possessed of the three qualities," viz. sīla - kkhandhesu, etc. It 51; cp. A i.291; v.326. tīhi khandhehi . . . aṭṭhangiko maggo sangahito M i.301; sīlakkhandhaṃ, etc. paripūreti "to fulfil the sīla - group" A i.125; ii.20, iii.15 sq. These 3 are completed to a set of 5 by (4) vimutti° the group dealing with the attainment of emancipation and (5) vimutti - nāṇa - dassana° the group dealing with the realization of the achievement of emancipation. As 1 - 4 only at D iii.229 (mis- print puñña for paññā); cp. A i.125. As 5 at S i.99=A i.162; S v.162; A iii.134, 271; v.16 (all loc.=S i.99); It 107, 108; Nd2 under sīla. B. (absolute) in individual sense: constituent element, fac- tor, substantiality. More especially as khandhā (pl.) the ele- ments or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form. Their char- acter according to quality and value of life and body is evanes- cent, fraught with ills & leading to rebirth. Paraphrased by Bdgh. as rāsi, heap, e. g. Asl. 141; Vibh A 1 f.; cf. B. Psy. 42. 1. Unspecified. They are usually enumerated in the foll. stereotyped set of 5: rūpa° (material qualities), vedanā (feeling), saññā (perception), sankhārā (coefficients of con- sciousness), viññāṇa (consciousness). For further ref. see rūpa; cp. also Mrs. Rh. D. Dhs trsl. pp. 40 - 56. They are enumerated in a different order at S i.112, viz. rūpaṃ vedayitaṃ saññaṃ viññāṇaṃ yaṃ ca sankhataṃ n' eso 'ham asmi. Detailed discussions as to their nature see e. g. S iii.101 (=Vbh 1 - 61); S iii.47; iii.86. As being comprised in each of the dhātus, viz. kāma° rūpa° arūpa - dhātu Vbh 404 sq. (a) As factors of existence (cp. bhava). Their rôle as such is illustrated by the famous simile: "yathā hi angasambhārā hoti saddo ratho iti evaṃ khandhesu santesu hoti satto ti sammuti" "just as it is by the condition precedent of the co - existence of its various parts, that the word G chariot is used, just so it is that when the skandhas are there, we talk of a G being" (Rh. D.) (cp. Hardy, Man. Buddh. p. 425) S i.135=Miln 28. Their connotation "khandha" is discussed at S iii.101 =M iii.16: "kittāvatā nu kho khandhānaṃ khandhādhivacanaṃ? rūpaṃ (etc.) atītānāgatapaccuppannaṃ ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhā vā oḷārikaṃ," etc.: i.e. material qualities are equivalent terms for the kh. What causes the manifestation of each kh.? cattāro mahābhūtā . . . paccayo rūpa - khandhassa paññāpanāya; phasso . . . vedana°, saññā°, sankhārā°, etc.; nāmarūpaṃ . . . viññāṇa°: the material elements are the cause of rūpa, touch is that of vedanā, saññā, sankhārā, name and shape that of viññāṇa (S iii.101); cp. M i.138 sq., 234 sq. On the same principle rests their division in: rūpa - kāyo rūpakkhandho nāmakāyo cattāro arūpino khandhā "the ma- terial body forms the material factor (of existence), the individualized body the 4 immaterial

factors” Nett 41; the rū- pakkhandha only is kāmadhātu - pariyāpanno: Vbh 409; the 4 arūpino kh° discussed at Ps ii.74, also at Vbh 230, 407 sq. (grouped with what is apariyāpanna) - Being the ”substantial” factors of existence, birth & death depend on the khandhas. They appear in every new conjuncture of individuality concerning their function in this paṭisandhi - kkhane; see Ps ii.72 - 76. Thus the var. phases of life in transmigra- tion are defined as - (jāti:.) ya tesam tesam sattānam tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khand- hānam pātubhāvo āyatanānam paṭilābho Nd2 on Sn 1052; cp. jāti dvīhi khandhehi sangahitā ti VvA 29; khandhānam pā- tubhāvo jāti S ii.3; Nett 29; khandhānam nibbatti jāti Vism 199. - (maraṇam:.) yā tesam tesam sattānam... cuti cavanatā bhedo antaradhānam maccu maraṇam kālakiriya khandhānam bhedo kalevarassa nikkhepo M i.49=Vbh 137=S ii.3, 42. - vivaṭṭa - **kkhandha (adj.) one whose khandhas have revolved (passed away)**, i. e. dead S i.121=iii.123. - **kh°anam udaya - vyaya (or udayabbaya) the rising and passing of the kh., transmigration** Dh 374=Th 1, 23, 379=It 120=KhA 82; Ps i.54 sq. - (b) Their relation to attachment and craving (kāma): sattisūlūpamā kāmā khandhānam adhikuṭṭanā S i.128=Th 2, 58, 141 (ThA 65: natthi tesam adhik°?); craving is their cause & soil: hetupaṭicca sambhūtā kh. S i.134; the 4 arūpino kh. are based on lobha, dosa, moha Vbh 208. - (c) their annihi- lation: the kh. remain as long as the knowledge of their true character is not attained, i. e. of their cause & removal: yaṃ rūpaṃ, etc . . . n’ etaṃ mama n’ eso ’ham asmi na m’ eso attā ti; evaṃ etaṃ yathābhūtaṃ sammappaññāya passati; evaṃ kho jānato passato . . . ahankāramamankāra - mānānusayā na hontī ti S iii.103; - pañca - kkhandhe pariññāya S iii.83; pañca - kkhandhā pariññātā tiṭṭhanti chinnamūlakā Th 2, 106. See also S i.134. - (d) their relation to dhātu (the physical el- ements) and āyatana (the elements of sense - perception) is close, since they are all dependent on sensory experience. The 5 khandhas are frequently mentioned with the 18 dhātuyo & the 12 āyatanāni: khandhā ca dh° cha ca āyatanā ime hetuṃ paṭicca sambhūtā hetubhangā nirujjhare S i.134; kh° - dh° - āyatanam sankhataṃ jātimūlam Th 2, 472; dhammam adesesi khandh’ - āyatana - dhātuyo Th 2, 43 (cp. ThA 49). Enumerated under sabba - dhammā Ps i.101=ii.230; under dhammā (states) Dhs 121, as lokuttara - kkhandhā, etc. Dhs 358, 528, 552. - khandhānam khandhattho abhiññeyyo, dhātūnam dhātuttho, etc. Ps i.17; cp. i.132; ii.121, 157. In def. of kāmāvacarā bhūmi Ps i.83. In def. of dukkha and its recog- nition Nett 57. In def. of arahanto khīṇāsavā Nd2 on sankhāta - dhammā (”kh. sankhātā,” etc.), on tiṇṇa (”khandha - (etc.) pariyante thitā”), & passim. - (e) their valuation & their bearing on the ”soul” - conception is described in the terms of na mama (na tumhākaṃ), anattā, aniccaṃ and dukkhaṃ (cp. upādānakkh° infra and rūpa) rūpaṃ (etc.). . . aniccaṃ, dukkhaṃ, n’ eso ’ham asmi, n’ eso me attā ”material qualities (etc. kh. 2 - 5) are evanescent, bad, I am not this body, this body is not my soul” Vin i.14=S iv.382. n’ eso ’ham asmi na m’ eso attā S i.112; iii.103, 130 & passim; cp. kāyo na tumhākaṃ (anattā rūpaṃ) S ii.65; Nd2 680; and rūpaṃ na tumhākaṃ S iii.33 M i.140=Nd2 680. - rūpaṃ, etc. as anattā: Vin i.13; S iii.78, 132 - 134; A i.284= ii.171; 202; cp. S iii.101; Vin i.14. - as aniccaṃ: S iii.41, 52, 102, 122, 132 sq., 181 sq., 195 sq., 202 - 224, 227; A iv.147 (aniccānupassī dukkhānupassī); anicca dukkha roga, etc., Ps ii.238 sq.; Vbh 324. - 2. Specified as panc’ upādāna-kkhandhā the factors of the fivefold cling- ing to existence. Defined & discussed in detail (rūpūpadāna - kkhandha, etc.) S iii.47; 86 - 88; also Vin i.10; S iii.127 sq. Specified S iii.58 iii.100=M iii.16; S iii.114, 158 sq.; v.52, 60; A iv.458; Vism 443 sq. (in ch. xiv: Khandha - niddesa), 611 sq. (judged aniccato, etc.). - Mentioned as a set exempli- fying the number 5: Kh iii.; Ps i.22, 122. Enumerated in var. connections S i.112; D iii.233; M i.190;

A v.52; Kh iv. (expld KhA 82=A v.52); Miln 12 (var. references concerning the discussion of the kh. in the Abhidhamma). - What is said of the khandhas alone - see above 1 (a) - (e) - is equally applied to them in connection with upādāna. - (a) As regards their origin they are characterized as chandamūlakā "rooted in desire, or in wilful desire" S iii.100; cp. yo kho... pañcas' up- ādānakkhandhesu chandarāgo taṃ tattha upādānaṃ ti M i.300, 511. Therefore the foll. attributes are characteristic: kummo pañcann' etaṃ upād° ānaṃ adhivacanaṃ M i.144; bhārā have pañcakkh°ā S iii.26; pañcavadhakā paccatthikā pañcann'... ad- hivacanaṃ S iv.174; pañc' upād° . . . sakkāyo vutto M i.299= S iv.259. - (b) their contemplation leads to the recognition of their character as dukkha, anicca, anattā: na kiñci attānaṃ vā attaniyaṃ vā pañcasu upādānakkhandhesu S iii.128; rogato, etc. . . manasikātabbā pañc° S iii.167; pañcasu upād°esu an- iccānupassī "realizing the evanescence in the 5 aggregates of attachment" A v.109; same with udayavyayānupassī S iii.130; A ii.45, 90; iii.32; iv.153; and dhammānupassī M i.61. Out of which realization follows their gradual destruction: pañc' . . . khandhānaṃ samudayo atthangamo assādo, etc. S iii.31, 160 sq.; A ii.45, 90; iv.153; Nd2 under sankhārā. That they occupy a prominent position as determinants of dukkha is evident from their rôle in the exposition of dukkha as the first one of the noble truths: sankhittena pañc'upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā "in short, the 5 kh. are associated with pain" Vin i.10=M i.48=A i.177=S v.421; Ps i.37, 39; Vbh 101 & passim; cp. katamaṃ dukkham ariyasaccaṃ? pañc'upād° ā tissa vacaniyaṃ, seyyathidaṃ . . . S iii.158=v.425; khandhādisā dukkhā Dh 202 (& expl. DhA iii.261). - 3. Separately mentioned: khandhā as tayo arūpino kh° (ved°, sañña°, sankh°) DhA i.22; viññāṇa - kh° (the skandha of discriminative consciousness) in Def. of manas: manindriyaṃ viññāṇaṃ viññ° - khandho tajjā manoviññāṇadhātu Nd2 on Sn 1142=Dhs 68.

- **Cuta** [pp. of cavati; Sk. cyuta] 1. (adj.) shifted, disappeared, deceased, passed from one existence to another Vin iv.216; Sn 774, 899; It 19, 99; J i.139, 205; Pug 17. - -accuta permanent. not under the sway of Death, Ep. of Nibbāna Dh 225. - 2. (n.) in cpd. **cutūpapāta disappearance & reappearance, transmigration**, Saṃsāra (see cuti) S ii.67 (āgatigatiyā sati c° hoti); A iii.420; iv.178; DhA i.259; usually in phrase sattānaṃ cutūpapāta - ñāṇa the discerning of the saṃsāra of beings D i.82=M i.248; D iii.111. As cutuppāta at A ii.183. Cp. jāti- saṃsāra - ñāṇa.
- **Jāti** (f.) [see janati & cp. Gr. $\gamma \epsilon \gamma \epsilon \nu \epsilon \acute{\alpha}, \gamma \acute{\epsilon} \nu \epsilon \sigma \iota \zeta$; Lat. gens; Goth. kind - ins]. - Instr. jātiyā (Sn 423) & jaccā (D ii.8; J iii.395; Dh 393); abl. jātiyā (S i.88) & jātito (by descent: D ii.8); loc. jātiyaṃ (PvA 10) & jātiyā (PvA 78). - 1. birth, rebirth, possibility of rebirth, "future life" as disposition to be born again, "former life" as cause of this life. Defined (cp. the corresp. expln of jarā) as: yā tesāṃ tesāṃ sattanaṃ tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo āyataṇānaṃ paṭilābho D ii.305 =S ii.3=Nd2 257. - Jāti is a condition precedent of age, sickness & death, and is fraught with sorrow, pain & disappointment. It is itself the final outcome of a kamma, resting on avijjā, performed in anterior births; & forms thus the concluding link in the chain of the Paṭicca - samuppāda. Under the first aspect it is enumd in various formulae, either in full or abbreviated (see Nd2 258), viz, (a) as (1) jāti, (2) jarā, (3) vyādhi, (4) maraṇa, (5) soka-paridevadukkhadomanass' upāyāsa in the dukkham ariyasaccaṃ (the noble truth of what is misfortune) Vin i.10; A i.176; iii.416; °dhamma destined to be born, etc. M i.161 sq., 173; - A v.216; Nd2 258, 304, 630, etc., in var. connections (referring to some dukkha). - (b) as Nos.

1 - 4: Nd2 254, 494b; J i.168, etc. - (c) as Nos. 1, 2, 4 (the standard quotation, implying the whole series 1 - 5): S v.224; A v.144; jātipaccayā jarāmarañam Vin i.1; D ii.31, 57, etc.; °ika A ii.11, 173; °īya M i.280; Nd2 40. - (d) to this is sometimes added (asuming up) saṃsāra: Nd2 282f; cp. kiccham loko āpanno jāyati ca jīyati ca mīyati ca cavati ca uppajjati ca D ii.30. - (e) as Nos. 1+4: pahīna - jātimaraṇa (adj.) (=free from life & death, i. e. saṃsāra) A i.162; °bhayassa pāraga A ii.15; °kovida Sn 484; atāri °m asesam Sn 355 (cp. 500); °assa pāraga Sn 32. - (f)=e+saṃsāra (cp. d): sattā gacchanti saṃsāram jātimaraṇagāmino A ii.12=52; jātimaraṇasaṃsāram ye vajanti punappunam . . . avijjāy' eva sā gati Sn 729. - (g) as Nos. 1+2, which implies the whole series: atāri so jātijaram A i.133= Sn 1048; jātijar' upaga Sn 725=It 106; saṃyojanam jātijarāya chetvā It 42; - Sn 1052, 1060; Dh 238, 348; cp. jāti ādinā nihīna PvA 198. - Other phrases & applications: Various rebirths are seen by one who has perfect insight into all happening & remembers his former existences (D i.81; iii.50; A i.164; M ii.20). Arahantship implies the impossibility of a future rebirth: see formula khīṇā jāti (M i.139; Sn p. 16, etc.) and arahant ii.A: jātiyā parimuccati S i.88; jātim bhabbo pahātuṃ A v.144 sq. - antimā jāti the last rebirth D ii.15 (cp. carima); purimā j. a former existence PvA 1; atītajātiyam in a former life (=pure) PvA 10. On jāti as dukkha see Vism 498 - 501. - 2. descent, race, rank, genealogy (cp. φ u η, genus), often combd w. gotta. Two grades of descent are enumd at Vin iv.6 as hīnā jāti (low birth), consisting of Candāḷa, Veṇa, Nesāda, Rathakāra & Pukkusa; and ukkaṭṭhā j. (superior birth), comprising Khattiyas & Brāhmaṇas. - The var. meanings of jāti are given by Bdgh at Vism 498, 499 in the foll. classification (with examples) bhava, nikāya, sankhata - lakkhaṇa, paṭisandhi, pasūti, kula, ariya - sīla. - Kim hi jāti karissati? What difference makes his parentage? D i.121; jāti - rājāno kings of birth, genuine kings J i.338; na nam jāti nivāresi brahmalok' ūpapattiyā Sn 139; jātim akkhāhi tell me the rank of his father & mother Sn 421, 1004; cp. 462; na jaccā vasalo hoti Sn 136; 142; id. w. brāhmaṇo Sn 650; with nāma & gotta in the description of a man jātiyā nāmena gottena, etc. Vin iv.6; jātito nāmato gottato by descent, personal & family name D ii.8; cp. jāti - gotta - kula J ii.3. See also j. - vāda. - 3. a sort of, kind of (cp. jāta 3): catujātigandha four kinds of scent J i.265; ii.291. - 4. (jāti°) by (mere) birth or nature, natural (opp. artificial); or genuine, pure, excellent (opp. adulterated, inferior), cp. jāta 1 (b): in cpds., like °maṇi, °vīṇā, etc. - **saṃsāra the cycle of transmigration, the saṃsāra of rebirths** (see above 1 d. f.): **pahīna left behind, overcome (by an Arahant)** M i.139; A iii.84, 86; °m khetvā id. Th 2, 168; vitiṇṇo j.° n' atthi tassa punabbhavo Sn 746;

- **Parinibbāna** (nt.) [pari+nibbāna] "complete Nibbāna" in two meanings: 1. **complete extinction of khandhalife; i. e. all possibility of such life & its rebirth, final release from (the misery of) rebirth and transmigration, death (after the last life - span of an Arahant). This is the so - called "an - upādi - sesa Parinibbāna,"** or "extinction with no rebirth - sub-stratum left."- 2. **release from cravings & attachment to life, emancipation (in this life) with the assurance of final death; freedom of spirit, calm, perfect well - being or peace of soul. This is the so - called "sa - upādisesa - P,"** or "extinction (of passion) with some substratum left."- The two kinds are distinguished by Bdgh at DhA ii.163 as follows: "arahatta - pattito paṭṭhāya kilesa - vaṭṭassa khetitattā sa - upādi - sesena, carima - citta - nirodhena khandhavatṭassa khetitattā an - upādi - sesena cā ti dvīhi pi parinibbānehi parinibbutā, an - upādāno viya padīpo apanṇattika - bhā-vaṃ gatā." - 1. D ii.72 sq. (the famous **Mahā - parinibbāna - suttanta** or "**Book of the Great Decease**"); M iii.127, 128; A ii.79

(°samaye); iii.409 (°dhamma, contrasted with āpāyikanerayika, cp. DhA iv.42); Mhvs 7, 1 (°mañcamhi nipanna); VvA 158; PvA 244. - 2. D iii.55; A v.64; Sn 514 (°gata+ vitiṇṇa - kankho); Vv 5324 (°gata+sītibhūta). This state of final emancipation (during life) has also received the determination of anupādā - parinibbāna, i. e. emancipation without ground. for further clinging (lit. without fuel), which corresponds to Bdgh's term "kilesavattassa khep-itattā sa - upādi - sesa p." (see above); thus at M i.148; S iv.48; v.29; A i.44; v.65 (nicchāto nibbuto sītibhūto etc.); A v.233=253=Dh 89 (+khīṇāsava).

- **Vatṭa**¹ (adj. - nt.) [pp. of vṛt, Sk. vṛtta in meaning of "round" as well as "happened, become" etc. The two meanings have become differentiated in Pāli: vatṭa is not found in meaning of "happened." All three Pāli meanings are specialized, just as the pres. vatṭati is specialized in meaning "behoves"] 1. round, circular; (nt.) circle PvA 185 (āyata+); KhA 50 (°nāli). See cpd.°anguli. - 2. (fig.) **"rolling on," the "round" of existences, cycle of transmigrations, saṃsāra, evolution** (=involution) (as forward or ascending circle of existences, without implying a teleological idea, in contrast to vivaṭṭa "rolling back" or devolution, i. e. a new (descending) cycle of existence in a new aeon with inverted [vi -] motion, so to speak) S iii.63; iv.53 (pariyādiṇṇa°), cp. M iii.118; Th 1, 417 (sabba°: "all constant rolling on" trsln); SnA 351 (=upādāna); DhsA 238. - There are 3 vatṭas, (te - bhūmaka vatṭa, see also tivatṭa) embracing existence in the stages of kamma- vatṭa, kilesa° and vipāka°, or circle of deed, sin & result (found only in Commentarial literature): KhA 189; SnA 510 (tebhūmaka°); DhA i.289 (kilesa°); iv.69 (tebhūmaka°). See also Māra; and °dukkha, °vivaṭṭa below. - 3. "what has been proffered," expenditure, alms (as t. t.) J vi.333 (dāna° alms - gift); DhA ii.29 (pāka° cooked food as alms); VvA 222 (id.); Mhvs 32, 61 (alms - pension); 34, 64 (salāka - vatṭabhatta). - Cp. vi°. **-dukkha the "ill" of transmigration** (a Commentary expression) Vism 315; DhA iv.149; VvA 116.
- **Saṃyojana** (nt.) [fr. saṃyuñjati] bond, fetter S iv.163 etc.; especially **the fetters that bind man to the wheel of transmigration** Vin i.183; S i.23; v.241, 251; A i.264; iii.443; iv.7 sq. (diṭṭhi°); M i.483; Dh 370; It 8 (taṇhā); Sn 62, 74, 621; J i.275; ii.22; Nett 49; DhA iii.298; iv.49. The ten fetters are (1) sakkāyadīṭṭhi; (2) vicikicchā; (3) sīlabbataparāmāso; (4) kāmacchando; (5) vyāpādo; (6) rūparāgo; (7) arūparāgo; (8) māno; (9) uddhaccaṃ; (10) avijjā. The first three are the tīṇi saṃyojanāni - e. g. M i.9; A i.231, 233; D i.156; ii.92 sq., 252; iii.107, 132, 216; S v.357, 376, 406; Pug 12, 15; Nett 14; Dhs 1002; DA i.312. The seven last are the satta saṃyojanāni, Nett. 14. The first five are called orambhāgiyāni - e. g. A i.232 sq.; ii.5, 133; v.17; D i.156; ii.92, 252; M i.432; S v.61, 69; Th 2, 165; Pug 17. The last five are called uddhambhāgiyāni - e. g. A v.17; S v.61, 69; Th 2, 167; ThA 159; Pug 22; Nett 14, 49. A different enumeration of the ten saṃyojanas, at Nd2 657=Dhs 1113, 1463 (kāmarāga, paṭigha, māna, diṭṭhi, vicikicchā, sīlabbataparāmāsa, bhavarāga, issā, macchariya, avijjā); compare, however, Dhs 1002. A diff. enumn of seven saṃyojanas at D iii.254 & A iv.7, viz. anunaya°, paṭigha°, diṭṭhi°, vicikicchā°, māna°, bhavarāga°, avijjā°. A list of eight is found at M i.361 sq. Cp. also ajjhata-saṃyojano & bahiddhāsaṃyojano puggalo A i.63 sq.; Pug 22; kiṃ-su-s° S i.39= Sn 1108.

We will come back to these terminologies at a later stage in this monograph, where i will explain the terms in BLUE and the context behind it! Below are the images of representations of *Saṃsāra* in figs. 19 and 20.

Figure 19: *Samsāra* as represented in Commons (2025i)

Figure 20: *Samsāra* as represented in Commons (2025h). The Bhavachakra showing 6 realms of existence in which a being can reincarnate according to rebirth perspectives of Buddhism. Buddhist god Yama face is at the top of the outer rim. The outer rim shows the 12 *nidānas* of the *Paṭcca-Samuppāda* or the teachings of the dependent origination of the Shakyamuni Buddha. The image / painting is from Bhutan.

The word **transmigrate** has its root in **Latin**, i.e **transmigrare** which is the **composition of the words, trans** meaning "across" and **migrare** or "to move or migrate". In **English**, it is the **movement**

- The **dot . . .** is **LIFE**
- The **encasement / encapsulation . . .** is a **CONFIGURATION** of the **COSMOS**

Figure 21: A PICTORIAL representation of the CHANGING CONFIGURATION of COSMOS in time and space, that ENCAPSULATES LIFE, however LIFE itself remains UNTOUCHED!

from one place to another OR passing of soul from one body to another. Now, let's drop the terminology of "soul" for a moment. Just let's look @ LIFE itself!

One says that one has passed from one body to another, INCLUDING the existence in the intermediate realm of the unseen. So are a few questions to ask oneself -

Φ WHAT transmigrated? . . . LIFE?

Φ Did LIFE REALLY move from one place to another?

Φ You say . . . mother / father PASSED AWAY! IS IT TRUE? DID they REALLY PASS AWAY?

Lets look at this image in fig. 21. The dot represents LIFE and the ENCAPSULATION / ENCASUREMENT is the CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS at ONE MOMENT in TIME. So, i have represented a CONFIGURATION with a particular colour. Next, in one *kṣaṇa* (i.e. $\frac{1}{75}$ second), the ENTIRE CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS CHANGES, here represented by a DIFFERENT COLOUR and a SHIFT of 20° or degrees. So LIFE or the principle of LIFE, DOES NOT MOVE! IT is STILL and the CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS in Beloved Mother NATURE . . . CHANGES, and CHANGES, and CHANGES . . .! Again, . . . in one *kṣaṇa* (i.e. $\frac{1}{75}$ second), the ENTIRE CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS CHANGES . . . and so on, and so forth! Further, if you have meditated long in this life, sincerely and / or at advanced level, due to sustained meditations [may be for life times], it will come to observation or sight (*Anupassanā*) that the human body (*kāya*) [or for that matter any form i.e. *rūpa* encapsulating life within] . . . is a PARTICULAR FREQUENCY WAVE. That particular frequency wave, . . . has APPEARED, STAYS / PERSISTS

& DISSOLVES . . . It HOLDS on to the LIFE within for a certain period of time. Once that time is over, the frequency dissolves . . . Depending on the deeds of that frequency, the new body is acquired within another frequency in the changing configuration of COSMOS, stamped by time and space.

Again, as per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in which have been used in the foregoing paragraph, have their meanings below -

- **Bhagavant** (adj. n.) [cp. Vedic bhagavant, fr. bhaga] fortunate, illustrious, sublime, as Ep. and title "Lord." Thus applied to the Buddha (amhākaṃ Bh.) and his predecessors. **Occurs with extreme frequency**; of fanciful exegetic explns of the term & its meaning we mention e. g. those at Nd1 142=Nd2 466; Vism 210 sq.; DA i.33 sq. Usual trs. Blessed One, Exalted One.
- **Upaṭṭhita** [pp. of upaṭṭhahati or upaṭiṭṭhāti, cp. BSk. upa-sthita Divy 281, 342] - 1. **furnished provided, served, got ready, honoured** with Sn 295 (°asmiṃ yaññasmiṃ); J v.173 (an- nena pānena); Pv i.52 (= sajjita paṭiyatta PvA 25); ii.98 (= payirupāsita PvA 116); PvA 132. - 2. **come, come about, appeared, arrived; present, existing** Sn 130 (bhattachāle upaṭṭhite when mealtime has come), 898; Dh 235; Miln 274; PvA 124 (dānakāle °e). - 3. **standing up (ready), keeping in readiness** M i.77; A ii.206; Sn 708 (= ṭhito C.); Pv ii.953 (ready for service, serving, waiting upon cp. PvA 135. -sati with ready attention, one whose attention is fixed, concentrated Vin i.63; D iii.252, 282; S iv.186; A iii. 251; Pug 25.
- **Parivasati** [pari+vas2] **to stay, dwell, to live under probation** Vin iii.186 (grd. °vatthabba); iv.30, 127; D i.176; M i.391; S ii.21; Sn 697 (=pabbajitvā tāpasavesena vasati SnA 490). - ppr. med. paribbasāna; pp. parivutṭha & parivuttha (q. v.).
- **Parivāsa** [fr. pari+vas2, cp. Epic Sk. parivāsa only in meaning 1] 1. **sojourn; stay**, in phrase vipassanā° DhA iii.118; DhsA 215. - 2. **period under probation, (living under) probation** Vin iii.186 (°m vasati, cp. parivuttha); iv.30; S ii.21 (°m vasati). °m deti to allow probation Vin i.49; ii.7; iv.30, 127; °m yācati to ask for probation Vin iv.30, 127. - samodhāna° inclusive probation Vin ii.48 sq.; suddhanta° probation of complete purification Vin ii.59 sq. - 3. period, time (lit. stay), interval, duration Ud 7 (eka - ratti°). -dāna the allowance of probation A i.99.
- **Parivāsika** (adj.) [fr. pari+vas2, see parivasati] 1. **"staying," i. e. usual, accustomed, common** SnA 35 (°bhatta; or is it "fermented," and thus to be taken to No. 3?); a° unusual, new, uncommon J ii.435 (where it is combd with abhinava, which should be substituted for readings accuṇḥa, abbhunḥa & ab- hiṇḥa according to similar expln of paccaggha at PvA 87), with v. l. samparivāsita (well - seasoned?). - 2. **a probationer** Vin ii.162. In this meaning usually spelt pāri° (q. v.). - 3. in combn cira° (with ref. to food) it may be interpreted either as **"staying long, being in use for a long time,"** i. e. stale; or it may be derived fr. vāsa3 (odour, perfume or seasoning) and translated (so Mrs. Rh. D. in Expositor 63, 64) **"long - fermented"** (better "seasoned"?) DhsA 48 (°vāsika & vāsiya); ThA 29.
- **Parivutṭha & °vuttha** [pp. of parivasati] **staying (a period), living (for a time), spending (or having spent) one's probation** (cp. BSk. paryuṣita - parivāsa AvŚ i.259) Vin iii.186 (tth); S ii.21 (ṭṭh).

- **Vasati2** [vas2; Idg. * υ es to stay, abide; cp. Av. varGhaiti; Lat. Vesta the goddess of the hearth=Gr. $\epsilon\sigma\tau\iota\alpha$ hearth; Goth. wisan to stay, remain, be (=Ohg. wasan, E. was, were); Oicel. vist to stay, Oir. foss rest. - Dhtm 470: kanti - nivāsesu] **to live, dwell, stay, abide; to spend time** (esp. with vassaṃ the rainy season); trs. **to keep, observe, live, practise** Sn 469 sq., 1088 (=saṃvasati āvasati parivasati Nd2 558); PvA 3, 12, 78 (imper. vasatha). - uposathaṃ vasaṃ (ppr.) keeping the Sunday J vi.232; brahmacariyaṃ v. to live a chaste life M i.515 (cp. same expression Ait. Br. 5, 13; Śat. Br. 12, 2, 2; 13, 8. 22). - ppr. vasanto PvA 75, 76; ppr. med. vasamāna J i.21, 236, 291; PvA 117; Pot. vaseyya M i.515; Pv ii.97 (ghare), & vase Miln 372. - aor. vasi Sn 977; J iv.317 (piya - saṃvāsaṃ); PvA 111; Mhvs 1, 13 (vasī vasi); 5, 229. - ger. vasitvā J i.278; iv.317; PvA 13; grd. vasitabba Sn 678; PvA 42; & vatthabba Mhvs 3, 12; inf. vatthum Th 2, 414, & vasitum PvA 12, 112. Fut. vasissati [=Sk. vasiṣyati] Mhvs 14, 26; PvA 12; and (older) vacchati [=Sk. vatsyati] Vin i.60; Th 2, 294; J iv.217; 1st sg. vacchāmi J v.467 (na te v. santike); vi.523, 524, & vacchaṃ Th 2, 414. - Pass. vussati [Sk. uṣyate] M i.147 (brahmacariyaṃ v.). - pp. vasita, vusita [=vi+uṣita], vuttha [perhaps=vi+uṣṭa], q. v. - Caus. I. vāseti to cause to live, stay or dwell; to make live; to preserve (opp. nāseti at S iv.248) Vin iii.140; S iv.248; Miln 211; PvA 160 (inf. vāsetum); see also vāseti2. - Caus. II. vasāpeti (cp. ad- hivāsāpeti) to make live or spend, to cause to dwell, to detain J i.290; ii.27; PvA 20 (vassaṃ). - pp. vāsita. - See also adhi°, ā°, ni°, pari°.
- **Viharati** [vi+harati] **to stay, abide, dwell, sojourn (in a certain place); in general: to be, to live; appld: to behave, lead a life** (as such expld with "iriyati" at Vism 16). Synonyms are given at Vbh 194 with iriyati, vattati, pāleti, yapeti, yāpeti, carati; cp. VbhA 262. - See e. g. D i.251; Sn 136, 301, 925; Pug 68; DhsA 168; DA i.70, 132; PvA 22, 67, 78. - Special Forms: aor. 3rd sg. vihāsi Sn p. 16; Pv ii.960; Mhvs 5, 233; PvA 54, 121; 3rd pl. vihimsu Th 1, 925, & vihaṃsu A ii.21; fut. viharissati A iii.70; vihessati Th 1, 257; vihissati Th 2, 181; and vihāhisi J i.298 (doubtful reading!), where C. expls as "vijahissati, parihāyissati"; with phrase sukhaṃ vihāhisi cp. dukkhaṃ viharati at A i.95, and see also vihāhesi. - pp. not found.
- **Vihāra** [fr. viharati] 1. (as m. & adj.) **spending one's time (so- journeying or walking about), staying in a place, living; place of living, stay, abode (in general)** VvA 50 (jala°); PvA 22, 79; eka° living by oneself S ii.282 sq.; janghā° wandering on foot PvA 73; divā° passing the time of day Sn 679; PvA 142. See also below 3 a. - 2. (appld meaning) state of life, condition, mode of life (in this meaning almost identical with that of vāsa2), e. g. ariya° best condition S v.326; SnA 136; dibba° supreme condition (of heart) Miln 225; brahma° divine state S v.326; SnA 136; Vism 295 sq. (ch. ix.); phāsu° comfort A iii.119, 132; sukha° happiness S iii.8; v.326; A i.43; ii.23; iii.131 sq.; iv.111 sq., 230 sq.; v.10 sq. See further D i.145, 196; iii.220 (dibba, brahma, ariya), 250 (cha satata°), 281; S ii.273 (jhāna°); iii.235 (id.); A iii.294 (°m kappeti to live one's life); Ps ii.20; Nett 119 sq. - 3. (a) a habitation for a Bud- dhist mendicant, an abode in the forest (arañña°), or a hut; a dwelling, habitation, lodging (for a bhikkhu), a single room Vin ii.207 sq.; D ii.7; A iii.51, 299 (yathāvihāraṃ each to his apartment); Sn 220 (dūra° a remote shelter for a bhikkhu), 391; Vism 118 (different kinds; may be taken as c.). - (b) place for convention of the bhikkhus, meeting place; place for rest & recreation (in garden or park) DA i.133. - (c) (later) a larger building for housing bhikkhus, an organized monastery, a Vi- hāra Vin i.58; iii.47; S i.185 (°pāla the guard of the monastery); J i.126; Miln 212; Vism 292; DhA i.19 (°cārikā visit to the monastery), 49

(°pokkharañī), 416; Mhvs 19, 77; PvA 12, 20, 54, 67, 141. 151; and passim. See also Dictionary of Names. The modern province Behar bears its name from the vihāras.

- **Nirujjhati** [Pass. of nirundhati (nirodhati) ni+rundhati] **to be broken up, to be dissolved, to be destroyed, to cease, die** Vin i.1; D i.180 sq., 215; ii.157; S iii.93 (aparisesam); iv.36 sq., 60, 98, 184 sq.; 294, 402; v.213 sq.; A iii.165 sq. (aparisesam); v.139 sq.; J i.180; Pug 64; Sdhp 606. - pp. niruddha. Cp. nirodha.
- **Vilaya** [vi+laya, cp. liyati] **dissolution**; °m gacchati, as much as: "to be digested," to be dissolved Miln 67. - adj. dissolved, dispersed Dpvs i.65.
- **Visiveti** [vi+siveti, which corresponds to Sk. vi - śyāpayati (lex- icogr!), **Caus. of śyā, śyāyati to coagulate; lit. to dissolve, thaw.** The v stands for p; śyā is contracted to sī] to warm oneself Miln 47; J ii.68; DhA i.225, 261; ii.89. As visibbeti (in analogy to visibbeti to sew) at Vin iv.115. - Caus. II. visivāpeti J ii.69.
- **Samvattati** [sam+vattati] 1. **to be evolved, to be in a process of evolution** (opp. vivattati in devolution) D i.17; iii.84, 109; A ii.142; DA i.110. - 2. **to fall to pieces, to come to an end (like the world's destruction), to pass away, perish, dissolve** (intrans.) J iii.75 (paṭhavī s.; v. l. samvaddh°); Miln 287 (ākāso °eyya). For samvatt° at J i.189 read samvaddh°.
- **Dhāraka** (adj. - n.) 1. **bearing, one who holds or possesses** DhA iii.93 (sampattim). - 2. **one who knows or remembers** A ii.97 (°jātika); iv.296 sq., 328 (id.).
- **Pāleti** [cp. (Epic) Sk. pālayati, fr. pā] 1. to protect, guard, watch, keep Sn 585; J i.55; iv.127; vi.589; Miln 4 (paṭhavī lokam pāleti, perhaps in meaning **"keeps, holds, encircles,"** similar to meaning 2); Sdhp 33. - 2. (lit. perhaps "to see through safely"; for palāyati by false analogy) **to go on, to move, to keep going**, in defn of carati as viharati, iriyati, vattati, pāleti, yapeti, yāpeti at Nd2 237; Vbh 252; DhsA 167. Cp. pālana. So also in phrase attham pāleti (so read for paleti?) "to come home" i. e. to disappear Sn 1074 (see expld Nd2 28). See other refs. under palāyati. - pp. pālita. See also abhi° & pari°. A contracted (poetical) form is found as pallate at J v.242, expld by C. as pālayati (pālayate), used as Med. - Pass.

Φ Then what is the NEXT QUESTION to ASK?

Φ WHAT is impermanent i.e *aniccā*, the CHANGING CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS . . . or . . . LIFE or the principle of LIFE AS-IT-IS, i.e *Yathā-bhūta*?

LIFE . . . IS . . . [PERIOD] It reverberates through and through . . . you say father or mother PASSED AWAY ??? NO . . . NOT at all! . . . The CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS CHANGED and the impermanent i.e *aniccā* , BODY DISSOLVED or DECAYED or DISINGTEGRATED! You HOLDING on i.e *Upādāna* , to ONE particular CONGIFURATION of COSMOS causes you DEEP MISERY and SORROW i.e *Dukkha* ! And you continue to do this ONE life after another . . . WHILE being UNABLE to see i.e *Anupassanā* , the TRUTHS of LIFE AS-IT-IS or *Yathā-bhūta*.

In the *Khuddakanikāya, of the Dhammapada Verses of Dhamma 146-156, Jarāvagga (Chapter on Decay, 11), Visākhāyasahāyikānaṃvatthu, Udānavatthu*, So said the Buddha -

Anekajātisamsāraṃ, sandhāvissaṃ anibbisam,

Transmigrating or moving in circles, through countless births and rebirths in different genealogy
. . .
while running through / transmigrating, not finding . . .

Gahakāraṃ gavesanto, dukkhā jāti punappunam!

looking for the house builder (the one who builds on the craving / hunger / thirst, in the body) .
. . .
again and again, the countless births and rebirths in different genealogy, were fraught with pain /
entailing sorrow or trouble / unpleasant / causing misery!

Gahakāraka diṭṭhosi! puna geham na kāhasi?

Now, grasped and seen, O! house builder (the one who builds on the craving / hunger / thirst, in
the body) . . .
Where again? Will you, make enter / allow to enter / usher in OR leave behind / to give up, a
dwelling / hut / house?

Sabbā te phāsukā bhaggā, gahakūṭam visaṅkhatam!

With all the ribs broken . . .
the topmost point or the a trap / a snare / falsehood / deceit, of the house, . . .
is lost / asundered / disturbed, that was put together / compounded / conditioned / produced by a
combination of causes / created / brought about as effect of actions in former births!

Visaṅkhāragatam cittam, taṇhānam khayamajjhagā!

Thus, losing / asundering / disturbing, that was put together / compounded / conditioned / pro-
duced by a combination of causes / created / brought about as effect of actions in former births, . . .
now gone in a certain way / affected / behaved / fared / fated / being in or having come into a state
or condition, . . .
of the heart (psychologically), i. e. the centre & focus of one's emotional nature and intellectual
element which inheres in & accompanies its manifestations; i. e. thought . . .
i came to / got to / found / obtained / experienced, . . .
waste, destruction, consumption; decay, ruin, loss; of the passing away of night; with reference to
the extinction of passions & such elements as condition, life, & rebirth, . . .
of craving / hunger / thirst!

Transmigration or running in cycles i.e *samsāra* is NOTHING, but the LIFE WITHIN YOU . . .
MOVING in CYCLES . . . BEING STUCK WITH the CONFIGURATION of the COSMOS . . .
in Beloved Mother NATURE!

Now, if you JUST look at this WORD *Parinibbāna*, as mentioned above . . . it says . . .

”complete Nibbāna” in two meanings: 1. complete extinction of khandhalife; i. e. all possibility of such life & its rebirth, final release from (the misery of) rebirth and transmigration, death (after the last life - span of an Arahant). This is the so - called ”an - upādi - sesa Parinibbāna,” or ”extinction with no rebirth - sub-stratum left.” 2. release from cravings & attachment to life, emancipation (in this life) with the assurance of final death; freedom of spirit, calm, perfect well - being or peace of soul. This is the so - called ”sa - upādisesa - P.,” or ”extinction (of passion) with some substratum left.”

In this context, i will QUOTE a paragraph of an article titled - **Prajna-paramita-hridaya / The Heart sutra : Bhagavati, the heart of transcendental knowledge**, released in **October of 2016**, @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which was developed and has a context in the web-page @ <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinha/shriprakashsinha/friendship-1st-teachings-sutta-nipata>. The following is the text

But does one see the essence of the teachings? The former buddha is now using the stepping stones of the great cycle which he has already experienced and uses his own body as a foundation stone to unlock the cycle. The kaya or body which is a form of ignorance has now become the stepping stone for meditation. The grip of the body comes to awareness and passes off. So on and so forth with the other aspects of sensations and mind.

A stage comes when there are no wants to go for, no search to go on, no journey to be taken and no effort to be put forth. There is nothing to say, nothing to do and nothing to become. Even the search for nirvana stops. In those moments, the inexplicable state of nirvana manifests. Awareness tastes some nectars in silence. Contentment dawns in awareness and so does abundance as one re-enters the limited domain of nature. Now, even if nirvana happens once, the mind can still be impure and this is not the fully liberated stage. This stage is called *Saupadisesa-nibbana*. Depending on the individual further stages pass by in time. This journey is long and a slow process for those who wish to walk the slow and a natural path.

It has been heard that Siddhartha begins his journey one million life times back to the stage of bodhisattva (*nirvana* experienced for the first time). As a bodhisattva, he begins perfecting the knowledge of unlocking the cycle of *samsara*, life after life. In the last life as Siddhartha, buddhahood dawns in him. *Now an important point is this. If you want to become a Buddha you will never become. But when the heart experiences and realizes that there is nothing to become, then the journey into buddhahood has already begun.* He wants to enter parinirvana at the age of 36, but extends his life for a few more years for the benefit of others. Finally, living a life of Buddha for just one life time, he enters *parinirvana*. There is no desire to live many lives as a Buddha also. The journey ends as truth absorbs him completely, erasing his entire existence. So, *nirvana* has already been experienced, but previous impressions force the being to again enter the school of *samsara* to finish what needs to be finished (stage of *saupadisesa-nibbana*). Life flips between *samsara* and *nirvana* as the balance is maintained. Entering *parinirvana*, this flipping stops.

Now, lets get back to the context of this . . . Transmigration. The Buddha says . . . and i repeat a few words from the above . . .

Anekajātisamsāraṃ, sandhāvissaṃ anibbisam,

Transmigrating or moving in circles, through countless births and rebirths in different genealogy
...
while running through / transmigrating, not finding . . .

Gahakāraṃ gavesanto, dukkhā jāti punappunam!

looking for the house builder (the one who builds on the craving / hunger / thirst, in the body) .
...
again and again, the countless births and rebirths in different genealogy, were fraught with pain /
entailing sorrow or trouble / unpleasant / causing misery!

and then ONE fine MOMENT, ONE DAY that RUNNING STOPPED FOREVER! In the STILL-
NESS of AWARENESS, "complete Nibbāna" happened, FULL LIBERATION transpired and BUD-
DHAHOOD dawned in Siddhartha! The final chapter of his long journey from Hermit Sumedha to
. . . Siddhartha to . . . the Shakyamuni Buddha had CULMINATED, with him DROPPING or RE-
NOUNCING the PRINCIPLE of LIFE itself and GETTING ERASED in the Absolute Truth . . . i.e
Parinibbāna. For those interested, in the JOURNEY of Hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha, please study
the article titled - **Chapter # 2 : From hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha • The journey of a thou-
sand li commenced with a single step : 千里之行始于足下- 老子, Lao Tzu • A journey of four
incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons @ <http://osf.io/8hn5e/files/g8bdc>.**

Lastly, to reiterate the same which started the topic, i.e The word transmigration or *Samsāra* has
deep meaning! i repeat the two statements below for continuity purpose.

- In simple terms, *lokas* are the realms of existence in the changing configuration of the cosmos,
in the dimension of time and space, in Beloved Mother Nature!
- So, if i use this measurement of one *kṣaṇa*, i.e $\frac{1}{75}$ second, the entire configuration of the
cosmos has changed, in the dimension of time and space! Now, can you see the entire change
in the cosmos, that has happened in that one *kṣaṇa* ? How much deep is your awareness ?

For this, the plot of rotation of galaxy curve is shown in fig. 22, which depicts the CHANGE in the
CONFIGURATION of a part of COSMOS in Beloved Mother Nature, over the dimension of time
and space!

Figure 22: A **galaxy rotation curve** is a plot of the orbital speeds of visible stars or gas versus their radial distance from the galactic center. Source from Commons (2026o) and there are ADDITIONAL 10 references for this image.

4.3 The Cessation or STOPPING of the Transmigration & moving in circles :: The story of Aṅgulimāla

So said the Buddha :: **I have stopped, Aṅgulimāla . . .** (the one who wore 999 cut fingers weaved into a necklace, while waiting for the last one . . .)

In the following 4 episodes, I present here a succinct account of the story of Aṅgulimāla.

4.3.1 Episode # 1

- ☞ the gem Ahiṃsaka (the harmless one), who was forced to become a ruthless brigand & murderer, due to . . .
- ☞ the jealousy of his peers who plotted with the narrative of Ahiṃsaka seducing the teacher's wife . . .
- ☞ & vindictive / venomous schemes of an evil teacher . . . who forced Ahiṃsaka to pay GURU DAKSHINA (payment for completion of studies under him) by ASKING him to bring 1000 (ONE THOUSAND) fingers . . . EACH from a different human as PAYMENT . . . to GET FINAL APPROVAL of his certification by the teacher, while the INTENTION was that Ahiṃsaka be KILLED in the GRISLY act . . .

4.3.2 Episode # 2

- ☞ Thus Ahiṃsaka TURNED into the DREADED Aṅgulimāla!

4.3.3 Episode # 3

- ☞ @ 999, the mother planning to save Ahiṃsaka, from COMPLETING the TASK of obtaining 1000 fingers tries to find him, while Ahiṃsaka was DETERMINED to kill anyone. [IF MOTHER was in FRONT, he would KILL MOTHER ALSO]
- ☞ The Buddha perceiving this as an IMPENDING DISASTER . . . if MATRICIDE would happen, Aṅgulimāla would be DOOMED and UNSAVABLE as his MOTHER would be the 1000th to be KILLED MERCILESSLY!
- ☞ So appearing in front of the DREADED Aṅgulimāla, while MOTHER was there, . . . the Buddha WALKED SLOWLY, while Aṅgulimāla kept on RUNNING BEHIND him, but COULD NEVER REACH the Buddha!
- ☞ EXASPERATED . . . Aṅgulimāla shouts :: STOP RUNNING you COWARD! Why are you RUNNING AWAY?
- ☞ So said the Buddha :: I have STOPPED Aṅgulimāla . . . YOU STOP!
- ☞ Aṅgulimāla says :: I will CUT your FINGER and KILL you!
- ☞ the Buddha LOOKED at his fingers and POINTS 10 fingers at him and ASKS :: WHICH FINGER do you WANT ?

- ☒ Āṅgulimāla was **STUNNED** as for the **FIRST TIME** he met someone who **DID NOT VALUE** his **LIFE** and had **NO FEAR!**
- ☒ **Later the Buddha asks Āṅgulimāla . . . :: CAN you DO ONE THING for me ? PLUCK a BRANCH from a TREE!**
- ☒ **Āṅgulimāla says :: WHAT is the BIG DEAL ?**
- ☒ . . . and he goes and **PLUCKS** the **BRANCH** and brings it back to the Buddha!
- ☒ **the Buddha SMILES and says :: GOOD! NOW go BACK and PUT it BACK into the TREE where you GOT it FROM!**
- ☒ **Āṅgulimāla says :: THIS is IMPOSSIBLE! WHAT are you SAYING!**
- ☒ the Buddha says :: **EXACTLY! YOU should NEVER do an IRREVERSIBLE PROCESS in Beloved MOTHER Nature! HOW can you TAKE LIFE, when YOU DO NOT HAVE the POWER to GIVE BACK or RESTORE life, of WHOM you have TAKEN MERCILESSLY!**
- ☒ Āṅgulimāla **SHOOK INTERNALLY! AS IF his BEING WAS SHAKEN to the core . . . HIS CONSCIENCE was SHOT WITH THE ARROW of GRUESOME acts he had DONE and INFLICTED MISERY into the LIVES of many ORDINARY and INNOCENT ONES!**
- ☒ Āṅgulimāla **FELL @ Buddha's FEET . . . asking to SAVE HIM!**
- ☒ Āṅgulimāla **STOPPED** that day . . . and choose to change the course of his life . . .

4.3.4 Episode # 4

- ☒ **HOWEVER**, though transformed . . . **KARMA** had its own way . . .
- ☒ **WHEREVER** the **MONK Āṅgulimāla** would go . . . **DEEP HATRED** followed him!
- ☒ **ASKING** for **ALMS** . . . people would **THROW STONES** at him for **ALMS** and he **WOULD BLEED** profusely . . .
- ☒ **SOMETIMES** he was **BEATEN** with **STICK** by many . . .
- ☒ One day . . . he **RETURNED** to **BUDDHA CRAWLING** on **GROUND** . . . while **BLEEDING** and **BADLY** hurt!
- ☒ **the Buddha SAW and CAME IMMEDIATELY to him and ASKED :: What happened Āṅgulimāla ???**
- ☒ **Āṅgulimāla SAID :: TEACHER / MASTER! . . . Today i have FELT the WOUNDS i have INFLICTED on THEM, WHO WERE INNOCENT and DID NOTHING and i DESTROYED their LIVES! . . . Today . . . i HAVE REALIZED . . . it WAS ALL MY DOINGS and THEY ARE NOT AT ALL @ FAULT for making this CONDITION of mine!**
- ☒ **the Buddha smiled and said to Āṅgulimāla :: Today . . . you are FREE Āṅgulimāla!**

Figure 23: An image of Āṅgulimāla, running behind the Buddha in the madness to complete his task of taking 1000th finger. Source from Commons (2026k)

Figure 24: An image of the Stupa of Āṅgulimāla, in reverence. Source from Commons (2025e)

☞ later . . . as time progressed Āṅgulimāla . . . **forged into an Arahant and protector of women during pregnancy and childbirth through his paritta & having command over healing and medicine!**

Thus the one who wore 999 cut fingers weaved into a necklace, while **KILLING 999, FORGED in the FIRE of TRUTH to transform himself into an ARHANT and ATTAINED liberation . . . with the HELP of his BELOVED Teacher . . . Shakyamuni Buddha!** For a latest reference on Āṅgulimāla, read Sahay (2026) and also go through multiple references on the Wikipedia page on Āṅgulimāla @ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A%E1%B9%85gulim%C4%811a>. Lastly, . . . depicted here are two images, one depicting the encounter and the other the Stupa of Āṅgulimāla. See figs. 23 and 24, respectively for the same!

4.4 Matter in general :: Bhūta

Now, this entire specturm of COSMOS, is made up of matter . . . to whatever extent i can grasp! And then matter is physical by nature and modern physics has made division of the same for specific study purpose. In Pali, matter in general in physiscal sense, is called *Bhūta*!

As per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by *Davids and Stede (1921-1925)* OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following is the meaning of the word **Bhūta** in Pali -

- **Bhūta** [pp. of bhavati, Vedic etc. bhūta] grown, become; born, produced; nature as the result of becoming. - The (exegetical) definition by Bdhgh of the word bhūta is interesting. He (at MA i.31) distinguishes the foll. 7 meanings of the term: (1) *animate Nature as principle, or the vital aggregates (the 5 Khandhas)*, with ref. M i.260; (2) *ghosts (amanussā)* Sn 222; (3) *inanimate Nature as principle, or the Elements (the 4 dhātus)* S iii.101 (mahābhūtā); (4) *all that exists, physical existence in general (vijjamānam)* Vin iv.25 (bhūtam); (5) *what we should call a simple predicative use, is exemplified by a typical dogmatic example, viz. "kālaghaso bhūto,"* where *bhūta* is given as meaning *khiṇṇāsava (Arahant)* J ii.260; (6) *all be- ings or specified existence, animal kingdom (sattā)* D ii.157; (7) *the vegetable kingdom, plants, vegetation (rukkh' ādayo)* Vin iv.34 (as bhūta - gāma). - Meanings: 1. bhūtā & bhūtāni (pl.) beings, living beings, animate Nature Sn 35 (expld at Nd2 479 as 2 kinds, viz. tasā & thāvarā, movable & immovable; S. ii.47 (K.S. ii.36) mind and body as come - to - be; Dh 131 (bhūtāni), 405; M i.2 sq. (paṭhavī, āpo etc., bhūtā, devā, Pajāpatī etc.), 4; MA i.32. The pl. nt. bhūtāni is used as pl. to meaning 2; viz. inanimate Nature, elements, usually enumd under term mahā - bhūtāni. - 2. (nt.) nature, creation, world M i.2 (bhūte bhūtato sañjānāti recognises the beings from nature, i. e. from the fact of being nature); DhA 312 (°pasāda - lakkhaṇa, see Expos. 409). See cpds. °gāma, °pubba (?). - 3. (nt. adj.) that which is, i. e. natural, genuine, true; nt. truth; neg. abhūta falsehood, lie Sn 397; PvA 34. See cpds. °bhāva, °vacana, °vāda. - 4. a su- pernatural being, ghost, demon, Yakkha; pl. bhūtā guardian genii (of a city) J iv.245. See cpds. °vijja, °vejja. - 5. (-°) pp. in predicative use (cp. on this meaning Bdhgh's meaning No. 5, above): (a) what has been or happened; viz. mātu - bhūtā having been his mother PvA 78; abhūtapubbam bhūtam what has never happened before happened (now) DA i.43 (in expln of abbhuta); - (b) having become such & such, being like, acting as, being, quāsi (as it were), consisting of, e. g. andha° blind, as it were J vi.139; aru° consisting of wounds DhA iii.109; udapāna° being a well, a well so to speak PvA 78; opāna° acting as a spring A iv.185; hetu° as reason, being the reason PvA 58; cp. cakkhu° having become an eye of wisdom. Sometimes bhūta in this use hardly needs to be translated at all.

If one studies this slightly deeply, IN ALL 7 MEANINGS of Bhūta, one finds sthe DIFFERENT LEVELS or REALMS of EXISTENCE, all CONTAINING MATTER.

In **modern Physics**, there are a range of images that have been presented the various forms of **matter**. These are depicted in the following images -

- ☞ map of **dark matter** in the Universe was obtained from data from the KiDS survey, using the VLT Survey Telescope at ESO's Paranal Observatory in Chile; in fig. 25.
- ☞ **Dark matter** map from 2007 by the Cosmic Evolution Survey; in fig. 26.
- ☞ In reference to **anti matter** of electron, the cloud chamber photograph of the first positron ever observed, in fig. 27.

Figure 25: This map of [dark matter](#) in the Universe was obtained from data from the KiDS survey, using the VLT Survey Telescope at ESO's Paranal Observatory in Chile. It reveals an expansive web of dense (light) and empty (dark) regions. This image is one out of five patches of the sky observed by KiDS. Here the invisible dark matter is seen rendered in pink, covering an area of sky around 420 times the size of the full moon. This image reconstruction was made by analysing the light collected from over three million distant galaxies more than 6 billion light-years away. The observed galaxy images were warped by the gravitational pull of dark matter as the light travelled through the Universe. Some small dark regions, with sharp boundaries, appear in this image. They are the locations of bright stars and other nearby objects that get in the way of the observations of more distant galaxies and are hence masked out in these maps as no weak-lensing signal can be measured in these areas. Source from [Commons \(2024g\)](#)

☞ [Hydrogen density plots](#) for n up to 4, where [Wavefunctions of the electron in a hydrogen atom at different energy levels](#) are shown in fig. 28.

☞ [Spectrum = gas discharge tubes](#) with different gases are shown in fig. 4.4.

Here i just show the Pali words, that contain the WORD . . . **MATTER**, in relation to [Bhūta](#).

As per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by [Davids and Stede \(1921-1925\)](#) OR the online Pali dictionary @ [Univ. of Chicago](#), the following are the words in Pali that contain **matter** -

- **Vatthu**¹ (nt.) [Class. Sk. vastu, fr. vas1] lit. "ground," hence 1. (lit.) object, real thing, property, thing, substance (cp. vatthu²!) A ii.209 (khetta°, where khetta in lit. sense, cp. No. 2). Here belongs the defn of kāma as twofold: vatthu-kāma and kilesa-kāma, or desire for realities, objective kāma, and desire as property of stained character, i. e. subjective kāma, e. g. Nd1 1; SnA 99, 112; DhsA 62. - On vatthu as general philos. term cp. Dhs. trsln 2§§ 455, 679, 1229, also introd. p. 86; Cp. 15, 31, 1741. - 2. (appld meaning) object, item Vin i.121 (antima - vatthum ajjhāpannaka guilty of an extreme offence?); v.138 (the 10 āghāta - vatthūni, as at Vbh 86); D iii.252 (seven niddesa°), 255 (eight kusīta°), 258 (eight dāna°); S ii.41, 56 sq.;

Figure 26: [Dark matter](#) map from 2007 by the Cosmic Evolution Survey. Source from [Commons \(2024f\)](#)

Figure 27: Photo of a [positron](#). Removed white background, derived from another photo. Cloud chamber photograph of the first positron ever observed. The thick horizontal line is a lead plate. The positron entered the cloud chamber in the lower left, was slowed down by the lead plane, and curved to the upper left. The curvature of the path is caused by an applied magnetic field that acts perpendicular to the image plane. The higher energy of the entering positron resulted in lower curvature of its path. A 63 million volt positron ($H\rho = 2.1 \times 10^5$ gauss-cm) passing through a 6 mm lead plate and emerging as a 23 million volt positron ($H\rho = 7.5 \times 10^4$ gauss-cm). The length of this latter path is at least ten times greater than the possible length of a proton path of this curvature. Source from [Anderson \(1933\)](#) and [Commons \(2025f\)](#)

Vbh 71 (cakkhu° etc.), 306 sq., 353; Nett 114 (ten); SnA 172; DhA iv.2 (akkosa°); PvA 8, 20 (dāna°), 26 (left out in id. p. KhA 209), 29, 65 (alabbhaneyya°), 96 (id.), 119, 121 (iṭṭha°), 177, 220. Cp. °bhūta. - 3. occasion for, reason, ground A ii.158 (+khetta [in fig. sense!], āyatana & adhikaraṇa); iv.334; D i.13 sq. (aṭṭhādasahi vatthūhi etc.); J ii.5 (avatthumhi chandaṃ mākari do not set your heart on what is unreasonable); vatthunā (instr.) because PvA 118; vatthuto

Figure 28: [Hydrogen density plots](#) for n up to 4. [Wavefunctions of the electron in a hydrogen atom at different energy levels](#). Quantum mechanics cannot predict the exact location of a particle in space, only the probability of finding it at different locations. The brighter areas represent a higher probability of finding the electron. Source from [Commons \(2026I\)](#)

Figure 29: [Spectrum = gas discharge tubes](#). The gases: Hydrogen H_2 , Deuterium D_2 , Nitrogen N_2 , Oxygen O_2 , mercury Hg . Used with 1.8kV, 18mA, 35kHz. Approx. 8" length. Source from [Commons \(2025g\)](#)

(abl.) on account of PvA 241. - 4. basis, foundation, seat, (objective) substratum, substance, element J i.146 (kāyo paridevānaṃ v.); VbhA 404 (+ārammaṇa). See most of the cpds. - 5. subjectmatter, subject, story, account SnA 4; DhA ii.66; PvA 77, 92, 263, 269. Cp. °gāthā & titles like Petavatthu, Vimānavatthu. **-rūpa** substance or substratum of matter, material form Vism 561, 564; VbhA 22, 172.

- **Rūpa** [i have mentioned below] **-ārammaṇa** a visible thing as object Dhs 146, 365; DhsA 310 (cp. Expos. 407). **-āvacara** world of form, sphere of matter (cp. Expos. 67, 216n, 264) PvA 163.
- **Mana / Mano** [we have discussed earlier] **-mattaka**, in phrase mana - mattakena (adv.) "by mere mind," consisting of mind only, i.e. memorial, as a matter of mind J iv.228.
- **Indriya** (nt.) [Vedic indriya adj. only in meaning "belonging to Indra"; nt. strength, might (cp. inda), but in specific pāli sense "belonging to the ruler", i. e. governing, ruling nt. governing, ruling or controlling principle] A. On term: Indriya is one of the most comprehensive & important categories of Buddhist psychological philosophy & ethics, meaning "controlling principle, directive force, élan, $\delta \acute{u} \nu \alpha \mu \iota \zeta$ ", in the foll. applications: (a) with reference to sense - perceptibility "faculty, function", often wrongly interpreted as "organ"; (b) w. ref. to objective aspects of form and matter "kind, characteristic, de-terminating principle, sign, mark" (cp. woman - hood, hood = Goth. haidus "kind, form"); (c) w. ref. to moods of sensation and (d) to moral powers or motives controlling action, "principle, controlling" force; (e) w. ref. to cognition & insight "category". - Definitions of indriya among others at DhsA 119; cp. Expositor 157; Dhs trsl. lvii; Cpd. 228, 229. B. Classifications and groups of indriyāni. An exhaustive list comprises the indriyāni enumd under A a - e, thus establishing a canonical scheme of 22 Controlling Powers (bāvisati indriyāni), running thus at Vbh 122 sq. (see trsl. at Cpd. 175, 176); and discussed in detail at Vism 491 sq. (a. sensorial) (1) cakkh - undriya ("the eye which is a power", Cpd. 228) the eye or (personal potentiality of) vision, (2) sot - indriya the ear or hearing, (3) ghān° nose or smell, (4) jivh° tongue or taste, (5) kāy° body - sensibility, (6) man° mind; (b. material) (7) itth° female sex or femininity, (8) puris° male sex or masculinity, (9) jīvit° life or vitality; (c. sensational) (10) sukh° pleasure, (11) dukkh° pain, (12) somanasa° joy, (13) domanass° grief, (14) upekh° hedonic indifference (d. moral) (15) saddh° faith, (16) viriy° energy, (17) sat° mind-fulness, (18) samādh° concentration, (19) paññ° reason; (e. cognitional) (20) anaññāta-ñassāmīt° the thought "I shall come to know the unknown", (21) aññ° (= aññā) gnosis, (22) aññātā-v° one who knows. - Jīvitindriya (no. 9) is in some redactions placed before itth° (no. 7), e. g. at Ps i.7, 137. - From this list are detached several groups, mentioned frequently and in various connections, no. 6 manas (mano, man - indriya) wavering in its function, being either included under (a) or (more frequently) omitted, so that the first set (a) is marked off as pañc' indriyāni, the 6th being silently included (see below). This uncertainty regarding manas deserves to be noted. The foll. groups may be mentioned here viz 19 (nos. 1 - 19) at Ps i.137; 10 (pañca rūpīni & pañca arūpīni) at Nett 69; three groups of five (nos. 1 - 5, 10 - 14, 15 - 19) at D iii.239, cp. 278; four (group d without paññā, i. e. nos. 15 - 18) at A ii.141; three (saddh°, samādh°, paññ°, i. e. nos. 15, 18, 19) at A i. 118 sq. Under aṭṭhavidhaṃ indriya - rūpaṃ (Cpd. 159) or rūpaṃ as indriyaṃ "form which is faculty" Dhs 661 (cp. trsl. p. 204) are understood the 5 sensitives (nos. 1 - 5), the 2 séx - states (nos. 7, 8) and the vital force (no. 9), i. e. groups a & b of enumd.; discussed & defined in detail at Dhs 709 - 717, 971 - 973. - It is often to be

guessed from the context only, which of the sets of 5 indriyāni (usually either group a or d) is meant. These detached groups are classed as below under C. f. - Note. This system of 22 indriyāni reflects a revised & more elaborate form of the 25 (or 23) categories of the Sāṅkhya philosophy, with its 10 elements, 10 indri, īni & the isolated position of manas. C. Material in detail (grouped according to A a - e) (a) sensorial: (mentioned or referred to as set of 5 viz B. nos. 1 - 5): M i.295; S iii.46 (pañcannam °ānam avak kanti), 225; iv.168; A ii.151 (as set of 6, viz. B. nos. 1 - 6): M i.9; S iv.176; v.74, 205, 230; A i.113; ii.16, 39, 152; iii.99, 163, 387 sq.; v.348. Specially referring to restraint & control of the senses in foll. phrases: in driyāni saṁvutāni S ii.231, 271; iv.112; pañcasu °esu saṁvuto Sn 340 (= lakkhaṇato pana chaṭṭham pi vuttaṁ yeva hoti, i. e. the 6th as manas included, SnA 343); °esu susaṁvuta Th 2, 196 (= mana - chaṭṭhesu i° suṭṭhu saṁvutā ThA 168) indriyesu guttadvāra & guttadvārātā D iii.107; S ii.218; iv.103, 112, 175; A i.25, 94, 113; ii.39; iii.70, 138, 173, 199, 449 sq.; iv.25, 166; v.134; It 23, 24; Nd1 14; Vbh 248, 360; DA i.182 (= manachattesu indriyesu pihita - dvāro hoti), i. vipasannāni S ii. 275; iii.2, 235; iv.294; v.301; A i.181; iii.380. °ānam samatā (v. l. samatha) A iii.375 sq. (see also f. below) °āni bhāvitāni Sn 516 (= cakkh' ādāni cha i. SnA 426); Nd2 475 B8. - Various: S i.26 (rakkhati), 48 (°ūpasame rato); iv.40, 140 (°samppanna); v.216, 217 sq. (independent in function, mano as referee); Ps. i.190 (man°); Vbh 13 (rūpa), 341 (mud° & tikkh°) 384 (ahīn°). - (b) phys- ical: (above B 7 - 9) all three: S v.204; Vism 447; itthi° & purisa° A iv.57; Vbh 122, 415 sq.; puris° A iii.404; jīvit° Vbh 123, 137; Vism 230 (°upaccheda = maraṇa). See also under itthi, jīvita & purisa. - (c) sensational (above B 10 - 14): S v.207 sq. (see Cpd. 111 & cp. p. 15), 211 sq.; Vbh 15, 71; Nett 88. - (d) moral (above B 15- 19): S iii.96, 153; iv.36, 365 sq.; v.193 sq., 202, 219 (corresponding to pañcabalāni), 220 sq. (and amata), 223 sq. (their culture brings assurance of no rebirth), 227 sq. (paññā the chief one), 235, 237 (sevenfold fruit of), A iv.125 sq., 203, 225; v.56, 175; Ps ii.49, 51 sq., 86; Nd1 14; Nd2 628 (sat° + satibala); Kvu 589; Vbh 341; Nett 15, 28, 47, 54. Often in standard combn. with satipaṭṭhāna, sammappadhāna. iddhipāda, indriya, bala, bojḅhanga, magga (see Nd2 s. v. p. 263) D ii.120; Vin iii. 93, Ps ii.166 & passim. As set of 4 indriyāni (nos. 16- 19) at Nett 83. - (e) cognitional (above B 20 - 22) D iii.219 = S v.204 (as peculiar to Arahantship); It 53; Ps i.115; ii.30. - (f) collec- tively, either two or more of groups a - e, also var. peculiar uses: personal; esp. physical faculties. S i.61 (pākat°), 204 (id.); iii.207 (ākāsam °āni sankamanti); iv.294 (vipari - bhin- nāni); A iii.441 (°ānam avekallatā). magic power A iv.264 sq. (okkhipati °āni). indriyānam paripāko (moral or physical) over - ripeness of faculties S ii.2, 42; A v.203; Nd2 252 (in def. of jarā); Vbh 137. moral forces Vin i.183 (°ānam samatā, + viriyānam s. as sign of Arahant); ii.240 (pañc°). principle of life ekindriyam jīvaṁ Vin iii.156; Miln 259. heart or seat of feeling in phrase °āni paricāreti to satisfy one's heart PvA 16, 58, 77. obligation, duty, vow in phrase °āni bhinditvā breaking one's vow J ii.274; iv.190. D. Unclassified material D i 77 (ahīn°); iii 239 (domanass° & somanass°) M i.437 (vemattatā), 453 (id.); ii. 11, 106; iii.296; S iii.225; v.209 (dukkh°, domanass°); A i.39, 42 sq., 297; ii.38 (sant°), 149 sq.; iii.277, 282; Ps i.16, 21, 88, 180; ii.1 sq, 13, 84, 119, 132, 143, 145, 110, 223; Nd1 45 (°dhīra), 171 (°kusala), 341 (pucchā); Dhs 58, 121, 528, 556 (dukkh°), 560, 644. 736; Nett 18 (sotāpannassa), 28 (°vavaṭṭhāna), 162 (lok'uttara); Vism 350 (°vekallatā); Sdhp 280, 342, 364, 371, 449, 473. E. As adj. (-°) having one's senses, mind or heart as such & such S i.138 (tikkh° & mud°); iii.93 (pākat°); v.269 (id.); A i.70 (id) & passim (id.); A i.70 (saṁvut°) 266 (id.), 236 (gutt°); ii.6 (samāhit°); 8n 214 (susamāhit° his senses well - composed); PvA 70 (pīṇit° joyful or gladdened of heart).

4.5 Composition of matter :: Aṇu + Kalāpas

i repeat contents of section 1 for continuity, over here . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary](#) @ University of Chicago, **atom** is -

- **Aṇu** Aṇu (adj.) [Sk. aṇu; as to etym. see Walde Lat. Wtb. under ulna. See also āṇi] small, minute, atomic, subtle (opp. thūla, q. v.) D i.223; S i.136; v.96 (°bīja); Sn 299 (anuto aṇuṃ gradually); J iii.12 (= appamattaka); iv.203; Dhs 230, 617 (= kisa); ThA 173; Miln 361. Note aṇu is freq. spelt anu, thus usually in cpd. °matta.

Also, from the English-Pali dictionary by **Buddhadatta (1989)**, one finds for **atom** -

- **atom** : (m.) paramāṇu.
- **atomic** : (adj.) paramāṇuvisayaka.
- **atomism** : (m.) paramāṇuvāda.
- **atomise** : (v.t.) paramāṇubhāvaṃ pāpeti. (pp.) paramāṇubhāvaṃ papita.
- **atomy** : (m.) 1. kisadeha; 2. aṭṭhikaṅkala; 3. aṇuppamāṇajīvī.

and the word **Kalāpa**, has its meaning as -

- **Kalāpa** [cp. Sk. kalāpa] 1. **anything that comprises a number of things of the same kind; a bundle, bunch; sheaf; a row, multitude; usually of grass, bamboo - or sugar - canes, sometimes of hair and feathers** S iv.290 (tiṇa°); J i.158 (do.); 25 (naḷa°), 51 (mālā°), 100 (uppalakumuda°); v.39 (usīra°); Miln 33; PvA 257, 260 (ucchu°), 272 (veḷu°); 46 (kesā), 142 (mora - piṇja°) - 2. **a quiver** Vin ii.192; It 68; J vi.236; Miln 418; PvA 154, 169. - 3. **in philosophy: a group of qualities, pertaining to the material body (cp. rūpa°)** Vism 364 (dasadhamma°) 626 (phassa - pañcamakā dhammā); Bdhd 77 (rūpa°) 78, 120. -agga (nt.) "the first (of the) bunch," the first (sheaves) of a crop, given away as alms DhA i.98. -sammasanā grasping (characteristics) by groups Vism 287, 606, 626 sq.

4.6 The Elements :: Dhātu

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the [link to online Pali dictionary](#) @ University of Chicago, **elements** is -

- **Dhātu** (f.) [Sk. dhātu to dadhāti, Idg. *dhē, cp. Gr. τ ῑ χ η μ ι, ῑ α ν ῑ α η μ α, Sk. dhāman, dhātr (=Lat. conditor); Goth. gadēds; Ohg. tāt, tuom (in meaning -°=dhātu, cp. E. serf - dom "condition of . . .") tuon=E. to do; & with k - suffix Lat. fa- cio, Gr. (ῑε) χ η κ(α), Sk. dhāka; see also dhamma] element. Closely related to dhamma in meaning B 1b, only implying a closer relation to physical substance. As to its gen. connota- tion cp. Dhs. trsl. p. 198. - 1. **a primary element, of which the usual set comprises the four paṭhavī, āpo, tejo, vāyo (earth, water, fire, wind), otherwise termed cattāro mahābhūtā(ni):** D i.215; ii.294; iii.228; S i.15; ii.169 sq., 224; iv.175, 195; A ii.165; iii.243; Vbh 14, 72; Nett 73. See discussed at Cpd. 254 sq. - A defn of dhātu is to be found at Vism 485. - Singly or in other combns paṭhavī° S ii.174; tejo° S i.144; D iii.227; the four plus ākāsa S iii.227, plus viññāna S ii.248; iii.231; see below 2 b. - 2. (a) **natural condition, property, disposition; factor, item, principle, form.** In this meaning in var. combns & applications, esp. closely related to khandha. Thus

men- tioned with **khandha & āyatana** (sensory element & element of sense - perception) as bodily or physical element, factor (see khandha B 1 d & cp. Nd2 under dhātu) Th 2, 472. As such (physical substratum) it constitutes one of the lokā or forms of being (khandha° dhātu° āyatana° Nd2 550). Freq. also in combn kāma - dhātu, rūpa° arūpa° ”the elements or properties of k. etc.” as preceding & conditioning bhava in the respective category (Nd2 s. v.). See under d. - As ”set of conditions or state of being (-°)” in the foll.: **loka°** a world, of which 10 are usually mentioned (equalling 10,000: PvA 138) S i.26; v.424; Pv ii.961; Vbh 336; PvA 138; KS ii.101, n. 1; - **nibbāna°** the state of N. S v.8; A ii.120; iv.202; J i.55; It 38 (dve: see under Nibbāna); Miln 312. Also in the foll. connections: am- ata° It 62; bhū° the verbal root bhū DA i.229; ṭhapitāya dhā- tuyā ”while the bodily element, i. e. vitality lasts” Miln 125; vaṇṇa° form, beauty S i.131; Pv i.31. In these cases it is so far weakened in meaning, that it simply corresponds to E. ab- str. suffix - hood or - ity (cp. °hood=origin. ”form”: see ketu), so perhaps in Nibbāna°=Nibbāna - dom. Cp. dhātuka. - (b) elements in sense - consciousness: referring to the 6 ajjhattikāni & 6 bāhirāni āyatanāni S ii.140 sq. Of these sep. sota° D i.79; iii.38; Vbh 334; dibbasota° S ii.121, 212; v.265, 304; A i.255; iii.17, 280; v.199; cakkhu° Vbh 71 sq.; mano° Vbh 175, 182, 301; mano - viññāṇa° Vbh 87, 89, 175, 182 sq. - (c) various: aneka° A i.22; iii.325; v.33; akusala° Vbh 363; avijjā° S ii.132; ābhā° S ii.150; ārambha° S v.66, 104 sq.; A i.4; ii.338; ṭhiti° S ii.175; iii.231; A iii.338; dhamma° S ii.56; nekkhamma° S ii.151; A iii.447; nissāraṇiyā dhātuyo (5) D iii.239; A iii.245, 290. See further S i.134, 196; ii.153, 248 (aniccā); iii.231 (nirodha); iv.67; A i.176; ii.164; iv.385; Dhs 58, 67, 121; Nett 57, 64 sq.; ThA 20, 49, 285, - (d) Different sets and enumerations: as 3 under kāma°, rūpa°, arūpa A i.223; iii.447; Ps i.137; Vbh 86, 363, 404 sq.; under rūpa°, arūpa°, nirodha° It 45. - as 6 (pathavī etc.+ākāsa° & viññāṇa°): D iii.247; A i.175 sq.; M iii.31, 62, 240; Ps i.136; Vbh 82 sq. - as 7 (ābhā subha etc.): S ii.150. - 18: Ps i.101, 137; ii.230, Dhs 1333; Vbh 87 sq., 401 sq.; Vism 484 sq. - 3. *a humour or affection of the body* DA i.253 (dhātusamatā). - 4. *the remains of the body after cremation* PvA 76; a relic VvA 165 (sarīra°, bodily relic); Dāvs v.3 (dasana° the toothrelic). - abl. dhātuso *according to one’s nature* S ii.154 sq. (sattā sattehi saddhim samsandanti etc.); It 70 (id.); S iii.65.

4.7 the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense / the elements or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form :: (s)Khandha

JUST to reiterate, though mentioned earlier, as per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in Pali for (s)Khandha have been found or contain the same -

- **Khandha** [Sk. skandha] - I. Crude meaning: bulk, massiveness (gross) substance. A. esp. used (a) of an elephant: the bulk of the body, i. e. its back S i.95; vāraṇassa J iii.392; hatthi - khandha - vara - gata on the back of the state elephant J i.325; PvA 75. Also with ref. to an elephant (hatthināga) sañjāta° "to whom has grown bulk=a large back" Sn 53, expl. SnA 103 by sasaṅghitakkhandho "well endowed with bulk." - (b) of a person: the shoulder or back: nangalaṃ khandhe karitvā S i.115 appl. to Māra; Vism 100; DhA iv.168 (ohita° - bhāra the load lifted off his shoulder). - - (c) of a tree: the trunk. rukkhassa PvA 114, also as rukkha° J i.324; tāla° the stem of a palm PvA 56; nigrodhassa khandhaja (see cpds.) S i.207=Sn 272; mūlaṃ atikkamma kh° ṃ sāraṃ pariye- sitabbaṃ "one must go beyond the root and search the trunk for sweetness" S iv.94. - (d) as t.t. in exegetical literature: section, chapter, lit. material as collected into uniform bulk; freq. in postscripts to Texts and Commentaries. See also khandhaka. - B. More general as denoting bulk (-°); e. g. aggi° a great mass of fire M ii.34, 41; J iv.139; udaka° a mass of water (i. e. ocean) A iii.336; S iv.179; J i.324; PvA 62; puñña° a great accumulation of merit A iii.336=S v.400; bhoga° a store of wealth A v.84; J i.6; maṇi° an extraordinarily large jewel (possessing magic power) J ii.102 sq. - II. Applied meaning. - A. (-°) the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense "all that is comprised under"; forming the substance of. - (a) dukkha° all that is comprised under "dukkha," all that goes to make up or forms the substance, the idea of "ill." Most prominent in phrase ke- valassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudaya and nirodha (the origin & destruction of all that is suffering) with ref. to the paṭi- casamuppāda, the chain of causal existence (q. v.) Vin i.1; S ii.95; iii.14; A i.177; v. 184 & passim. Similarly: samu- daya Vbh 135 sq. nirodha Nett 64; antakiriya A i.147; vyādhi- maraṇatunnānaṃ dukkhakkhandhaṃ vyapānudi Th 2, 162. - (b) lobha° dosa° moha° the three ingredients or integrations of greed, suffering and bewilderment, lit. "the big bulk or mass of greed" (see also under padāleti), S v.88 (nibbijjhati through the satta bojjangā). - (c) vayo° a division of age, part of age, as threefold: purima°, majjhima°, pacchima° Nd2 in def. of sadā. - (d) sīla (etc.) kh° the 3 (or 5) groups or parts which constitute the factors of right living (dhamma), viz. (1) sīla° the group dealing with the practice of morality; (2) samādhi° that dealing with the development of concentration; (3) paññā° that dealing with the development of true wisdom. They are also known under the terms of sīla - sampadā, citta°, paññā° D i.172 sq.; see sīla. - D i.206; Nett 64 sq.; 126. tīhi dham- mehi samannāgato "possessed of the three qualities," viz. sīla - kkhandhesu, etc. It 51; cp. A i.291; v.326. tīhi khandhehi . . . aṭṭhangiko maggo sangahito M i.301; sīlakkhandhaṃ, etc. paripūreti "to fulfil the sīla - group" A i.125; ii.20, iii.15 sq. These 3 are completed to a set of 5 by (4) vimutti° the group dealing with the attainment of emancipation and (5) vimutti - nāṇa - dassana° the group dealing with the realization of the achievement of emancipation. As 1 - 4 only at D iii.229 (mis- print puñña for paññā); cp. A i.125. As 5 at S i.99=A i.162; S v.162; A iii.134, 271; v.16 (all loc.=S i.99); It 107, 108; Nd2 under sīla. B. (absolute) in individual sense: constituent element, fac- tor, substantiality. More especially as khandhā (pl.) the ele- ments or substrata

of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form. Their character according to quality and value of life and body is evanescent, fraught with ills & leading to rebirth. Paraphrased by Bdgh. as rāsi, heap, e. g. Asl. 141; Vibh A 1 f.; cf. B. Psy. 42. 1. Unspecified. They are usually enumerated in the foll. stereotyped set of 5: **rūpa° (material qualities)**, **vedanā (feeling)**, **saññā (perception)**, **sankhārā (coefficients of consciousness)**, **viññāṇa (consciousness)**. For further ref. see rūpa; cp. also Mrs. Rh. D. Dhs trsl. pp. 40 - 56. They are enumerated in a different order at S i.112, viz. rūpaṃ vedayitaṃ saññaṃ viññāṇaṃ yañ ca sankhataṃ n' eso 'ham asmi. Detailed discussions as to their nature see e. g. S iii.101 (=Vbh 1 - 61); S iii.47; iii.86. As being comprised in each of the dhātus, viz. kāma° rūpa° arūpa - dhātu Vbh 404 sq. (a) As factors of existence (cp. bhava). Their rôle as such is illustrated by the famous simile: "yathā hi angasambhārā hoti saddo ratho iti evaṃ khandhesu santesu hoti satto ti sammuti" "just as it is by the condition precedent of the co - existence of its various parts, that the word G chariot is used, just so it is that when the skandhas are there, we talk of a G being" (Rh. D.) (cp. Hardy, Man. Buddh. p. 425) S i.135=Miln 28. Their connotation "khandha" is discussed at S iii.101 =M iii.16: "kittāvataṃ nu kho khandhānaṃ khandhādhivacanaṃ? rūpaṃ (etc.) atitānāgatapaccuppannaṃ ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhā vā oḷārikaṃ," etc.: i.e. material qualities are equivalent terms for the kh. What causes the manifestation of each kh.? cattāro mahābhūtā . . . paccayo rūpa - khandhassa paññāpanāya; phasso . . . vedanā°, saññā°, sankhārā°, etc.; nāmarūpaṃ . . . viññāṇa°: the material elements are the cause of rūpa, touch is that of vedanā, saññā, sankhārā, name and shape that of viññāṇa (S iii.101); cp. M i.138 sq., 234 sq. On the same principle rests their division in: rūpa - kāyo rūpakhandho nāmakāyo cattāro arūpino khandhā "the material body forms the material factor (of existence), the individualized body the 4 immaterial factors" Nett 41; the rū - pakhandha only is kāmādhātu - pariyāpanno: Vbh 409; the 4 arūpino kh° discussed at Ps ii.74, also at Vbh 230, 407 sq. (grouped with what is apariyāpanna) - Being the "substantial" factors of existence, birth & death depend on the khandhas. They appear in every new conjuncture of individuality concerning their function in this paṭisandhi - kkhāṇe; see Ps ii.72 - 76. Thus the var. phases of life in transmigration are defined as - (jāti): ya tesam tesam sattānaṃ tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo āyatanānaṃ paṭilābho Nd2 on Sn 1052; cp. jāti dvīhi khandhehi sangahitā ti VvA 29; khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo jāti S ii.3; Nett 29; khandhānaṃ nibbatti jāti Vism 199. - (maraṇaṃ): yā tesam tesam sattānaṃ... cuti cavanatā bhedo antaradhānaṃ maccu maraṇaṃ kālakiriyaṃ khandhānaṃ bhedo kalevarassa nikkhepo M i.49=Vbh 137=S ii.3, 42. - vivatta - **kkhandha (adj.) one whose khandhas have revolved (passed away)**, i. e. dead S i.121=iii.123. - **kh°anaṃ udaya - vyaya (or udayabbaya) the rising and passing of the kh., transmigration** Dh 374=Th 1, 23, 379=It 120=KhA 82; Ps i.54 sq. - (b) Their relation to attachment and craving (kāma): sattisūlūpamā kāmaṃ khandhānaṃ adhikuṭṭānaṃ S i.128=Th 2, 58, 141 (ThA 65: natthi tesam adhik°?); craving is their cause & soil: hetupaṭicca sambhūtā kh. S i.134; the 4 arūpino kh. are based on lobha, dosa, moha Vbh 208. - (c) their annihilation: the kh. remain as long as the knowledge of their true character is not attained, i. e. of their cause & removal: yaṃ rūpaṃ, etc. . . n' etaṃ mama n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā ti; evaṃ etaṃ yathābhūtāṃ sammappaññāya passati; evaṃ kho jānato passato . . . ahankāramamankāra - mānānusayā na hontī ti S iii.103; - pañca - kkhandhe pariññāya S iii.83; pañca - kkhandhā pariññatā tiṭṭhanti chinnamūlakā Th 2, 106. See also S i.134. - (d) their relation to dhātu (the physical elements) and āyatana (the elements of sense - perception) is close, since they are

all dependent on sensory experience. The 5 khandhas are frequently mentioned with the 18 dhātuyo & the 12 āyatanāni: khandhā ca dh° cha ca āyatanā ime hetum paṭicca sambhūtā hetubhangā nirujjhare S i.134; kh° - dh° - āyatanam sankhataṃ jātimūlam Th 2, 472; dhammam adesesi khandh° - āyatanā - dhātuyo Th 2, 43 (cp. ThA 49). Enumerated under sabba - dhammā Ps i.101=ii.230; under dhammā (states) Dhs 121, as lokuttara - kkhandhā, etc. Dhs 358, 528, 552. - khandhānam khandhattho abhiññeyyo, dhātūnam dhātuttho, etc. Ps i.17; cp. i.132; ii.121, 157. In def. of kāmāvacarā bhūmi Ps i.83. In def. of dukkha and its recognition Nett 57. In def. of arahanto khīṇāsavā Nd2 on sankhāta - dhammā ("kh. sankhātā," etc.), on tiṇṇa ("khandha - (etc.) pariyante thitā"), & passim. - (e) their valuation & their bearing on the "soul" - conception is described in the terms of na mama (na tumhākaṃ), anattā, aniccaṃ and dukkhaṃ (cp. upādānakkh° infra and rūpa) rūpaṃ (etc.). . . aniccaṃ, dukkhaṃ, n' eso 'ham asmi, n' eso me attā "material qualities (etc. kh. 2 - 5) are evanescent, bad, I am not this body, this body is not my soul" Vin i.14=S iv.382. n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā S i.112; iii.103, 130 & passim; cp. kāyo na tumhākaṃ (anattā rūpaṃ) S ii.65; Nd2 680; and rūpaṃ na tumhākaṃ S iii.33 M i.140=Nd2 680. - rūpaṃ, etc. as anattā: Vin i.13; S iii.78, 132 - 134; A i.284= ii.171; 202; cp. S iii.101; Vin i.14. - as aniccaṃ: S iii.41, 52, 102, 122, 132 sq., 181 sq., 195 sq., 202 - 224, 227; A iv.147 (aniccānupassī dukkhānupassī); anicca dukkha roga, etc., Ps ii.238 sq.; Vbh 324. - 2. Specified as panc' upādāna-kkhandhā the factors of the fivefold clinging to existence. Defined & discussed in detail (rūpūpadāna - kkhandha, etc.) S iii.47; 86 - 88; also Vin i.10; S iii.127 sq. Specified S iii.58 iii.100=M iii.16; S iii.114, 158 sq.; v.52, 60; A iv.458; Vism 443 sq. (in ch. xiv: Khandha - niddesa), 611 sq. (judged aniccato, etc.). - Mentioned as a set exemplifying the number 5: Kh iii.; Ps i.22, 122. Enumerated in var. connections S i.112; D iii.233; M i.190; A v.52; Kh iv. (expld KhA 82=A v.52); Miln 12 (var. references concerning the discussion of the kh. in the Abhidhamma). - What is said of the khandhas alone - see above 1 (a) - (e) - is equally applied to them in connection with upādāna. - (a) As regards their origin they are characterized as chandamūlakā "rooted in desire, or in wilful desire" S iii.100; cp. yo kho... pañcas' upādānakkhandhesu chandarāgo taṃ tattha upādānaṃ ti M i.300, 511. Therefore the foll. attributes are characteristic: kummo pañcann' etaṃ upādānaṃ adhivacanaṃ M i.144; bhārā have pañcakkhā S iii.26; pañcavadhakā paccatthikā pañcann'... adhivacanaṃ S iv.174; pañc' upādāna . . . sakkāyo vutto M i.299= S iv.259. - (b) their contemplation leads to the recognition of their character as dukkha, anicca, anattā: na kiñci attānaṃ vā attaniyaṃ vā pañcasu upādānakkhandhesu S iii.128; rogato, etc. . . manasikātabbā pañc° S iii.167; pañcasu upādānesu aniccānupassī "realizing the evanescence in the 5 aggregates of attachment" A v.109; same with udayavyayānupassī S iii.130; A ii.45, 90; iii.32; iv.153; and dhammānupassī M i.61. Out of which realization follows their gradual destruction: pañc' . . . khandhānam samudayo atthagamo assādo, etc. S iii.31, 160 sq.; A ii.45, 90; iv.153; Nd2 under sankhārā. That they occupy a prominent position as determinants of dukkha is evident from their rôle in the exposition of dukkha as the first one of the noble truths: sankhittena pañc' upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā "in short, the 5 kh. are associated with pain" Vin i.10=M i.48=A i.177=S v.421; Ps i.37, 39; Vbh 101 & passim; cp. katamaṃ dukkham ariyasaccaṃ? pañc' upādāna tissa vacaniyaṃ, seyyathidaṃ . . . S iii.158=v.425; khandhādisā dukkhā Dh 202 (& expl. DhA iii.261). - 3. Separately mentioned: khandhā as tayo arūpino kh° (ved°, sañña°, sankh°) DhA i.22; viññāna - kh° (the skandha of discriminative consciousness) in Def. of manas: manindriyaṃ viññānaṃ viññ° - khandho tajjā manoviññānadhātu Nd2 on Sn 1142=Dhs 68.

In this context, i will QUOTE a paragraph of an article titled - **Prajna-paramita-hridaya / The Heart sutra : Bhagavati, the heart of transcendental knowledge**, released in **October of 2016**, @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which was developed and has a context in the web-page @ <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinah/shriprakashsinha/friendship-1st-teachings-sutta-nipata>. [Citation **Sinha (2017)**].

4.7.1 T. Yang dey tse jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik, wang chuk she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa nyi la nam par ta zhing pung po nga po de dak la, yang rang zhin gyi tong par nam par tao/

T. And at the same time noble Avalokiteshvara, the bodhisattva-mahasattva, looking at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge, saw that those five *skandhas* are empty by nature.

N. *He looks at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge.* The practice of the way to enter *Samadhi* via meditation on form (i.e using support *alambana*) to meditation without form (i.e formless without support) in order to experience the truth of emptiness, has been stressed upon. He is looking at the practice first. The knowledge is there, but he is looking at the practice first. This is crucial. He is pointing to the fact that the practice is important. Without proper practice, it is not possible to acquire the deep knowledge. The way to acquire knowledge is absolutely essential.

Then, through the experience of the emptiness in heart, the bodhisattva experiences emptiness in *skandhas*. Experience in heart cannot be matched with limited understanding of the mind as they are beyond the mind.

4.7.2 Q. Now, why does the sutta start with skandhas and not any other aspect?

A stupid answer is that one has to start somewhere. But jokes apart, the spiritual journey begins with existence of constituents that form an important aspect of a cycle. Here, by experiential knowledge of the heart, the former Buddha acknowledges the existence of the cycle that is crucial for existence of cycle that is crucial for existence of samsara and later on uses the steps in the cycle to experience nirvana. So first there is recognition of existence of cycle through the experiential knowledge and then the cycle is used to unlock this process of repeated births and deaths. He does not say that the cycle is bad. If one notices, Siddhartha as Buddha starts his final journey as Bodhisattva some 534 life times back (as in Jataka Tales) and uses this knowledge of *Samsara* (the inherent cycle), birth after birth to enter *parinirvana*. Again, he is not condemning the cycle. There is an acknowledgement in experience. *If one has not experienced the fundamentals of the nature of the cycle by which things are working in Samsara, then it is not easy to grasp the way to unlock this cycle.*

4.7.3 Q. What are these five skandhas?

Exposition - The five skandhas or aggregates that constitutes the various aspects of samsara or the world i.e the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). There is form or body (*rupa*) and within the form are sensations (*vedana*). The perception (*samjna*) of these sensations exists and repeated perceptions (*samjna*) of the sensations lead to impressions (*sankhara*) in the mind body complex. And in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) the impressions (*sankhara*) pushes one to take the next action in order to maintain the cycle. These are fundamental elements which form an integral aspect of a greater cycle of *Samsara*. In a deeper sense Samsara or the world is a projection either dynamic

or static and neither dynamic nor static aspects which has the property to veil and superimpose the universal truths regarding life and not allow one to see the way things are (i.e *yatha-bhuta*). There are two kinds of truths, namely - *paramartha* or the absolute truth and the *samvritta* or the relative truths of the world. One finds contradictions in the relative truths but the absolute is beyond the relative. Now this doesn't mean that the relative truths are of no value and *Samsara* is bad. It is *Samsara* which prepares one to transcend into the higher states of truth and leads to *nirvana*. Thus *Samsara* is a means or a school where one passes one step at a time to finally merge into the absolute. This is a way of expressing in the relative terms but note that the *Samsara* is connected to *nirvana* through and through. The goal (*nirvana*) and the way to the goal (in *Samsara*) are here and now as the river and the ocean is connected through and through. *Again, it is important to value the path that is there in this Samsara.*

Now again, there are two aspects of the journey. Mostly one is focused on the goal, but rarely one is focused on the way to the goal. The second is extremely rare case where the journey is more important than the goal. Kamalasila explains in his profound and deep treatise on Bhavanakrama (the steps of meditation) that there are usually two kinds of mindsets in enlightened ones. The first is the *pranidhi-chitta* or the mind fixed on the goal and the second is the *prasthanachitta* or the mind aware of the journey to the goal. This second one is an extremely rare case where a being is more focused on the journey rather than the goal and is referred to as entering the path of *anuttara-samyak-sambodhi*.

So to recapitulate, the five *skandhas* or aggregates, that constitutes the various aspects of *samsara* or the world are the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). Form (*rupa*) can be any image in any dimension that contains a boundary and gives the perception (*samjna*) of a compounded formation. Perception helps in the cognition of a form (*rupa*) and repeated perceptions of a phenomena or object of perception through sensations (*vedana*) towards the object of perception, in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) leads to mental formations (*sankhara*). Thus a cycle is formed. A cycle which leads one from birth to death to birth and so on!

4.7.4 Q. What is the procedure of seeing emptiness?

But before delving deeply into how the cycle works, it is important to know how one sees emptiness in all these five *skandhas*. Seeing is not through the ordinary eyes. It is through the heart. When the heart experiences and absorbs a knowledge through awareness, then the heart sees through the nature of the object under investigation. Thus the way is simple. It is by letting emptiness come to awareness and dissolving the individuality completely into emptiness. This happens through meditation. *Now one does not create emptiness. Emptiness is not an object of meditation. It is already there but it has not been experienced in the heart.* When the essence of emptiness or *shunyata* is experienced in the heart through meditation (i.e *bhavanamayi-prajna*), one experiences the emptiness in form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*) and consciousness (*vijnana*). A more detailed explanation of experiencing emptiness is given in latter exposition below. That is how one sees emptiness in the *skandhas*. Finally, emptiness cannot be described in words as it is directly connected to the *paramartha* or the absolute truth. Being not connected to the relative truths or *samvritti*, it can only be experienced in heart. Emptiness in heart, leads to emptiness in mind.

Regarding the deeper aspects of the cycle due to the skandhas, it is explained by the former Buddha in detail in the *Paṭicca-samuppāda-sutta* in the *Samyutta-nikaya, XII (I), 1*. See BELOW!

4.8 The 6 Senses & Organs :: Saḷāyatana

In this context, i will QUOTE the whole of the article titled - **Life, DNA, the Mahasattipatthan Sutra & the Heart Sutra - an interconnected and intertwined synergy**, @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/4qwd3>, AS it is NEEDED!

4.8.1 "This earth, is the witness" - The Buddha

In the grand scale of cosmos, it is the human form, in which qualities (guna) exist which make it capable to understand and grasp the intricacies and work through to liberate itself from the limited cycles of birth and death and the coordinates governing them. That liberation has stages, which leads to fully liberated stage and is connoted by the term Buddha. And it is only in the human form that one can acquire the stage of Buddha, however, the journey is long.

4.8.2 Salayatan and introductory molecular biology

Not deviating much from the point of the topic and continuing from the abstract, these five, mind-matter (*naam-rupa*), sensations (*vedana*), perception (*samnya*), impressions (*sankhara*) and consciousness (*viñjana*), collectively are termed as skandhas. For life, when encapsulated by limited physical form, needs a complex structural mechanism called *salayatan*, which assists life in day to day activities. At introductory level, there are two gradations in *salayatan*. One is gross physical and another is subtle mind (*chitt*). The physical *salayatan* develops through basic molecular building blocks of DNA (Deoxyribonucleic acid), RNA (Ribonucleic acid) and proteins at one strata. DNA contains the coding and non-coding blocks which pass on hereditary information as well as govern the overall functioning of the various processes that leads to inception, sustenance and decay of a cell. A collection of such cells in their various forms, functionalities and interactions or complex compounded conglomeration constitutes a physical body with appropriate functionalities. And life, in its immaculate state is encased within. We need to have basic understanding of the fundamental biological aspects of *salayatan* in order appreciate the importance of the body (*kaya*) in a greater context of the journey.

4.8.3 Signaling

This is basically the transmission information via changes in the molecular structure of the intra and the extracellular factors or substances. The message passes into the cell when some factors/substances are captured at the cell surface or membrane, by the structures called as receptors. Once the factors/substances are captured by the receptors, then there is a change in the configuration of the multiplex (extracellular factor + receptor) that induces a signal via changes in chemical bonding. This signal is then passed through the cytoplasm via the changing configuration of the different biomolecules, before reaching the nucleus of the cell.

In the cell, the further processing of the information happens as genetic code in the form of DNA is transcribed into RNA and then translated to proteins (within the cytoplasm). Signaling transduction is then an important phenomena by which the cell controls various activities. A schematic diagram of the signaling transduction is shown in figure 30.

For example, in figure 30 molecule A gets attached at the cell receptor and then there is a change in the configuration of the whole complex. A series of biomolecules then get engaged in

Figure 30: Cartoon of signaling.

transducing the signal by arranging themselves in a particular order (say the configurations of B, C and D changes in that order) before the transcription of a particular part of DNA ensues. Note that the DNA is the fundamental block which carries the entire information about a particular species at biological level, only. Everything that is needed in a particular species is encoded in the DNA.

4.8.4 Chromosome

But this DNA is not present or available for processing directly. The DNA or the entire genetic material (genome) is spread over different chromosomes. So the part of the DNA will appear as represented in the diagram of chromosome (figure 31). The chromatid is one copy of the pair that forms the X shape of the chromosome. The centromere is the part of chromosome that ties the two chromatids together. This is done via spindle fiber. The chromatids themselves are formed by condensation of chromatin. Chromatin is a complex mess of the DNA that is bound with some molecules for packing purpose. The main functionality of chromatin is to (a) package DNA (b) prevent DNA damage (c) reinforce DNA for mitosis and (d) control gene expression and DNA expression. The structure of chromatin is a complex one which contains DNA, proteins and RNA. The entire strand of DNA or RNA is packaged or wrapped up along a series of protein molecules called histones (figure 32).

4.8.5 Histones

The DNA-protein complex is referred to as the nucleosome or the most basic level of chromosome packing. Each nucleosome is a pair containing double-stranded DNA that is approximately 147 nucleotides long and a core of histone octamer. The histone octamer is a combination of four histone variants with the presence of two molecules of each variant. These histone variants are H2A, H2B, H3 and H4. So the break up of the histone-DNA pair can be viewed in the following schematic diagram in figure 33 (©Alberts et al. (2007)).

We began the discussion with the fact that DNA cannot be accessible directly as it is densely packed. The packaging happens as the DNA is bound with these histone octamers. The octamers have a special structure called as tails which are highly flexible and originate from the variants of the histone at different locations. These tails are the locations where different covalent modifications

Figure 31: Cartoon of chromosome.

Figure 32: Cartoon of histones.

can occur. Due to these covalent modifications there is unfolding of the chromatin and this the tight packaging. Since the modifications are reversible, the removal of modifications lead to folding of the chromatin for a certain period of time. It is during this period that the processing of DNA/RNA gets done. Some of the known modifications are (1) methylation (2) acetulation (3) phosphorylation (4) ubiquitylation. Each of the modifications is followed by an addition of a particular group (a chemical one) (example - methylation will add CH_3 group). To aid this process of addition, special complexes called histone transferases are used. To remove the added groups another set of complexes called histone de-xes complex are employed. So, for addition of acetyl group histome acetyl transferse (HATs) are used and removal of the acetyl group is via histone deacetylase complexes (HDACs). There are other functionalities of tails as well as histones but we are now considering only a general picture of the cell, in the context of signaling.

4.8.6 DNA, RNA, proteins

Hitherto, we have been talking about DNA, RNA and protiens, but what is the link between all of these and how does the cell communicate or transmit information using these components? Note that the entire genetic information of any species is encoded in the DNA. The DNA is a structure

Figure 33: Cartoon of nucleosome. ©Alberts:2007molecular

Figure 34: Cartoon of nucleotide. ©Alberts et al. (2007)

made up of nucleotides. Each nucleotide is a sugar-phosphate molecule with a nitrogen containing side group (or base) attached to it (figure 34). The four bases are A, C, T, G (or adenine, guanine, cytosine and thymine).

Then the DNA strand is a chain of nucleotides linked via the sugar-phosphate linkages. There is a particular direction or polarity in reading the DNA strand. Through templated polymerization a single strand of DNA is combined with a complementary strand in such a manner that A of

Figure 35: Cartoon of strand. Chemical structures of nucleobases by Roland1952. (+SA). [contributors \(2019a\)](#)

one strand is bound to T of another, by hydrogen bonds. Similarly C is bounded to G. The nucleotides are bonded together with a tighter covalent bonding. Thus a double strand will look like the following in figure 35. Replication of DNA happens by pulling apart the two strands and via templated polymerization, the complementary strand is attached to the respective strand. Further information processing happens via the process of transcription and translation. Transcription is the process when the DNA is read through and via templated polymerization, short segments of DNA are used to generate single strands of RNA. Via transcription multiple copies of RNA can be generated. Note that RNA contains Uracil (U) instead of Thymine (T) and these intermediate complexes serve as messenger RNA (mRNA) for further information processing. The process of transcription is depicted in figure 36. In the second stage, a more advanced process takes place wherein the RNA is converted to proteins using a coding scheme. This process is called translation. But before that, proteins are molecules that are formed by linking building blocks called amino acids. Similar to the covalent bonding that gives a strong backbone to DNA strand, the proteins are chains of amino acids that form long structures and can be folded in 3D to form various conformations. Information in the sequence of mRNA is read out in groups of 3 nucleotides at a time and these 3 nucleotides together are called as codons. These codons are read via special class of RNA molecules called transfer RNA (tRNA). At the one end of the tRNA is the amino acid group and the other end is the complementary of the codon i.e. anti-codon, which can form bonds with the codon. For translation process, i.e. building up of a protein polymer from mRNA, the tRNA needs to be processed in a

Figure 36: Cartoon of transcription. By Kelvin Song. . contributors (2019b)

sequential manner. This processing is done with a highly preserved molecule called the ribosomal RNA (rRNA). The process starts together by bringing together the different tRNAs along with the associated amino acids in such a manner that the codons match and pair with the anti-codons so as to give a sequence of arrangements to the amino acids. As the sequence is generated the tRNAs with their amino-acids detached from them are then relieved. This process of combining the amino acid continues till the end of mRNA is reached. See figure 37.

Figure 37: Cartoon of translation. By Kelvin Song. contributors (2019c)

4.8.7 Salayatan

Now, if one looks at the complexity of the compounded materials at physical realm, it can be observed that there is definitely a complex interaction that happens within the building blocks at molecular level which drives the whole system of body (*kaya*), when taken on a grand scale. Enmeshed with the external environment and the input to and output from the system, based on the perception (*samnya*), through *salayatan* deep impressions (*sankhara*) are formed as sensations (*vedana*) arise at physical as well as mental level. In the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*), the beings act on these

impressions (*sankhara*) and sensations (*vedana*) and thus continue to exist in the flow of cycle of birth and death. It is not that the physical *salayatan* disintegrates and the chapter closes. The mental *salayatan* covering over life remains and as the configuration of the cosmos changes at the moment of the death, the physical *salayatan* is left behind. This mental *salayatan* intact along with life, exits in subtly with the *sankharas* of the previous birth and in time, again takes new birth in a new physical *salayatan* as it (life) is pushed by the force of the accumulated *sanhkaras*, in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*). The next birth, has its own mind and matter (*naam-rupa*) and the cycle continues. However, as we will see, this forms a very small aspect of the greater cycle which has been described in the law of dependent origination.

4.8.8 The cycle of dependent origination - Paticca-samuppada-sutta

Regarding the deeper aspects of the cycle due to the *skandhas*, it is explained by the former Buddha in detail in the *Paticca-samuppada-sutta* in the *Samyutta-nikaya, XII (I), 1*. It follows in this way -

Avijja-paccaya sankhara,
Ignorance causes impressions,

sankhara-paccaya vijnanam,
impressions causes flow in consciousness,

vijnana-paccaya nama-rupam,
the flow of consciousness causes the appearance
of name and form (mind and matter),

nama-rupa-paccaya salayatana,
with name and form (mind and matter) arise
the senses and the complex interactions,

salayatana-paccaya phasso,
due to the senses and complex interactions
arise contact,

phasa-paccaya vedana,
due to contact arises sensation,

vedana-paccaya tanaha,
with sensation arises desire
(craving and aversion),

tanaha-paccaya upadanam,
with desire arises attachment,

upadana-paccaya bhavo,
with attachment comes existence,

bhava-paccaya jati,
due to existence birth happens,

jati-paccaya jara-maranan-soka-parideva-dukkha-
domanassupayasa sambhavanti
with birth comes old age, death, grief, lamentation,
sorrow (physical, mental and spiritual),
bitterness of mind and other tribulations

Evame-tassa kevalassa dukkhakhandhasa samudayo hoti
Thus by this arises the chunks of sorrow in life ...

4.8.9 The essence of the Mahasattipatthan Sutra

Here, we reproduce aspects from a related article by ?. ? describes in detail the Heart sutra and it is not possible to explain every aspect of the same in this manuscript.

This formation of mental/physical body is nothing but birth and referred to as *jati*. Due to birth (*jati*) arises old age (*jara*), death (*maranan*), grief (*soka*), lamentation (*paridev*), sorrow physical, mental and spiritual (*dukkha*), bitter mindedness (*domanasu*) all come through. It is because of this that the entire mass of sorrow arises. Thus begins the acknowledgement of the first truth, i.e there is misery in life. This acknowledgement can only happen when one realizes through ones heart and not just via knowledge gained through senses or through intellectual curiosity. Next, this misery is due to a cause which forms the second truth. Since misery is not perennial, there is the cause which can be eliminated; the third truth. Finally, the fourth truth is the revelation that there is "a" way out. It is not "the" way out, but there is "a" way out. There is no force here, but an acknowledgement of an existence of a way out of this misery and the countless cycles of birth and death.

These four truths reveal the fundamental nature of phenomena that occurs in a life form (sentient/insentient). The solution to the issues encountered in the four truths are revealed in the next four truths. These truths are basically processes going through which leads to breaking of the cycle of birth and death as well as the miseries associated with it.

To begin with, the essence is to sit still and be. To sit not like a rigid stone on a ground, but as a lotus flower resting on the surface of a pond. Note that the spinal cord needs to be erect with head straight and eyes closed. Now, what happens when one sits still and be? Whatever phenomena in the mind-body-consciousness complex manifests with strongest intensity, comes to awareness. Depending on the structure of one's body, texture of mind and the quality of consciousness, a corresponding experience comes to awareness. For example, if one sits still after having a nice exercise, the temperature of the body comes to awareness. The awareness experiences the intensity of the temperature of the body rising to a peak and then passing off, as a wave rises to a peak and then falls off. Similarly, the density of the body, the throbbing of the heart, the flux of the blood, the flow of the natural breath comes to awareness. The silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena in the gross body is referred to as *kayanupaschayana*.

Longer sittings lead to refinement in awareness when the sensations in the body mainly in the form of currents in the nervous system are experienced. Due to the texture of mind-body complex at a particular moment in time, these subtle sensations might appear as extremely painful, stress-

ful, soothing or blissful (to name a few) in awareness. Again, the silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *vedananupaschyana*.

Deeper sittings lead to further refinement in awareness when the flow of the thoughts or the texture of the mind is experience. Anger, greed, happiness, bitterness, gratefulness, a child like nature, lust to name a few, comes to awareness. The texture of the mind comes to awareness. Silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *chittanupaschyana*.

Further, when the awareness reaches a more refined state after continued practice, the natural laws pertaining to the mind-body-consciousness complex comes to awareness. The rise, the persistence and the gradual decay of the any phenomena appearing on the complex comes to awareness. If a peaceful nature arises, persists and passes off on this complex, it comes to awareness. This silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the natural rise-persistence-decay law is referred to as *dhammanupaschyana*.

Note that these might happen in any order depending on the nature of the mind-body-consciousness complex at a particular moment in time. Again, advanced sittings lead to a state of awareness when one's discriminative intellect, emotions and individual ego comes to awareness. These arise, persist and gradually dissolve into nothingness. The individuality of the ego is of atomic nature in comparison to the vastness of the universal awareness. Steady continued practice leads to loss of individuality which reveal the nature of universal awareness with innumerable qualities like that of purity, benevolence, compassion, love etc.

But does one see the essence of the teachings? The former buddha is now using the stepping stones of the great cycle which he has already experienced and uses his own body as a foundation stone to unlock the cycle. The kaya or body which is a form of ignorance has now become the stepping stone for meditation. The grip of the body comes to awareness and passes off. So on and so forth with the other aspects of sensations and mind.

A stage comes when there are no wants to go for, no search to go on, no journey to be taken and no effort to be put forth. There is nothing to say, nothing to do and nothing to become. Even the search for nirvana stops. In those moments, the inexplicable state of nirvana manifests. Awareness tastes some nectars in silence. Contentment dawns in awareness and so does abundance as one re-enters the limited domain of nature. Now, even if nirvana happens once, the mind can still be impure and this is not the fully liberated stage. This stage is called *Saupadisesa-nibbana*. Depending on the individual further stages pass by in time. This journey is long and a slow process for those who wish to walk the slow and a natural path.

4.8.10 The essence of the Heart Sutra

The heart sutra raises the female aspect to a higher level, by terming emptiness (a.k.a shunyata) as the mother of all Buddhas, ?. It is not that emptiness has a gender, however, in existence, the female aspect is raised higher. On a deeper level, there are 5 stages into the realms of truth - *Anicca* (impermanence), *Dukkha* (sorrow due to not grasping impermanence), *Annatta* (non-self or an existent individual identity), *Shunyata* (emptiness) and *Tathagata* (observing the way as it is or what nature wants to show). This 4th stage of Shunyata is the mother of all Buddhas. Emptiness or Shunyata is also referred to as Goddess Bhagvati or the transcendental knowledge behind all phenomenas. *Gate gate paragate parasamgate bodhi soha* meaning "going going, going beyond, transcending

all fields, one merges into the fully liberated stage of enlightenment”. Where does one go? As the lotus flower rests gently on the surface of the pond, while the happenings within the petals of the flower, like the flow of nutrition etc, occurs naturally and spontaneously, so also the when the human body sits still, the fields of body (*kaya*), sensations (*vedana*), mind (*chitta*) and the laws of nature (*dhamma*), come to awareness and passes off. *Kayanupaschyana* (observation of body), *Vedananuspaschyana* (observation of sensations within the body), *Chittanuspaschyana* (observation of the flow of mind) and *Dhammanupaschyana* (observation of the law of rise, persistence and fall of myriads of phenomena) or the stages of *Vipassana* meditation, all happen naturally and spontaneously as the human body sits still like a resting lotus flower! However the journey is over many life times. The Prajna-paramita-hridaya assauges multiple conflicts that one faces in one’s journey into the realms of truth. The exposition sheds light on aspects that have come to awareness and have been put in a few words. However, words cannot completely capture the essence in this journey and one’s experiential knowledge is of greatest value. Going going, going beyond, transcending all fields, one merges into the fully liberated stage. The heart sutra contains the Mahasattipatthan sutra.

4.8.11 The interconnected and intertwined synergy

Life, deviates, searches and finds its destiny in truth and liberation through the long winding road through this *samsara*. This whole *samsara* burns. It burns in the fire of desire or want, either spiritual or material. Something or the other it searches. It is not bad. All experiences refine one to take the path into the realms of truth. Life gets entangled into the never ending cycle of limitations. These limitations come in support of the life which has gotten entangled. They remain with life as long as the journey continues in the cycle of birth and death. As has been explained earlier, salayatan is one of the components in the cause of dependent origination. The complexity of salayatan and its interactions with the environment is of extreme importance. Biological knowledge to a certain extent is necessary in understanding the fact that the human body is a vehicle in this sansara through which higher advanced realms of truth open up. Though, the law of dependent origination talks about it as one of the links for the cause of existence, the same link becomes a foundation stone through which one delinks this cycle. Also, not only is it necessary to acquire knowledge from theoretical perspective, it is also important to have a experiential understanding and the skill to deal with such knowledge also. This is because, the journey is over lifetimes and as humans, material and spiritual knowledge both are needed in the journey through existance, unless one has reached a very advanced level of existence. As one delinks the cycle, one starts the practice of the teachings rendered in the Mahasattipatthan sutta. The right practice along the path leads to stages which one experiences in mind body complex. As one progresses on the path, and experiences higher advanced stages, the path erases itself. The grip of the path and all supports loosen on the awareness that life has. It is then that the emptiness as well as shunyata is experienced. However, due to the paradoxical nature of the existance of the body in nature during these experiences, humans come back to the state of the *samsara* and continue to live lead their lives. It is thus that the Heart Sutra contains the Mahasattipatthan Sutra and both complement each other. The path is in *samsara* and will remain as long as the goal of nirvana has not been reached. However, when in goal, the path and conditionings erases itself. Yet, due to existence and the laws of this mother nature, the human body remains in existence untill all conditoinings are eradicated over many lifetimes. In essence, in his final teachings before parinirvana, the Buddha states (paraphrased) : ”All compounded phenomena and objects are subject to dissolution and impermanent. Strive hard for your own salvation.”

This includes all 24 conditionings which have been described as follows in *Paccayavibhangavara Paccayuddesa*.

4.8.12 **Conditionings - Paccayavibhangavara Paccayuddesa**

The Paccayavibhangavara Paccayuddesa is a section in the Tikapatthana of the Abhidhamma Pitaka, Part I: Paccayavibhangavara. The conditionings are -

Hetupaccayo, arammanapaccayo, adhipatipaccayo
root condition, object condition,
predominance condition

anantarapaccayo, samanantarapaccayo
preceding condition, prior condition

sahajatapaccayo, annamannapaccayo
arising together condition, mutuality condition

nissayapaccayo, upanissayapaccayo
support condition, strong support condition

purejatapaccayo, pacchajatapaccayo, asevanapaccayo,
arising before condition, arising later condition,
habitual condition

kammapaccayo, vipakapaccayo
intentional deed condition, result condition

aharapaccayo, indriyapaccayo
nutrient condition, faculty condition

jhanapaccayo, maggapaccayo
absorption condition, path condition

sampayuttapaccayo, vippayutapaccayo
association condition, dissociation condition

attipaccayo, nattipaccayo
presence condition, absence condition

vigatapaccayo, avigatapaccayo ti.
disappearance condition, non-disappearance condition.

These conditionings or *patthana* when observed with the right alertness or *satti*, in awareness (*satti-patthan*), leads to eradication of conditionings, culminating in the grasp of knowledge of *shunyata*, which is the essence of the Heart sutra. The Buddha states in Dhammapada Verses

277, 278 and 279, Aniccalakkhana Vatthu, Dukkhalakkhana Vatthu and Anattalakkhana Vatthu, respectively, the following.

Verse 277:

"Sabbe sankhara anicca" ti
yada pannaya passati
atha nibbindati dukkhe
esa maggo visuddhiya.
"All conditioned phenomena are impermanent";
when one sees this with Insight-wisdom,
one becomes weary of dukkha (i.e., the khandhas).
This is the Path to Purity.

Verse 278:

"Sabbe sankhara dukkha" ti
yada pannaya passati
atha nibbindati dukkhe
esa maggo visuddhiya.
"All conditioned phenomena are dukkha";
when one sees this with Insight-wisdom,
one becomes weary of dukkha (i.e., the khandhas).
This is the Path to Purity.

Verse 279:

"Sabbe sankhara anatta" ti
yada pannaya passati
atha nibbindati dukkhe
esa maggo visuddhiya
"All phenomena (dhammas) are without Self";
when one sees this with Insight-wisdom,
one becomes weary of dukkha (i.e., the khandhas).
This is the Path to Purity.

Here the *pannaya* is Insight-wisdom that dawns through the vipassana meditation (see section 4). And it is only through the precious human body which constitutes the *salayatan* that one can acquire the deep knowledge in the realms of truth. An understanding of the human body at molecular biology level assists in scientific understanding, of the spiritual journey at one level.

4.8.13 Conclusion

Life, DNA, the Mahasattipatthan Sutra and the Heart Sutra are deeply intertwined and interconnected, synergistically. The experiential unfolding of the knowledge in awareness happens naturally in its own time.

5 Dependent Origination :: Paṭcca-Samuppāda

For, advanced level and deeper aspects on the topic, please read through the FUNDAMENTAL WORK (long) titles -

Depend / Interdepend / Dependent origination / Dependently originated phenomena / Cause available on CERN based ZENONDO @ <https://zenodo.org/records/18108253>
Tongue-Seal available @ available on CERN based ZENONDO @ <https://zenodo.org/records/18201523>

5.1 The Buddha, on *depend / interdepend* . . .

imasmim sati, in . . . *Bahudhātukasutta* (Many Elements), *Majjhima Nikāya* (115 Middle Discourses).

5.2 qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination' or '*paṭicca-samuppāda*'?

- **Pali** : "Kittāvatā pana, bhante, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū'ti alamvacanāyā'ti? **English** : "But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'?"
- **Pali** : "Idhānanda, bhikkhu evaṃ pajānāti : **English** : "It's when a mendicant understands:
- **Pali** : '*imasmim sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati*, **English** : 'When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : *imasmim asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati, yadidaṃ* - **English** : When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. *That is* :
- **Pali** : *avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā*, **English** : Ignorance is a condition for impressions.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhārapaccayā viññānaṃ*, **English** : Impressions are conditions for consciousness.
- **Pali** : *viññānapaccayā nāmarūpaṃ*, **English** : Consciousness is a condition for name and form.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpapaccayā saḷāyatanāṃ*, **English** : Name and form are conditions for the six sense fields.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatanapaccayā phasso*, **English** : The six sense fields are conditions for contact.
- **Pali** : *phassapaccayā vedanā*, **English** : Contact is a condition for feeling.
- **Pali** : *vedanāpaccayā taṇhā*, **English** : Feeling is a condition for craving.
- **Pali** : *taṇhāpaccayā upādānaṃ*, **English** : Craving is a condition for grasping.
- **Pali** : *upādānapaccayā bhavo*, **English** : Grasping is a condition for continued existence.
- **Pali** : *bhavapaccayā jāti*, **English** : Continued existence is a condition for rebirth.
- **Pali** : *jātipaccayā jarāmaṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā sambhavanti*. **English** : Rebirth is a condition for old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress to come to be.
- **Pali** : *Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti*. **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.
- **Pali** : *Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho*, **English** : When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.

- **Pali** : *saṅkhāranirodhā viññānanirodho*, **English** : When choices cease, consciousness ceases.
- **Pali** : *viññānanirodhā nāmarūpanirodho*, **English** : When consciousness ceases, name and form cease.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpanirodhā saḷāyatānanirodho*, **English** : When name and form cease, the six sense fields cease.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatānanirodhā phassanirodho*, **English** : When the six sense fields cease, contact ceases.
- **Pali** : *phassanirodhā vedanānīrodho*, **English** : When contact ceases, feeling ceases.
- **Pali** : *vedanānīrodhā taṇhānīrodho*, **English** : When feeling ceases, craving ceases.
- **Pali** : *taṇhānīrodhā upādānanīrodho*, **English** : When craving ceases, grasping ceases.
- **Pali** : *upādānanīrodhā bhavanīrodho*, **English** : When grasping ceases, continued existence ceases.
- **Pali** : *bhavanīrodhā jātinīrodho*, **English** : When continued existence ceases, rebirth ceases.
- **Pali** : *jātinīrodhā jarāmaṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā nirujjhanti*. **English** : When rebirth ceases, old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress cease.
- **Pali** : *Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.
- **Pali** : *Ettāvata kho, ānanda, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti*. **English** : *That's how a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'.*

5.3 Just the **basics of Paṭicca-samuppāda** or dependent origination from **Sinha (2017)**

In the *Saṃyutta Nikāya* 12.1, *Buddhavagga*, *Paṭiccasamuppādasutta* (Dependent Origination) . . .

Bhagavā etad avoca:

The Buddha said this:

paṭiccasamuppādaṃ vo, bhikkhave, desessāmi.

"Bhikkhus, I will teach you dependent origination".

Taṃ suṇātha, sādhukaṃ manasi karotha, bhāsissāmi'ti.

"Listen and apply your mind well, I will speak".

"Katamo ca, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo?"

"And what, bhikkhus, is dependent origination?"

Avijjā-paccayā, bhikkhave, saṅkhārā,

Ignorance, bhikkhus, causes impressions,

saṅkhāra-paccayā viññānaṃ;

impressions causes flow in consciousness,

viññāna-paccayā nāmarūpaṃ;

the flow of consciousness causes the appearance of name and form,

nāma-rūpa-paccayā saḷāyatanaṃ;

with name and form arise the senses and the complex interactions,

saḷāyatana-paccayā phasso;

due to the senses and complex interactions arise contact,

phassa-paccayā vedanā;
 due to contact arises sensation,
vedanā-paccayā taṇhā;
 with sensation arises desire (craving and aversion),
taṇhā-paccayā upādānaṃ;
 with desire arises attachment,
upādāna-paccayā bhavo;
 with attachment comes existence,
bhava-paccayā jāti;
 due to existence birth happens,
jāti-paccayā jarā-maraṇaṃ-soka-parideva-dukkha-domanassupāyāsā sambhavanti.
 with birth comes old age, death, grief, lamentation, sorrow (physical, mental and spiritual), bitterness of mind and other tribulations.
Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti.
 Thus by this arises the chunks of sorrow in life . . .
Ayaṃ vuccati, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo.
 This is called dependent origination.

Of utmost importance is the fact that Siddhartha sets on the journey, by acknowledging the existence of cycle that leads to *saṃsāra*, while experiencing the knowledge and puts forth in words. The cycle begins with the words ignorance. Please remember this!

Avijjā - ignorance What is ignorance? What are the properties which makes one recognize ignorance and what are the ingredients which constitutes ignorance? The spirit behind the word ignorance is to capture the nature of compounded materials that blocks awareness from (1) observing the way things are as well as (2) recognizing itself as awareness. These compounded materials can be classified into three divisions, namely (1) the gross materials composed of natural elements of earth, water, fire, air and space. These materials help in constituting the physical bodies of many life forms (both sentient and non sentient beings) (2) the mental materials that constitute various faculties by which different life forms exhibit different temperaments and behaviour. These temperaments and behaviour are often reflected in action through the physical bodies. Note that there are beings without physical bodies also, whose presence comes to awareness (in case the awareness is refined). (3) Finally, the third material is the spiritual matter that constitutes aspects of life as life force in different forms of sentient and insentient beings. Thus there exist the physical, mental and spiritual bodies (compounded materials or ignorance) of a being, each finer than the other.

All these compounded materials work in tandem with a few more dimensions like time, energy, will and nature. Working in parallel with all these dimensions, ignorance has the property to superimpose layers which do not allow awareness to observe the way things are and also to veil or obstruct awareness from recognizing itself as awareness.

Saṅkhārā - impressions It is these layers (superimpositions) and obstructions (veils) that are like impressions which is referred to as *saṅkhārā*. Now awareness is universal in nature, but depending on the amount of *saṅkhārā* and the individuality reflected in ego, awareness gets restricted in recognizing its own universal nature. *Saṅkhārā* or layers of impressions can be of various types and

intensity. It is due to the intensity of the *saṅkhārā* that the cycle of birth and death is maintained. The maintenance of the circulating nature of the cycle is done by consciousness or *viññāṇam*.

***viññāṇam* - consciousness** Consciousness helps in maintaining the flow in nature. It has that ability to store the impressions and propel a being into next cycle based on those impressions and their strengths. These impressions can be favourable /pleasant or unfavourable/ unpleasant. Depending on the kinds of accumulated impression the formation of the new identity and form is established. Some impressions lead to merit filled life and others to demerit filled life. The formation of new identity and form is referred to as *nāma-rūpaṃ*.

***Nāma-Rūpaṃ* - name (also meaning mind) and form (also meaning matter)** The name and form has an identity attached to it. For example, the symbol 0, the name of 0 as zero and the meaning as its identity attached to it. The form is the system that helps carry the current impressions and that of the past. It is also this form and the identity attached to it which interacts with the different stimuli via the different senses simultaneously. The individual identity is a mental aspect at a particular cycle. This along with the form interacts through the senses. This complex interaction through the senses is referred to as *saḷāyatanaṃ*.

***saḷāyatana* - Senses and its interaction** The senses and its complex interaction happens through contact with the different stimuli from the external environment and the internal working of the mind-body complex or *nāma-rūpa*. This contact is referred to as *phasso*.

***Phasso* - contact** Contact can happen at three different realms (1) the physical realm and the senses of physical dimensions (2) mental realm and the faculties of mental dimension and (3) spiritual realm and the faculties of spiritual dimension. Due to this contact arises sensation with the mind-body complex. The sensation(s) are referred to as *vedanā*.

***Vedanā* - sensation** *Vedanā* is sensation within the frame work of mind-body complex or naam-rupa. Also, the sensation might arise due to many of the infinite phenomena occurring in nature. These sensations can be labeled as favourable/pleasant or unfavourable/unpleasant depending on one's structure of the mind-body complex. Note that this complex can also constitute the life forces which form the spiritual body of a sentient/insentient being. Depending on the quality of sensation craving or aversion arises. Example - One sees an ice-cream and contact has been made. This contact leads to sensations in mind and body, which either have a force of desire for or against the object of contact. Based on repeated perception, *Saṅkhāra* of ice-cream happens in the flow of consciousness. At the end, one consumes so much ice-cream that body becomes sick in nature.

***Taṇhā* - desire/craving/aversion** The desire and the craving and aversion associated is referred to as *taṇhā*. It is this craving and aversion that keeps a being from being free. Depending on the intensity of sensation, craving and aversion appear in equivalent intensity. With craving/aversion attachment dawns towards object of craving/ aversion. This object can be of any form i.e material, mental or spiritual. The composition of this object is again based on the building blocks of material, mental and spiritual components that constitutes ignorance. Thus the *skandhas* are an integral part of explanation and appear in the beginning of the *sutta*.

Upādānam - attachment The attachment towards object of craving/aversion is upadan. Attachment here means affinity towards object of craving/ aversion. This affinity is a direct connection to the object in attention either through the force of craving or through the force of aversion. For example, "i like ice-cream" - the strength behind liking connects one to the object ice-cream in an attractive way. On the other hand, "i don't like ice-cream" - the strength behind not liking connects one to the object ice-cream in a repulsive way (Deeper explanation will follow below). Similarly, attachment can be for any phenomena/being in the existential world.

Bhava - existence The existence that happens due to the attachment is called as bhava. The attachment forces one to come into existence. This existence happens through the formation of spiritual body, the mental body and then the material/physical body.

Jāti - birth This formation of spiritual/mental/physical body is nothing but birth and referred to as jāti. Due to birth (*jāti*) arises old age (*jarā*), death (*marañan*), grief (*soka*), lamentation (*paridev*), sorrow physical, mental and spiritual (*dukkha*), bitter mindedness (*domanassa*) all come through. It is because of this that the entire mass of sorrow arises.

5.4 Grasping via example, . . . how because of the **Khandha or skandha** and **paṭiccasamuppāda** or dependent origination, that fire or conflagration of craving / aversion or **taṇhā** makes you run?

Lets take the example of an ice-cream. Suppose one is walking and see an ice-cream photo and the vendor standing by (may be for the first time OR a repetition).

One sees via eyes, that is one of the 6 *saḷāyatana*, which is a part of *nāma-rūpa*. This sight of the ice-cream, is phassa or contact, . . . the *saññā* or perception of which, . . . causes (*paccayā*), *vedanā* or sensations in mind and body. Due to these sensations, within the mind-body-heart complex, . . . *taṇhā* i.e desire and the craving for or aversion against, the ice-cream arises within. Now this force of desire, either for or against, and the grip of the desire, lead to *upādānam* or attachment, either in loving the object of *saññā* (perception) or hating the object of *saññā* (perception). Based on this, either one consumes the ice-cream or does not eat it! Further, based on repeated *saññā* or perception, *saṅkhārā* of ice-cream, registers within the mind-body-heart of a being and these *saṅkhārā*'s lead to a flow of *viññārā* consciousness.

Thus, this fire or conflagration of desire or *taṇhā*, based on the impressions or *saṅkhārā*, which burns one's senses or *saḷāyatana*, as one repeats the process of enjoyment, makes one run, and run and run . . .

At the end, one consumes or enjoys so much ice-cream that body and mind becomes full of *roga* or sickness in nature, as age progresses.

5.5 The acknowledgement of 4 Noble Truths and the way out, via **Vipassanā / vipaśyanā**

Thus begins the *acknowledgement of the first truth, i.e there is misery in life*. This acknowledgement can only happen when one realizes through ones heart and not just via knowledge gained through senses or through intellectual curiosity. *Next, this misery is due to a cause which forms the second truth*. Since *misery is not perennial, there is the cause which can be eliminated; the third truth*. Finally, the *fourth truth is the revelation that there is "a" way out. It is not "the" way out, but there*

is "a" way out. There is no force here, but an acknowledgement of an existence of a way out of this misery and the countless cycles of birth and death.

These four truths reveal the fundamental nature of phenomena that occurs in a life form (sentient/insentient). The solution to the issues encountered in the four truths are revealed in the next four truths. These truths are basically processes going through which leads to breaking of the cycle of birth and death as well as the miseries associated with it.

To begin with, the essence is to sit still and be. To sit not like a rigid stone on a ground, but as a lotus flower resting on the surface of a pond. Note that the spinal cord needs to be erect with head straight and eyes closed. Now, what happens when one sits still and be? Whatever phenomena in the mind-body-consciousness complex manifests with strongest intensity, comes to awareness. Depending on the structure of one's body, texture of mind and the quality of consciousness, a corresponding experience comes to awareness. For example, if one sits still after having a nice exercise, the temperature of the body comes to awareness. The awareness experiences the intensity of the temperature of the body rising to a peak and then passing off, as a wave rises to a peak and then falls off. Similarly, the density of the body, the throbbing of the heart, the flux of the blood, the flow of the natural breath comes to awareness. The silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena in the gross body is referred to as *kayanupaschyana*.

Longer sittings lead to refinement in awareness when the sensations in the body mainly in the form of currents in the nervous system are experienced. Due to the texture of mind-body complex at a particular moment in time, these subtle sensations might appear as extremely painful, stressful, soothing or blissful (to name a few) in awareness. Again, the silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *vedananupaschyana*.

Deeper sittings lead to further refinement in awareness when the flow of the thoughts or the texture of the mind is experience. Anger, greed, happiness, bitterness, gratefulness, a child like nature, lust to name a few, comes to awareness. The texture of the mind comes to awareness. Silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *chittanupaschyana*.

Further, when the awareness reaches a more refined state after continued practice, the natural laws pertaining to the mind-body-consciousness complex comes to awareness. The rise, the persistence and the gradual decay of the any phenomena appearing on the complex comes to awareness. If a peaceful nature arises, persists and passes off on this complex, it comes to awareness. This silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the natural rise-persistence-decay law is referred to as *dhammanupaschyana*.

Note that these might happen in any order depending on the nature of the mind-body-consciousness complex at a particular moment in time. Again, advanced sittings lead to a state of awareness when one's discriminative intellect, emotions and individual ego comes to awareness. These arise, persist and gradually dissolve into nothingness. The individuality of the ego is of atomic nature in comparison to the vastness of the universal awareness. Steady continued practice leads to loss of individuality which reveal the nature of universal awareness with innumerable qualities like that of purity, benevolence, compassion, love etc.

But does one see the essence of the teachings? The former buddha is now using the stepping stones of the great cycle which he has already experienced and uses his own body as a foundation stone to unlock the cycle. The kaya or body which is a form of ignorance has now become the

stepping stone for meditation. The grip of the body comes to awareness and passes off. So on and so forth with the other aspects of sensations and mind.

A stage comes when there are no wants to go for, no search to go on, no journey to be taken and no effort to be put forth. There is nothing to say, nothing to do and nothing to become. Even the search for nirvana stops. In those moments, the inexplicable state of nirvana manifests. Awareness tastes some nectars in silence. Contentment dawns in awareness and so does abundance as one re-enters the limited domain of nature. Now, even if nirvana happens once, the mind can still be impure and this is not the fully liberated stage. This stage is called Saupadisesa-nibbana. Depending on the individual further stages pass by in time. This journey is long and a slow process for those who wish to walk the slow and a natural path.

It has been heard that Siddhartha begins his journey many life times back to the stage of bodhisattva (nirvana experienced for the first time). As a bodhisattva, he begins perfecting the knowledge of unlocking the cycle of samsara, life after life. In the last life as Siddhartha, buddhahood dawns in him. Now an important point is this. If you want to become a Buddha you will never become. But when the heart experiences and realizes that there is nothing to become, then the journey into buddhahood has already begun. He wants to enter parinirvana at the age of 36, but extends his life for a few more years for the benefit of others. Finally, living a life of Buddha for just one life time, he enters parinirvana. There is/was no desire to live many lives as a Buddha also. The journey ends as truth absorbs him completely, erasing his entire existence. So, nirvana has already been experienced, but previous impressions force the being to again enter the school of samsara to finish what needs to be finished (stage of saupadisesa-nibbana). Life flips between samsara and nirvana as the balance is maintained. Entering parinirvana, this flipping stops.

Initially, while sitting still, the four (kaya - body, vedana - sensation, chit - mind and dhamma - rise/persistence/decay of natural laws) truths of silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation (paschyana) by the awareness are an optimistic, rewarding and a highly scientific way to evolve out of misery.

Extremely important is the way of observation. Neither to be averse with pleasant/unpleasant nor to crave for pleasant/unpleasant phenomena that has come to awareness. In case aversion or craving arises, then there is formation of impressions (sankharas) in the flow of consciousness. Silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation leads to dissolution of impressions and liberation from misery. Not in fighting but in silent experiential acknowledgement or observation of the untampered passage of the phenomena in the mind- body-consciousness complex is the way out.

Thus, the words go deep, in Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada 277-279 Maggavagga 20. Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu (Aniccalakkhaṇavatthu, Dukkhalakkhaṇavatthu, Anattalakkhaṇavatthu) -

Sabbe saṅkhārā aniccā”ti,

All impressions are impermanent,

yadā paññāya passati;

if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe,

thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

Sabbe saṅkhārā dukkhā”ti, All impressions are suffering,

yadā paññāya passati; if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe, thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

"Sabbe dhammā anattā"ti, All dhammās do not have an existential identity or are non-self,

yadā paññāya passati; if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe, thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

The *flowing thoughts of mind like "oh i have to observe" when experienced by awareness indicates chittanupaschayana*. Right observation breaks this flow. *External complexities of life fade away when impurities of one's own words, deeds and actions in life come to awareness which are a result of the impression of mind-body-consciousness complex*.

Here ends the exposition of the eight truths. The *Mahā-saṭṭipāṭṭhan sutta* will be of great help to those interested. But *such knowledge needs a certain level of maturity*. And this maturity dawns when one has experienced from one's heart that there is misery in life. It is only then that the journey begins, in search for freedom from misery. Even some practice to sit still and be, might save one from the misery one finds in. An important aspect to note is that as one sits still, automatically the different aspects of body, sensations, mind and the laws of nature starts coming into awareness. Observation happens naturally, without effort. The path is long and here the processes occur naturally. One cannot force one's way here. As a flower blossoms naturally so does advancement towards enlightenment.

Thus the sayings of Kabir goes well -

Dhere dhere re chala re mana,

Slowly slowly o mind,

dhere sabkuch howay,

slowly everything happens in nature,

mali seeche saw ghara,

the gardener waters a hundred pots,

ritu aaye phal howay . . .

when the weather is right, the fruits will arrive . . .

The *initial teachings begin with the description of the misery, the cause of misery, the possibility of elimination of the cause and the way out of it*. But note that the advanced stages described in *prajna-paramita-sutta* does not contradict the initial teachings. Please keep this note in mind when the paradoxical view is reached later on. Finally, the journey is not via negativa. It appears to be so but in fact it is not. *Samsara and its constituents are a school that help one prepare for nirvana*. The school is not filled with misery. The school provides comfort to move into higher and simpler dimension. "Oh! Samsara is bad." i am chanting 10,000 times or meditating in silence and a dog comes out of love in my presence and i kick it & say "may all sentient beings be happy!" And again start chanting the mantra. "Nirvana! Nirvana! Quick! The fastest way." Let's have so much focus

that i break the rules of samsara. If a queue is there, i get in the middle as i need to finish work by the power of mantra! ”*Samsara* is bad!” My dear! It is the same samsara which has given clothes. Why wear them? Throw them off and walk naked. See what happens! If the flower (*nirvana*) is beautiful then how can mud and water and minerals (*samsara* the school) nourishing the lotus is so bad? Now i am not saying you eat mud. Experience the balance of the paradoxical opposites as they will be revealed in the journey!

6 Sphere / locus / region :: Āyatana

6.1 Etymology

- **Āyatana** (nt.) [Sk. āyatana, not found in the Vedas; but freq. in BSk. From ā + yam, cp. āyata. The pl. is āyatanā at S iv.70. - For full definition of term as seen by the Pāli Commentators see Bdhgh's expln at DA i. 124, 125, with which cp. the popular etym. at KhA 82: "āyassa vā tananato āyatassa vā saṃsāradukkhaṃ nayanato āyatanāni" and at Vism 527 "āye tanoti āyatañ ca nayaṭi ti ā."] - 1. **stretch, extent, reach, compass, region; sphere, locus, place, spot; position, occasion** (corresponding to Bdhgh's definition at DA i.124 as "samosaraṇa") D iii.241, 279 (vimutti°); S ii.41, 269; iv.217; v.119 sq., 318. sq.; A iii.141 (ariya°); v.61 (abhibh°, q. v.) Sn 406 (rajass° "haunt of passion" = rāgādi - rajassa uppatti - deso SnA 381); J i.80 (raj°). Freq. in phrase araṇṇ° a lonely spot, a spot in the forest J i.173; VvA 301; PvA 42, 54. - 2. **exertion, doing, working, practice, performance** (comprising Bdhgh's definition at DA i.124 as paññatti), usually - °, viz. kamm° Nd1 505; Vbh 324, 353; kasiṇ° A v.46 sq., 60; Ps i.28; titth° A i.173, 175; Vbh 145, 367; sipp° (art, craft) D i.51; Nd2 505; Vbh 324, 353; cp. an° non - exertion, in- dolence, sluggishness J v.121. - 3. **sphere of perception or sense in general, object of thought, sense - organ & object; relation**, order. - Cpd. p. 183 says rightly: "āyatana can- not be rendered by a single English word to cover both sense - organs (the mind being regarded as 6th sense) and sense objects". - These *āyatanāni* (relations, functions, recipro- calities) are thus divided into two groups, inner (*ajjhaticāni*) and outer (*bāhirāni*), and comprise the foll.: (a) *ajjhaticāni*: 1. *cakkhu eye*, 2. *sota ear*, 3. *ghāna nose*, 4. *jivhā tongue*, 5. *kāya body*, 6. *mano mind*; (b) *bāhica*: 1. *rūpa visible object*, 2. *sadda sound*, 3. *gandha odour*, 4. *rasa taste*, 5. *phoṭṭhabba tangible object*, 6. *dhamma cognizable object*. - For details as regards connotation & application see Dhs transl. introduc- tion li sq. Cpd. 90 n. 2; 254 sq. - Approximately covering this meaning (3) is Bdhgh's definition of āyatana at DA i.124 as sañjāti and as kāraṇa (origin & cause, i. e. mutually occa- sioning & conditioning relations or adaptations). See also Nd2 under rūpa for further classifications. - For the above mentioned 12 āyatanāni see the foll. passages: D ii.302 sq.; iii.102, 243; A iii.400; v.52; Sn 373 (cp. SnA 366); Ps i.7, 22, 101, 137; ii. 181, 225, 230; Dhs 1335; Vbh 401 sq.; Nett 57, 82; Vism 481; ThA 49, 285. Of these 6 are mentioned at S i.113, ii.3; iv.100, 174 sq.; It 114; Vbh 135 sq., 294; Nett 13, 28, 30; Vism 565 sq. Other sets of 10 at Nett 69; of 4 at D ii.112, 156; of 2 at D ii.69. - Here also belongs ākāsa ānañc āyatana, ākiñcaññ° etc. (see under ākāsa etc. and s. v.), e. g. at D i.34 sq., 183; A iv.451 sq.; Vbh 172, 189, 262 sq.; Vism 324 sq. - Unclassified passages: M i.61; ii.233; iii.32, 216, 273; S i.196; ii.6, 8, 24, 72 sq.; iii.228; iv.98; v.426; A i.113, 163, 225; iii.17, 27, 82, 426; iv.146, 426; v.30, 321, 351, 359; Nd1 109, 133, 171, 340; J i.381 (paripuṇṇa°); Vbh 412 sq. (id.). -uppāda birth of the āyatanas (see above 3) Vin i.185. -kusala skilled in the ā. M iii.63. -kusalatā skill in the spheres (of sense) D iii.212; Dhs 1335. -tṭha founded in the sense - organs Ps i.132; ii.121.

6.2 Questions . . . for you !

- Φ How DEEP is your sphere / locus / region / stretch / extent . . . of your sense of perception?
- Φ How VAST is your sphere / locus / region / stretch / extent . . . of your sense of perception?

- Φ CAN you perceive beyond the 6 Senses & Organs i.e Saḷāyatana?
- Φ CAN you transcend the sphere / locus / region / stretch / extent . . . of your . . . 6 Senses & Organs i.e Saḷāyatana?
- Φ If so, . . . WHAT is the WAY?

6.3 The general phenomena !

Lets, address these questions in a succinct manner, with the hope that the basic fundamentals is grasped! For this section, i will take the CASE of eye or *cakkhu* only, as one of the 6 Senses & Organs i.e Saḷāyatana.

i repeat the below . . . from above, for the sake of continuity!

Lets take the example of an ice-cream. Suppose one is walking and see an ice-cream photo and the vendor standing by (may be for the first time OR a repetition).

One sees via eyes, that is one of the 6 *saḷāyatana*, which is a part of *nāma-rūpa*. This sight of the ice-cream, is phassa or contact, . . . the *saññā* or perception of which, . . . causes (*paccaḷāṇa*), *vedanā* or sensations in mind and body. Due to these sensations, within the mind-body-heart complex, . . . *taṇhā* i.e desire and the craving for or aversion against, the ice-cream arises within. Now this force of desire, either for or against, and the grip of the desire, lead to *upādānaṃ* or attachment, either in loving the object of *saññā* (perception) or hating the object of *saññā* (perception). Based on this, either one consumes the ice-cream or does not eat it! Further, based on repeated *saññā* or perception, *saṅkhārā* of ice-cream, registers within the mind-body-heart of a being and these *saṅkhārā*'s lead to a flow of *viññāṇā* consciousness.

Thus, this fire or conflagration of desire or *taṇhā*, based on the impressions or *saṅkhārā*, which burns one's senses or *saḷāyatana*, as one repeats the process of enjoyment, makes one run, and run and run . . .

At the end, one consumes or enjoys so much ice-cream that body and mind becomes full of *roga* or sickness in nature, as age progresses.

6.4 A perspective . . . on the human eye

i have NEVER studied the physiology of the human eye and the visual perception, EVEN IN THEORY, . . . FORGET THE PRACTICAL. However, i have heard a few things about them! Further based on my ONLY experience of DEVELOPING the EYE deditation . . . [details later!], HERE, i would like to give the LIMITED GRASP of the subject i have based on the meditations i have done and a few research material i have gone through regarding the same in the light of the TEACHING of the Buddha!

What i will do here is that, PRESENT a few IMAGES IN-ORDER . . . such that . . . even looking at them, a LAY person can grasp what is being CONVEYED!

A QUESTION I ASKED IN PHYSICS ?

1. Schematic diagram of **the HORIZONTAL CROSS SECTION of the Human eye**, in fig. 38. The numerical values in the caption, point to the medical terminology / nomenclature used for the different parts of the eye.
2. **Field of View (FOV) of both eyes**, in fig. 39. Whatever the extent of view comes to awareness, during a particular moment, is your Field of View, . . . this is what i can grasp!
3. **FOV from another perspective**, in fig. 40.
4. The **VISUAL PERCEPTION of Human FOV**, in fig. 41. The perceptions that happen when one recognizes the phenomena in pictorial / scenic format in one's mind, through the intricate mechanisms in the brain . . . is visual perception!
5. **Human VISUAL FIELD in BINOCULAR Vision**, in fig. 42. The perceptions that happen with the engagement of a pair of eyes is binocular vision.
6. A **healthy FUNDUS of the right eye**, in fig. 43. Fundus is the interior surface of the eye, in opposition to the lens, which includes macula, optic disc, retina, fovea and posterior pole.

Figure 38: The Schematic diagram of the HORIZONTAL CROSS SECTION of the Human eye. Numbers represent :: 1. Lens, 2. Zonule of Zinn or Ciliary zonule, 3. Posterior chamber and 4. Anterior chamber with 5. Aqueous humour flow; 6. Pupil, 7. Corneosclera or Fibrous tunic with 8. Cornea, 9. Trabecular meshwork and Schlemm's canal. 10. Corneal limbus and 11. Sclera; 12. Conjunctiva, 13. Uvea with 14. Iris, 15. Ciliary body (with a: pars plicata and b: pars plana) and 16. Choroid; 17. Ora serrata, 18. Vitreous humor with 19. Hyaloid canal/(old artery), 20. Retina with 21. Macula or macula lutea, 22. Fovea and 23. Optic disc → blind spot. 24. Visual axis (line of sight). 25. Optical axis. 26. Optic nerve with 27. Dural sheath, 28. Tenon's capsule or bulbar sheath, 29. Tendon. 30. Anterior segment, 31. Posterior segment. 32. Ophthalmic artery, 33. Artery and central retinal vein → 36. Blood vessels of the retina; Ciliary arteries (34. Short posterior ones, 35. Long posterior ones and 37. Anterior ones). 38. Lacrimal artery, 39. Ophthalmic vein, 40. Vorticose vein. 41. Ethmoid bone, 42. Medial rectus muscle, 43. Lateral rectus muscle, 44. Sphenoid bone. Source - Commons (2023c), under CC Attribution BY-SA 3.0 Unported license @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/deed.en>.

Figure 39: Field of View (FOV) of both eyes, horizontally. Source - Commons (d), under CC Attribution BY-SA 4.0 license @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>.

Figure 40: Field of View (FOV) from from another perspective. Source - Commons (2026i), under CC Attribution BY-SA 3.0 Unported license @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/deed.en>.

Figure 41: A human's visual perception in the field of view. Source - Commons (2026h), under CC Attribution BY-SA 4.0 license @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>.

Figure 42: The visual field as the portion of space seen by an eye looking straight ahead and remaining still. When the eye fixates on a point, it can detect lights, colours, and shapes within a limited area of space. This image illustrates some characteristics of the human visual field in binocular vision. Source - Commons (e), under CC Attribution BY-SA 4.0 license @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>.

Figure 43: Fundus photograph of the right eye, showing a fundus with no sign of disease or pathology. It is seen from front so that left in each image is to the person's right. The gaze is into the camera, so the macula is in the center of the image, and the optic disk is located towards the nose (right in image). The optic disk has some pigmentation at the perimeter of the lateral side, which is considered non-pathological. Veins are darker and slightly wider than corresponding arteries. Major nerve pathways are seen as white striped patterns radiating from the optic disk. In addition, there are also lighter areas close to larger vessels seen mainly at upper left in the image (person's upper right), which is regarded as a normal finding in younger people. Photo is taken at Gävle Hospital in Sweden in 2012 on a healthy 25-year old male volunteer. Source - ?, under CC0 1.0 Universal license @ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>.

- **BACK . . . LABEL**, is **PLACED** on the **INSIDE WALL** of the CUBE
- **SOLID RED** line **INDICATES** . . . **LOOKING INTO** the cube!
- **DOTTED RED** line **INDICATES** . . . **LOOKING THROUGH** the **BACK** of the cube
- And the **BLUE SKULL** is _ _ _

Figure 44: The Necker Cube problem shows that with ATTENTION on the CUBE, there are variations in perception of the projection of the cube, itself, though the cube remains same. They say it is optical illusion!

6.5 The Necker Cube . . . problem !

During my 2nd MSc program, while dealing with the development of the kernel methods for classifying regions of interests of the brain and particularly the visual cortex, based on the orientation of the stimuli and the colour of the stimuli, i came across the Necker CUBE problem. See PICTORIAL representation of the problem, in fig. 44.

What came to observation was the following :: ACTUALLY it is NOT an OPTICAL ILLUSION. What happens is that one is GAZING at the Necker CUBE and as TIME progresses, what happens is that SLIGHT MOVEMENT(s) in the ATTENTION . . . EVEN by FRACTION, through or in the eyes happens, DUE to those MOVEMENTS, there is a FLIP in the PERCEPTION of the PROJECTION of the Necker CUBE as, one SEES the ONE PROJECTION of the same CUBE transforming into ANOTHER PROJECTION of the CUBE and BACK and FORTH . . . this is what i could GRASP! But may be i am wrong!

However, i have taken the liberty to present this problem in the context of the above article with the intention that one can see how the combination of skhandas are working together, in synergy to create what happens in the mind-body physiology apropos *saḷāyatana*.

Figure 45: A moving SOAP Bubble, documenting the SNAPSHOTS of Sky and Buildings. Source - Commons (a)

6.6 A Water Bubble . . . perspective on Vision

During my TEMPORARY tenure as a Phd candidate, from 2011 to 2012, i used to BLOW SOAP BUBBLES in thin air . . . to RELAX from the stress! HOWEVER, i don't know what the perception was about me, and i MIGHT have LOOKED like a IDIOT!

NEVERTHELESS, a few DAYS down the line, i just made a COMMENT in front of 2 or 3 - Do you see these DRIFTING Bubble ??? They RECORD the ENTIRE PICTURE of the ROOM, at ONE time point, AND then as the Bubble SHIFTS to ANOTHER Location, in the NEXT time point . . . PROBABLY with the CONFIGURATION of the Bubble also changed, a NEW PICTURE of the SAME ROOM, is RECORDED . . . thus DOCUMENTING a NEW Visual PERSPECTIVE!!!

These observations were made during that time . . . however, it just reflected back from the depths of memory . . . the phenomena that was observed! Note this observation MIGHT NOW add a PERSPECTIVE to this monograph in context of *Āyatana*. Figs. 45, 46 and 47, DEPICT 3 instances of WHAT a Bubble DOCUMENTS, in its TRAJECTORY, as it DRIFTS through THIN Air!

In fig. 48, i pose a question MIGHT be of INTEREST to some in the field of Vision!

Figure 46: A moving Bubble, documenting the SNAPSHOTS of Trees. Source - [Commons \(2025b\)](#)

Figure 47: A moving Bubble, documenting the SNAPSHOTS of Tree, Building and Sky . Source - [Commons \(2026c\)](#)

Can you BUILD a system to record EACH CHANGING CONFIGURATION of the ENVIRONMENT RECORDED / IMPRINTED on A DRIFTING Water / Soap BUBBLE, that DRIFTS through the air in natural order, by the hands of Beloved Mother Nature, WITHOUT touching it, while its TRAJECTORY is NOT INFLUENCED ?

This MIGHT LEAD to the STUDY of VISUAL PERCEPTION, as documented in the Teaching of the Buddha of Cakkhu (eye) Ayatana (sphere / locus / region) ! It could OPEN up a NEW FIELD, to gain perspectives of VISION!

Figure 48: Can you build a SYSTEM for SUCH a Phenomena ???

6.7 Gödel, Escher & Bach (GEB) :: The interconnectedness of Mathematics, Tessellations, Geometry and Music :: by Hofstadter (1999) !

Further advancing this topic of perspectives, i now present a gentle idea of the synergy and interconnectedness of Mathematics, Tessellations, Geometry and Music, by Hofstadter (1999). Hofstadter (1999)'s book is on the works of logician, mathematician, and philosopher, Kurt Friedrich Gödel (April 28, 1906 - January 14, 1978), graphic artist whose work found inspiration from mathematics on woodcuts, lithographs, and mezzotints, Maurits Cornelis Escher (17 June 1898 - 27 March 1972), and composer and musician of the late Baroque period, Johann Sebastian Bach (31 March O.S.21March1685 – 28July1750).

It talks about how . . . there is a DEEP connection between the fields of Mathematics, Tessellations, Geometry and Music, via presentation of various examples and images. The Preface to GEB, under CC BY-SA license @ https://godel-escher-bach.fandom.com/wiki/Preface_to_GEB%27s_Twentieth-anniversary_Edition#cite_ref-1, touches and connects . . . fugues and canons, logic and truth, geometry, recursion, syntactic structures, the nature of meaning, Zen Buddhism, paradoxes, brain and mind, reductionism and holism, and colonies, concepts and mental representations, translations, computers and their languages, DNA, proteins, the genetic code, artificial intelligence, creativity, consciousness and free will - sometimes even art and music, of all things.

6.7.1 Kurt Friedrich Gödel :: in mathematics

In 1929, Kurt Gödel's discoveries in the foundations of mathematics led to the proof of his completeness theorem, which became a part of his Phd Thesis and later the publication of Gödel's incompleteness theorems in 1931 in Gödel and Meltzer (1992).

According to Gödel and Meltzer (1992), the author of the translation states in the PREFACE, which i quote here . . .

Kurt Gödel's astonishing discovery and proof, published in 1931, that even in elementary parts of arithmetic there exist propositions which cannot be proved or disproved within the system, is one of the most important contributions to logic since Aristotle. Any formal logical system which disposes of sufficient means to compass the addition and multiplication of positive integers and zero is subject to this limitation, so that one must consider this kind of incompleteness an inherent characteristic of formal mathematics as a whole, which was before this customarily considered the unequivocal intellectual discipline par excellence.

Further, the INTRODUCTION written by R. B. Braithwaite in Gödel and Meltzer (1992), which i quote here . . .

Gödel's Theorem, as a simple corollary of Proposition VI (p. 57) is frequently called, proves that there are arithmetical propositions which are undecidable (i.e. neither provable nor disprovable) within their arithmetical system, and the proof proceeds by actually specifying such a proposition, namely the proposition g expressed by the formula to which "17 Gen r " refers (p. 58). g is an arithmetical proposition; but the proposition that g is undecidable within the system is not an arithmetical proposition, since it is concerned with provability within an arithmetical system, and this is a meta-arithmetical

and not an arithmetical notion. Gödel's Theorem is thus a result which belongs not to mathematics but to metamathematics, the name given by Hilbert to the study of rigorous proof in mathematics and symbolic logic.

and finally, Jon von Neumann stated that -

Kurt Gödel's achievement in modern logic is singular and monumental - indeed it is more than a monument, it is a landmark which will remain visible far in space and time. . . . The subject of logic has certainly completely changed its nature and possibilities with Gödel's achievement.

Succintly, the Gödel's work on **incompleteness theorems** tackles limitations of formal axiomatic systems and points to the fact that a formal axiomatic system satisfying certain technical conditions cannot decide the veracity of all statements about the natural number, and thus cannot prove its own consistency; **for which** Gödel developed the **Gödel numbering**, which codes formal expressions as natural numbers. Thus, the two formulations we find, are in **Gödel and Meltzer (1992)** -

- ⊖ **First incompleteness theorem Proposition VI:** To every ω -consistent recursive class c of formulae there correspond recursive class-signs r , such that neither $\forall x \text{ Gen } r$ nor $\text{Neg } (\forall x \text{ Gen } r)$ belongs to $\text{Flg } (c)$ (where x is the free variable of r).
- ⊖ **Second incompleteness theorem Proposition XI:** If c be a given recursive, consistent class⁶³ of formulae, then the propositional formula which states that c is consistent is not c -provable; in particular, the consistency of P is unprovable in P ,⁶⁴ it being assumed that P is consistent (if not, of course, every statement is provable). **were**⁶³ c is consistent (abbreviated as $\text{Wid } (c)$) is defined as follows: $\text{Wid } (c) = (\exists x) \text{ Form}(x) \& \text{Bew}_c (x)$

and⁶⁴ *This follows if c is replaced by the null class of formulae.*

Now, **there is another intention of presenting this here.** The talk is about **LOGIC!** **Before we begin, i am NOT CONDEMING OR BELITTLING anyone's work in LOGIC. HOWEVER, LOGIC . . . belongs to the REALM of mind! . . . Is it true? . . . that you yourself know!** That churning of mind is happening and it produces the brilliance of **LOGIC.** **STILL** this is the **MIND** that is **RUNNING**, at a different level! This is depicted in fig. 61. In the depths of meditation, there are stages, where there is **DISSOLUTION** of the **MIND.** When the **MIND DISSOLVES**, Beloved Mother Nature reflects to you something that is **BEYOND** the realm of your **MIND!** This i am saying by experiential knowledge . . . or one may say that there is **CESSATION** of the **MIND . . . for a few moments!**

Lastly, fig. 49 representation of an example of a valid formula and a natural deduction proof of 1st Order Logic Completeness.

6.7.2 **Maurits Cornelis Escher :: in geometrical figures**

Maurits Cornelis Escher was known for his **work on mathematical objects and operations** which encompassed tessellations, explorations of infinity, perspectives, impossible objects, truncated and stellated polyhedra, reflection, symmetry, and hyperbolic geometry, to name a few, **THOUGH**, he admitted that he had **NO MATHEMATICAL** ability!

Figure 49: An example of a valid formula and a natural deduction proof of 1st Order Logic Completeness. Source - Commons (2024c)

Now, it might MIGHT NOT be, that one has MATHEMATICAL maturity, a term used in the field of mathematics, DEPICTING one’s ability to GRASP the abstract behind a formula and to formulate aspects of the abstract. There are MANY who might not have this ABILITY or FORMAL training, however, it has been OBSERVED, that there are MINDS . . . which CAN SOLVE and FORMULATE problems, in a WAY that DOES NOT contain MATHEMATICAL constructs. MAY be . . . there are MANY who can do this . . . but there is NO FORMAL system to TAP that TALENT and SHARPEN that skill!

Nevertheless, am presenting here some of the works, which were FORERUNNERS to and the ORIGINAL works of Escher!

Figure 50: Forerunner of Escher's ENDLESS Stairs : Piranesi's Carceri Plate VII - The Drawbridge, 1745 (reworked 1761). Source - Available at [Commons \(2025c\)](#) with reference to [Locher et al. \(1971\)](#)

Figure 51: Forerunner of Escher's IMPOSSIBLE Perspectives : William Hogarth's Satire on False Perspective, 1753. Source - Available at [Commons \(2026d\)](#) with reference to [Locher et al. \(1971\)](#)

Figure 52: Forerunner of Escher's CURVED Perspectives, Geometries and Reflections : Parmigianino's Self-portrait in a Convex Mirror, 1524. Source - Available at [Commons \(2025d\)](#) with reference to [Locher et al. \(1971\)](#)

Figure 53: Digitally enhanced photograph of a wall tiling at the Alhambra, in Granada, Spain, illustrating wallpaper group "p3"; WAS the inspiration behind Escher's work with tilings of the plane, which he made in 1936. Source - Available at [Commons \(2026e\)](#) with reference to [Locher et al. \(1971\)](#)

Figure 54: Organ of the St. Paul's Church in Leipzig, TESTED by Bach in 1717. Source - Available at [Commons \(2026a\)](#)

6.7.3 Johann Sebastian Bach :: in composition and music

Johann Sebastian Bach was known for his **work music and composition** and by profession, he was **Thomaskantor, violinist, organ expert, composer, keyboard player, conductor, school director**. He belonged to the family of Musicians and in Pali there is a word or a LEVEL of existence in which being are BORN as MUSICIANS. This LEVEL is called **Gandhabba** or **a musician, a singer / a Gandharva or heavenly musician, as a class belonging to the demigods who inhabit the Cātummahārājika realm**. Just a mere reference, in 1717, Bach TESTED the Organ of the St. Paul's Church in Leipzig and fig. 54 refers to the same.

6.8 Addressing the questions posed !

So we comb back, now to the questions i posed to you!

Φ How DEEP & VAST is your sphere / locus / region / stretch / extent . . . of your sense of perception? Let me DIG DEEPER . . . Φ CAN you observe the PROCESS of PERCEPTION that is HAPPENING at the DEEPER level of GRANULARITY? Φ ARE you EVEN AWARE of the PROCESS of the PERCEPTION that is UNFOLDING . . . within your MIND-BODY-BEING complex ? . . . OR . . . Φ ARE you JUST ROLLING with the PHENOMENA and getting ENTANGLED with it ?

Next . . . Φ CAN you PERCEIVE BEYOND the 6 Senses & Organs i.e *Saḥayātana* ? . . . and . . . Φ CAN you TRANSCEND the sphere / locus / region / stretch / extent . . . of your . . . 6 Senses & Organs i.e *Saḥayātana* ? Φ If so, . . . WHAT is the WAY?

6.9 A Way . . . out !

Meditate!

In context of the eye phenomena and perception, i have designed an EYE meditation process, which HELPS one to OBSERVE or SEE (*anupassanā*) the HAPPENINGS in the EYE . . . during the PROCESS of EYE meditation.

Those interested can try the same by DOWNLOADING the respective AUDIO file on OPEN Science Framework (OSF) @ <http://osf.io/8hn5e/files/r9syp>. This work was released in November 2016, though it was developed, while i worked in a HOSPITAL as staff scientist, from 2008-to-2010.

redAs one sits till with eyes closed, with initial slight effort, the attention can be placed in/on the eye balls. Slowly and steadily the sensations in the eyes comes to awareness. Without tampering the sensations and letting the sensations unfold, a lot of impressions get erased giving deep relaxation to the eyes. The greater the duration of the seating, the greater the relief. Sometimes, impressions appear as images in the eyes. As one keeps still, a lot of these images get eradicated.

One can also read through these two webpages also regarding the meditations related to the eyes, i.e. -

- EYE meditation on GOOGLE pages @ [LINK](#)
- MOON meditation on GOOGLE pages @ [LINK](#)

7 Absorptions :: Jhāna, A means to an end!

7.1 Etymology

As per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in Pali for absorptions and the related words to it -

- **Jhāna**¹ (nt.) [from jhāyati, 1 BSk. dhyāna. The (popular etym -) expln of jhāna is given by Bdgh at Vism 150 as follows: "ārammaṇ' ūpanijjhānato paccaṇṇika - jhāpanato vā jhānaṃ," i.e. called jh. from meditation on objects & from burning up anything adverse] **literally meditation**. But it never means vaguely meditation. **It is the technical term for a special religious experience, reached in a certain order of mental states**. It was **originally divided into four such states**. These may be summarized: 1. **The mystic, with his mind free from sensuous and worldly ideas, concentrates his thoughts on some special subject (for instance, the impermanence of all things)**. This he thinks out by attention to the facts, and by reasoning. 2. Then **uplifted above attention & reasoning, he experiences joy & ease both of body and mind**. 3. Then **the bliss passes away, & he becomes suffused with a sense of ease**, and 4. he **becomes aware of pure lucidity of mind & equanimity of heart**. The whole really forms one series of mental states, & the stages might have been fixed at other points in the series. So the **Dhamma - saṅgani makes a second list of five stages**, by calling, in the **second jhāna**, the fading away of observation one stage, & the giving up of sustained thinking another stage (Dhs 167 - 175). And the **Vibhaṅga** calls the first **jhāna the pañcaṅgika-jhāna** because it, by itself, can be divided into five parts (Vbh 267). **The state of mind left after the experience of the four jhānas is described** as follows at D i.76: **"with his heart thus serene, made pure, translucent, cultured, void of evil, supple, ready to act, firm and imperturbable."** It will be seen that there is no suggestion of trance, but rather of an enhanced vitality. In the descriptions of the crises in the religious experiences of Christian saints and mystics, expressions similar to those used in the jhānas are frequent (see F. Heiler Die Buddhistische Versenkung, 1918). Laymen could pass through the four jhānas (S iv.301). **The jhānas are only a means, not the end. To imagine that experiencing them was equivalent to Arahantship (and was therefore the end aimed at) is condemned (D i.37 ff.) as a deadly heresy**. In late Pali we find the phrase **arūpajjhānā**. This is **merely a new name for the last four of the eight Vimokkhā, which culminate in trance**. It was **because they made this the aim of their teaching that Gotama rejected the doctrines of his two teachers. Ājāra - Kālāma & Uddaka - Rāmaputta (M i.164 f.)**. - The **jhānas are discussed in extenso & in various combinations as regards theory & practice** at: D i.34 sq.; 73 sq.; S ii. 210 sq.; iv.217 sq., 263 sq.; v.213 sq.; M i.276 sq., 350 sq., 454 sq.; A i.53, 163; ii.126; iii.394 sq.; iv.409 sq.; v.157 sq.; Vin iii.4; Nd2 on Sn 1119 & s.v.; Ps i.97 sq.; ii.169 sq.; Vbh 257 sq.; 263 sq.; 279 sq.; Vism 88, 415. - They are frequently mentioned either as a set, or singly, when often the set is implied (as in the case of the 4th jh.). Mentioned as jh. 1 - 4 e. g. at Vin i.104; ii.161 (foll. by sotāpanna, etc.); D ii.156, 186; iii.78, 131, 222; S ii.278 (nikāmalābhin); A ii.36 (id.); iii.354;

S iv.299; v.307 sq.; M i.21, 41, 159, 203, 247, 398, 521; ii.15, 37; Sn 69, 156, 985; Dh 372; J i.139; VvA 38; PvA 163. - Separately: the 1st: A iv.422; v.135; M i.246, 294; Miln 289; 1st - 3rd: A iii.323; M i.181; 1st & 2nd: M ii.28; 4th: A ii.41; iii.325; v.31; D iii.270; VvA 4. - See also Mrs. Rh. D. Buddh. Psych. (Quest Series) p. 107 sq.; Dhs. trsl. p. 52 sq.; Index to Saṃyutta N. for more refs.; also Kasiṇa. **-anuyutta** applying oneself to meditation Sn 972; **-anga** a constituent of meditation (with ref. to the 4 jhānas) Vism 190. **-kīlā** sporting in the exercise of meditation J iii.45. **-pasuta** id. (+dhīra) Sn 709; Dh 181 (cp. DhA iii.226); **-rata** fond of meditation S i.53, 122; iv.117; It 40; Sn 212, 503, 1009; Vv 5015; VvA 38; **-vimokkha** emancipation reached through jhāna A iii.417; v.34; **-sahagata** accompanied by jh. (of paññābala) A i.42.

- **Vimokkha (& Vimokha)** [fr. vi+muc, cp. mokkha¹] deliverance, release, emancipation, dissociation from the things of the world, Arahantship D ii.70, 111; iii.34, 35, 230, 288; M i.196 (samaya° & asamaya°); S i.159 (cetaso v.); ii.53,123; iii.121; iv.33; A ii.87; iv.316; v.11; Vin v.164 (cittassa); Sn 1071 (which Nd2 588 expls as "agga" etc., thus strangely taking it in meaning of mokkha², perhaps as edifying etym.); Nd2 466 (in expln of Bhagavā); Ps i.22; ii.35 (as 68!), 243; Pug 11 sq.; Vbh 342; Dhs 248; Nett 90, 100, 119,126; Vism 13, 668 sq.; Miln 159; PvA 98; Sdhp 34, 264. - The three vimokkhas are: suññato v., animitto v., appaṇihito v. Ps ii.35; Vism 658. The **eight vimokkhas or stages of emancipation**, are: the **condition of rūpī, arūpa-saññī**, recognition of *subha*, realization of *ākāsānañc'āyatana*, of *viññāp'ānañc'āyatana*, *ākīñcaññ'āyatana*, *neva-saññā-n'āsaññ'āyatana*, *saññāvedayita-nirodha* D iii.262 (cp. Dial. iii.242), A i.40; iv.306; Vbh 342; expld in detail at Ps ii.38 - 40. [cp. BSk. aṣṭau vimokṣāḥ, e. g. AvŚ ii.69, 153.] - In sequence *jhāna vimokkha samādhi samāpatti (magga phala)* at Vin i.97, 104; iii.91; iv.25; A iii.417, 419; v.34, 38; Vbh 342. - See also jhāna.
- **Samāpatti** (f.) [fr. sam+ā+pad] attainment A iii.5; S ii.150 sq.; iv.293 (saññā - vedayita - nirodha°); Dhs 30= 101; a stage of meditation A i.94; Dhs 1331; J i.343, 473; PvA 61 (mahā - karuṇā°); Nd1 100, 106, 139, 143; the Buddha acquired sanekakoṭṭisāta - sahaṣṣā s. J i.77. The **eight attainments comprise** the four Jhānas, the **realm of the infinity of space, realm of the infinity of consciousness, realm of nothingness, realm of neither consciousness nor unconsciousness** Ps i.8, 20 sq.; Nd1 108, 328; Bu 192=J i.28, 54; necessary for becoming a Buddha J i.14; acquired by the Buddha J i.66; the **nine attainments, the preceding and the trance of cessation of perception and sensation** S ii.216, 222; described M i.159 sq. etc.; otherwise called *anupubbavihārā* D ii.156; A iv.410, 448 & passim [cp. Divy 95 etc.]. - In collocation with jhāna, vimokkha, and samādhi Vin i.97; A iii.417 sq.; cp. Cpd. 59, 133 n. 3.-°bhāvanā realizing the attainments J i.67;°kusalatā success in attainment D iii.212; Dhs 1331 sq.
- **Magga** [cp. Epic Sk. mārga, fr. mṛg to track, trace] 1. a road (usually high road), way, foot - path Vism 708 (maggam agata - pubba - purisa, simile of); VbhA 256 (tiyojana°, simile of a man travelling); DhA i.229. - **addhāna**° high road Vin iv.62; M iii.158; see under addhāna; antāra- magge on the road Miln 16; **ujuka**° a straight way S i.33; DhA i.18; **ummagga** (a) a conduit; (b) a devious way: see ummagga, to which add refs. J v.260; Th 2, 94; **kummagga** a wrong path: see kum°, to which add

S iv.195; Th 1, 1174. **passāva**^o & **vacca**^o defecation & urination Vin iii.127; **visama**^o a bad road S i.48. - 2. the road of moral & good living, the path of righteousness, with ref. to the moral standard (cp. the 10 commandments) & the way to salvation. The exegetic (edi- fying) etym. of magga in this meaning is "nibbān' atthikehi maggīyati (traced by those who are looking for N.), nibbānaṃ vā maggeti, kilese vā mārento gacchatī ti maggo" (VbhA 114). - Usually designated (a) the "**ariya atṭhangika magga**" or the "Noble Eightfold Path" (see atṭhangika). It is mentioned at many places, & forms the corner - stone of the Bud- dha's teaching as to the means of escaping "dukkha" or the ills of life. It consists of 8 constituents, viz. sammā - ditṭhi, sammā - sankappa, °vācā, °kammanta, °ājīva, °vāyāma, °sati, °samādhi, or right views, right aspirations, right speech, right conduct, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, right rapture. The 7 first constituents are at D ii.216 & M iii.71 enumd as requisites for sammā - samādhi. The name of this table of ethical injunctions is given as "maggam uttamaṃ" at Sn 1130, i. e. the Highest Path. See for ref. e. g. Vin iii.93; iv.26; D ii.353; iii.102, 128, 284, 286; It 18; Nd1 292; Nd2 485; Vbh 104 sq. 235 sq., VbhA 114 sq. (its constituents in detail), 121, 216; Vism 509 sq. (where the 8 constituents are discussed). - (b) as **ariya magga**: M iii.72; Pug 17; DA i.176 sq., 225 sq., 233; VbhA 373 sq.; ThA 205. - (c) as **pañcangika** or the Path of 5 constituents (the above first 2 and last 3): Dhs 89; Vbh 110 sq., 237 sq. - (d) other ex- pressions of same import: **dhamma**^o Miln 21; **magga** alone; S i.191 (Bhagavā maggassa uppādetā etc.)=M iii.9=S iii.66; Sn 429, 441, 724 sq., 1130; Dh 57, 273 sq., It 106; VbhA 53, 73. As the first condition & initial stage to the attainment of Arahantship (Nibbāna) it is often found in sequence of either **magga-phala-nirodha** (e. g. Vism 217, cp. Nd2 under dukkha II. p. 168), or **magga, phala, nibbāna** (e. g. Tikp. 155 sq., 158; VbhA 43, 316, 488). - **magga as entrance to Arahantship is the final stage in the recognition (ñāṇa, pariññā, paññā) of the truth of the causal chain, which realises the origin of "ill," the possibility of its removal & the "way" to the removal.** These stages are described as **dukkhe ñāṇaṃ, samudaye ñāṇaṃ nirodhe ñāṇaṃ and magge ñāṇaṃ** at D iii.227, Ps i.118. At the latter passage the foll. chapter (i.49) gives **dukkha-nirodha gāminī paṭipadā** as identical with **magga**. - Note. On the term see Cpd. 41 sq., 66 sq., 175, 186; Dhs trsl.2 58, 299 sq., 362 sq.; Expos. 216, 354n. On passages with **atṭhangika magga** & others where magga is used in similes see Mrs. Rh. D. in J.P.T.S. 1907, pp. 119, 120. - 3. Stage of righteousness, with ref. to the var. conditions of Arahantship divided into 4 stages, viz. **sotāpatti- magga, sakadāgāmi**^o, **anāgāmi**^o, **arahatta**^o, or the stage of entering the stream (of salvation), that of returning once, that of the never - returner, that of Arahantship. - At DhA i.110 **magga-phala** "the fruit of the Path" (i. e. the attainment of the foundation or first step of Arahantship) is identical with **sotāpattiphala** on p. 113 (a) in general: **arahatta**^o S i.78; A iii.391; DA i.224. - (b) in particular as the 4 paths: Nd2 612 A; Vbh 322 sq., 328, 335; Vism 453, 672- 678; DhA iv.30; VbhA 301. - 4. In the Tikapaṭṭhāna (under magga - paccaya - niddesa p. 52) 12 constituents of magga are enumd; viz. paññā, vitakka, sam- māvacā, s - kammanta, s - ājīva, viriya, sati, samādhi, mic- chā - ditṭhi, micchā - vācā, m - kammanta, m - ājīva. **-angāni** the constituents of the Ariyan Path VbhA 120. **-āmagga** which is the (right) road and which is not M i.147; Vism ch. xx (°ssa kovida)=Sn 627; S iii.108 (id.); DhA iv.169

(id.); A v.47 (°ssa ñāṇadassana); Dh 403. **-udaka** water found on the road Vism 338 (simile). **-kilanta** wearied by the road J i.129. **-kusala** one who is clever as regards the road, one who knows the road well S iii.108; Nd1 171; VbhA 332 (in simile); KhA 70, 126. **-kovida**=°kusala Nd1 446. **-kkhāyin** (should be °akkhāyin) one who tells the (right) way M iii.5; Nd1 33. **-jina** Conqueror of the paths Sn 84 sq. **-jīvin** who lives in the right path Sn 88. **-jjhāyin** reflecting over the Path Sn 85. **-ñāṇa** knowledge of the Path VbhA 416. **-ññū** knows the Path Nd1 446. **-tṭhāna** one who stands in the Path, attains the P. see Cpd. 23, 50. **-ttaya** the triad of the paths (i. e. the first 3 of the 4 Paths as given above under 3) DhA iv.109. **-dūsin** highway robber Sn 84. **-desaka** one who points out the way, a guide Sn 84; J iv.257; as°desika at DhA ii.246. **-desin**=°desaka Sn 87. **-dhamma** the rule of the Path, i. e. righteous living Sn 763. **-dhīra** wise as regards the Path Nd1 45. **-paṭipanna** - 1. one on the road, i. e. wandering, tramping DhA i.233. - 2. one who has entered the Path Pv iv.349. **-parissaya** danger of the road VvA 200. **-bhāvanā** cultivation of the Path (i. e. righteousness) Nd1 323. **-mūlha** one who has lost the way VvA 332. **-vaṇṇa** praise of the Path DhA i.115. **-vidū** one who knows the Path Nd1 446. **-sacca** the truth concerning the Path VbhA 114, 124. **-sira** N. of a month DA i.241.

7.2 What is absorption?

Suppose you are reading your favourite book, or a child is watching a favourite cartoon movie, or someone is listening to favourite music . . . etc. That is engaged in a favourite activity. Then may be we ask these questions -

- Φ What is the condition of the mind?
- Φ What is the condition of the being during those moments?

For the majority, DURING those moments, ONE is ABSORBED IN THAT ACTIVITY, to a CERTAIN DEGREE OF PURITY. Is it true? That you know by yourself, through personal experience!

Now, this ABSORPTION, is a CONDITION. In the *Paccayavibhangavara Paccayuddesa* is a section in the *Tikapatthana* of the *Abhidhamma Pitaka*, Part I: *Paccayavibhangavara*, ONE of two of the conditionings are -

jhanapaccayo, maggapaccayo
absorption condition, path condition

So this path and the absorptions that happen in it is a CONDITIONING. HOWEVER the CONDITIONINGS lead to the FINAL GOAL of LIBERATION and are important STEPS in the journey into the realms of the Absolute Truth! ONE MUST NOT DISMISS them, . . . HOWEVER, ONE MUST NOT HOLD ON to them also. IT comes in the journey and then you PASS that LEVEL to a HIGER LEVEL!

In this context, the NEXT section NEEDS to be read . . .

7.3 T. Ma rik pa me/ Ma rik pa ze pa me pa ne/ Ga shi me/ Ga shi ze pay bar du yang me do/ De zhin du duk ngal wa dang/ Kun jung wa dang/ Gok pa dang/ Lam me/ Yeshe me/ Tob pa me/ Ma tob pa yang me do/

In this context, i will QUOTE a paragraph of an article titled - **Prajna-paramita-hridaya / The Heart sutra : Bhagavati, the heart of transcendental knowledge**, released in **October of 2016**, @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which was developed and has a context in the webpage @ <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinah/shriprakashsinha/friendship-1st-teachings-sutta-nipata>. [Citation **Sinha (2017)**].

T. There is no ignorance and no wearing out of ignorance, and so on until no old age and death nor their wearing out. In the same way there is no suffering, no cause of suffering, no ending of suffering and no path; no wisdom, no attainment and no non-attainment.

N. **This part is dangerous, if not experienced properly.** The explanation further dives into deeper realms stating that there is no ignorance and no wearing out of ignorance. After nirvana, the former Buddha points to the cycle of misery and states that ignorance is one of the causes of suffering in *Paticcasamuppada-sutta* (explained before). So how do these paradoxical aspects reconcile each other? The key to this resolution is that when one begins on the journey, the fundamentals are set forth for any novice. The ignorance and the properties of ignorance are stated and how meditation helps one clear the different aspects is stated in detail. Note that *samsara* and *nirvana* are connected! Ignorance is a part of *samsara* but it is used as a means to experience *nirvana* via experiencing emptiness in constituents of ignorance. But when one crosses the bridge of enlightenment, it dawns in awareness that ignorance never existed in the first place and thus there is no wearing out of ignorance. What is being stated is that in emptiness the strength of ignorance is lost as it is virtual/relative and it never existed to begin with. Similarly the idea of old age and death is tackled with. Awareness being universal in nature and when one loses one's individuality as well as association with the mind body complex, experiences that what is doing to die and age is just the aggregates that constitute the compounded materials, however complex they might appear to be. The moment the universal awareness shines forth, the ideas of ignorance, suffering, old age, death etc is erased. On reaching that stage, one declares that there is no suffering, no cause of suffering and no ending of suffering. "No suffering! No cause of suffering!" We started with the first truth that there is misery in life and then there is a cause of suffering and the cause can be eliminated and there is a way out (a path)! Now they say it is nothing. Let's throw all this and enjoy! What for all this? "No! No!" The sutta shows the balance that exists between *samsara* and *nirvana*. One side of the sword is *samsara* and the other is *nirvana*. And the blade of the sword is emptiness. The edge is the balance. It is paradoxical that there is no suffering and there is no ending of suffering. The ending does not happen as long as one is established via experiential knowledge about the emptiness and it ends when there is complete experiential knowledge of the emptiness. Thus, no cause of suffering also exists.

Reaching such a stage, one declares that there is no path and neither there is wisdom. There is no wisdom! But the sutta is packed with wisdom! This is madness! Is it possible to see the paradox? The title of the sutta is the heart of transcendent knowledge which is profound, but here it says that there is no path and no wisdom. Be careful about this!

One walks the path of the four noble truths explained in the *kayanupaschyana*, *vedananu-paschyana*, *chittanupaschyana* and *dhammanupaschyana* and after through these reaches the ultimate stage of nirvana. So when one sits still, one is not moving but different fields of body, sensations, mind and laws come to awareness and passes off. One is using tools of *samsara* to erase the layers that cover universal awareness to experience *nirvana* and emptiness. In emptiness the great balance of *samsara* and *nirvana* exists as both are connected to each other. Passing through *nirvana*, one states there is no path and there is no wisdom. But if one has not experienced nirvana and says there is no path and no wisdom, it is going to bring troubles in life. The river merges in ocean and its identity is lost, but as long as it is flowing in the mainland, it is a river. The path is there and it merges into *nirvana*. There, in *nirvana*, there is no path. Nor there is any attainment and non attainment. Neither there is anything to attain as all grasping is over and nor there is non-attainment as emptiness does not make one devoid of anything because it encompasses everything in it. Emptiness is already there so there is no attainment but reaching the balance and experiencing emptiness, there is attainment (no non-attainment). Development of insight into the paradoxes is the key to unfolding the essence that the *sutta* carries. Repeated meditations and study will help in unlocking the potential that the *sutta* carries with it.

7.4 Absorptions :: an endeavour to express through pictorial representations & an anecdote

Let us start with the anecdote. Try to grasp the essence of the buildup!

- ☞ It has been heard . . .
- ☞ Buddha -
- ☞ Ananda! i am thirsty and it has been half an hour that we have passed the pond. Could you please bring some water from the pond we have passed?
- ☞ Ananda returns after an hour and says - Buddha! the water is dirty and not drinkable. We need to move on! There is pond near by just 10 minutes away.
- ☞ Buddha - Please go again to the pond we passed and see!
- ☞ Ananda returns dejected again and hears the same request. This continues for three or four times and Ananda finally gives up and is fed up.
- ☞ On the last request, Ananda goes to the pond without stating his concern and sits next to the pond and ponders so - Why is he sending me again and again when i have already told the situation!
- ☞ An hour passes near the pond. Finally Ananda returns with pitcher full of crystal clear water and greets the Buddha. Buddha smiles and inquires - How come the water is clear?
- ☞ Ananda - I did not wait to let the water settle. Every time i went there i was stirring the water with the pitcher and making it more dirty. This time i waited till the water became automatically crystal clear.
- ☞ Buddha - Same is state with our minds. We stir the muddy waters of the mind in the hope to clear it and end up making it more dirty. Even if the water is clear and one keeps on steering it, one cannot see the clear sky on it. So stop stirring the mud/water.

So also, when one sits still, then automatically sensations come to awareness and pass off. Vipassana happens automatically and effortlessly without stirring whatever comes into awareness. This process is slow yet it is effective. If one moves mentally also while sitting still, then also one creates impressions in mind. Does not movement in mind cause sankhara? Movement of attention or mental flow itself is due to a deep sankhara. One might state that all sankhara or impressions are impermanent but when? Only when one observes the sankhara with wisdom. One needs to be aware of the movement of mind as movement or the fundamental principle of observing as it is (yathā-bhūta).

In the *Maggavaggo*, of the *Dhammapada*, in *Khuddakanikāya* or the Minor Collection in *Suttapiṭaka*, it is said -

Sabbe saṅkhārā aniccā ti,
yadā paññāya passati,
atha nibbindatī dukkhe -
esa maggo visuddhiyā. [277]

All impressions are impermanent,
when one observes them with wisdom and does not react,
thus one removes sorrow from life,
in this path of purification . . .

Conducting vipassana on ones own being, while moving one's attention is like working through different realms with anticipation that sensations will be observed. Again, does not the movement in the mind lead to generation of impression (sankhara)? For example, when one moves from point A to point B, the movement itself causes friction. The very act causes embedding of seeds of impression in the form of friction within the mind. i am not against this process, but there comes a stage when vipassana happens automatically. Thus sit still and be . . .

Now, lets see the pictorial representations and here i will share a few insights through them.

- Fig. 55 - **Each wave says something, but the water is silent.** On the surface of the ocean, each wave appears different. To the human eye, it is NOT possible to see each an every wave. HOWEVER, the emergence of one wave or its awareness, on the surface of ocean, is interconnected or interdependent, on the all other waves, whether visible or invisible! Each wave says something SPECIFIC, . . . in the VICINITY of waves, . . . WHICH is a SET of SPECIFIC CONDITIONS, . . . HOWEVER, if one considers the OCEAN, IN TOTALITY, . . . the ELEMENT water, . . . of the ocean, is the same in all waves and . . . it is BY the same ELEMENT water of the ocean, that is EXPRESSED in different waves and is INTERCONNECTED and INTERDEPENDENT! It is the LIFE, that is INTERCONNECTED and INTERDEPENDENT, through and through in existence! Life does not move/go anywhere . . . only the configuration of the Cosmos, changes every fraction of a second (if that i take that depth of measurement!) So, in the next fraction, there is an entire change in the configuration of the Cosmos. One moment after another, this configuration changes, as it is impermanent (annica), in Mother Nature. Now, in context of absorption, when a

wave that is you, meditate, that SHEATH of IGNORANCE [at multiple levels] DISSOLVES and one FINDS the deeper truths, though NOT for long durations, that one is LIFE itself, and working in tandem with the Beloved Mother Nature. IN DEEP MEDITATIVE state or Absorptions, the SHEATH of IGNORANCE is DISSOLVED FOR a few moments.

- Fig. 56 - **Absorptions in graphical terms**. As one goes on meditating and absorptions happen again, and again, and again, . . . that GRIP o body on LIFE and that of the IGNORANCE and the CONTORTED patterns or CONDITIONIONS of the mind, loosens and dissolves, repeatedly, while purity begins to over take and with stability comes in life, in such a manner, that it leads to liberation or enlightenment . . . one moment. The CULMINATION OF THE JOURNEY is over life times and in CASE of the Shakyamuni Buddha, it was COMPLETE ERAZURE of the limited identities in existence, who RENOUNCED everything and INCLUDING the PRINCIPLE of LIFE and merged in Parinirvana.
- Fig. 57 - **The natural breath tames the mind**. At advanced stages of Anapana, DEEP absorptions happen! Have discussed about the same in one of the sections below! Further Buddhadasa and Santikaro (1988) talks in detail about Anapana while including on the teachings of the Shakyamuni Buddha.
- Fig. 58 - **Long Journey into the realms of the absolute truth**. It is spread over life times, each life being imbued with meditations and good service activity. Slowly the mind purifies and dissolves in absorptions . . . CLEANSING happens!
- Fig. 59 - **The WAY of the mind is different**. The DEEPER you STEER, the MORE MUDDIER it becomes. The MORE you let it be and in STILLNESS . . . it RESTS and PURIFICATION happens . . . in meditations and via Anapana process! There comes a stage when the MIND DISSOLVES and Beloved MOTHER Nature REFLECTS that which is BEYOND the mind!
- Fig. 60 - **In the stillness of awareness, let Beloved Mother Nature unfold as it is . . . Sit Still and be!** i have been in absorptions of different degrees depending on the CONDITIONING of the MIND and ENVIRONMENT.
- Fig. 61 - **Watching the mind!** Even this thought while SITTING - "PEACE! PEACE! PEACE!" Your MIND is STILL RUNNING. Be Silent and LET the RIVER of MIND FLOW . . . SLOWLY it will SUBSIDE and something else will be REFLECTED! SOMETIMES . . . absorptions will happen!

7.5 **Jhāna** :: as per the Shakyamuni Buddha

This topic is extremely vast and forms the BASIS of the Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings through PRATICAL EXPERIENTIAL KNOWLEDE. So, i would JUST touch some IMPORTANT ASPECTS and PROVIDE IMPORTANT references.

There are TWO DIVISIONS of the ENTIRE spectrum of *Jhāna*. One is *rūpa-jhāna* and the other is *arūpa-jhāna*. Let us first see the meaning of *rūpa* as per the the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago -

- **Rūpa** (nt.) [cp. Vedic rūpa, connected etymologically with varpa (Grassmann). - The nom. pl. is rūpā & rūpāni] **form, figure, appearance, principle of form**, etc.

Each wave says something,
but the water is silent

Figure 55: Each wave says something, but the water is silent.

Figure 56: Absorptions in graphical terms.

- A. Definitions. According to P. expositors rūpa takes its designation fr. **ruppati**, e. g. "ruppanato rūpaṃ" Vism 588; "ruppan' aṭṭhena r." VbhA 3; "rūpa - rūpaṃ=ruppana sabhāvena yuttaṃ" Cpd. 1567 (where **ruppati** is, not quite correctly, given as "change"), "ruppati ti: tasmā rūpan ti vuccati" S iii.86; other defns are "rūpayati ti rūpaṃ" (with cakkhu & the other 10 āyatanas) VbhA 45; and more scientifically: "paresu rūp' ādisu cakkhu - paṭihanana lakkhaṇaṃ rūpaṃ" Vism 446. - Of modern

Figure 57: Anapana.

Figure 58: Long Journey.

interpretations & discussions see e. g. Dhs. transl. introd. ch. vi. (pp. 41 - 63, or 248 - 71); Dial. ii.244; Expos. 67n; Cpd. 270 sq. (where objections are raised to trsln "form," and as better (philosophical) terms "matter," "material quality" are recommended). See also loka for similar etym. - B. (lit.) appearance, form, figure Dhs 597 sq. (=form either contrasted with what is unseen, or taken for both seen and unseen), 751; Mhvs 27, 30 (sīha - vyagghādirūpāni representations of lions, tigers etc.);

Figure 59: Don't STEER the mud!

Figure 60: Sit Sill and be . . .

30, 68 (ravicaṇḍa - tāra - rūpāni id.); 36, 31 (loha° bronze statue); ThA 257. - Esp. beautiful form, beauty S iv.275=Pv ii.958 (as one of the 10 attributes, with sadda etc., of distinction: see also below D ii.a); Miln 285; Mhvs 20, 4 (rūpa - mānini proud of her beauty); PvA 89. - **surūpa** very beautiful ThA 72; **durūpa** of evil form, ugly A ii.203 sq. (dubbaṇṇa+). - In phrase **rūpaṃ sikkhati** Vin i.77=iv.129 the meaning is doubtful; it may be "to study drawing, or arts & craft," or (with Mrs. Rh. D.) "weights

Figure 61: Chittanupaschyana - Watching the mind!

& measures,” or (w. Hardy) ”money changing.” It is said that through this occupation the eyes become bad; it is opposed to **gaṇanā**. - C. (-°) of such & such a form, like, kind, of a certain condition or appearance. In this appln very frequent & similar to E. - hood, or Ger. - heit, i. e. an abstract formation. Often untranslatable because of the latter character. It is similar to **kāya** (cp. expln of ātura- **rūpa** Vv 8314 by abhitunna **-kāya** Vva 328), but not so much with ref. to life & feeling as to appearance and looks. E. g. aneka° Sn 1079 (=anekavidha Nd2 54); adissamāna° invisible PvA 6 (lit. with invisible form); ummatta° as if mad, under the appearance of madness, like a madman Pv i.81; ii.63; eva° in such a condition Pv ii.15; tapassī° appearing to be an ascetic Pv i.32; tāra° the (shapes of the) stars Dhs 617; deva° as a deva PvA 92. Pleonastically e. g. in: anupatta° attaining Pv iv.166; taramāna° quickly Pv ii.62; yutta° fit PvA 157; sucitta° variegated Pv i.109. - Cases ad verbally: citta-**rūpaṃ** according to intention Vin iii.161; iv.177; cetabba - rūpaṃ fit to be thought upon J iv.157. (=°yuttakaṃ C.). - atta-**rūpena** on my own account S iv.97; godha-**rūpena** as an iguana Mhvs 28, 9. - D. (as philos. t. t.) principle of (material) form, materiality, visibility. - There are var. groups of psychological and metaphysical systematizations, in which rūpa functions as the material, gross factor, by the side of other, more subtle factors. In all these representations of rūpa we find that an element of moral psychology overshadows the purely philosophical & speculative aspect. A detailed (Abhidhammatic) discussion of rūpa in var. aspects is to be found at Dhs § 585 - 980. - 1. rūpa as **āyatana** or sense object. It is the object of the activity or sphere of the organ of sight (cakkhu). As such it heads the list of the 6 bāhirāni āyatanāni (see e. g. Nd2 p. 238 A - E & āyatana3) with ”cakkhunā rūpaṃ disvā” (the others: sota>sadda, ghāna>gandha, jivhā>rasa, kāya>phoṭṭhabba, mano>dhamma), cp. cakkhu - viññeyyā rūpā iṭṭhā kantā etc. D i.245; M i.266; cakkhunā rūpaṃ pas-

sati itṭha - rūpaṃ kanta - rūpaṃ etc. S iv.126; - see further: Vin i.34 (sabbaṃ ādittaṃ: cakkhuṃ ādittaṃ, rūpa ādittā etc. with sequence of other āyatanas); D ii.308 sq., 336 sq.; M iii.18 (yaṃ kho rūpaṃ paṭicca uppajjati sukhaṃ somanassaṃ, yaṃ rūpe assādo; cp. Ps ii.109 sq.), 291 (ye te cakkhu - viññeyyesu rūpesu avīta - rāgā etc.); Ps i.79; ii.38 (rūpī rūpāni passaṭī ti vimokkho); Dhs 617, 653, 878; Tikp 28. - 2. (metaphysically) as the representative of sensory or material existence: (a) universally as forming the corporeal stratum in the world of appearance or form (**rūpa**-bhava) as compared with the incorporeal (**arūpa**-bhava), being itself above, and yet including the **kāma**-bhava. (The kāmabhava is a subdivision of rūpabhava, which has got raised into a third main division.) This triad is also found in combns with **loka** or **dhātu** (see dhātu 2 a & d), or **avacara**. See e. g. D i.17; iii.215 (°dhātu), 216 (°bhava); Kvu 370 sq. (°dhātu); Dhs 499 (°āvacara), 585 (°dhātu); Vbh 17 (°āvacara), 25 (as garu - pariṇāma & dandha - nirodha compd with arūpa). A similar sequence **rūpa arūpa & nirodha** (i. e. nibbāna) in old verses at Sn 755; It 45, 62 (rūpehi arūpā santatarā, arūpehi nirodho santataro). On indriya - rūpa "faculty as form" see indriya B. - (b) individually in the sphere of saṃsāra as one (i. e. the material quality) of the substrata of sensory individual existence or the khandhas. They are the 5: rūpa - kkhandha, vedanā°, saññā°, sankhārā°, viññāṇa°; otherwise called **rūp' upādāna-kkhandha** etc. (e. g. D iii.223, 278; Vism 443). See khandha ii. B. - In this property rūpa consists of 28 subdivisions, viz. the 4 (great) dhātūs (mahābhūtāni or else bhūta - rūpa primary matter) and 24 upādārūpāni (i. e. derivative forms or accidentals). These are given in extenso in the rūpakkhandha section of the Vism (pp. 443 - 450), also at Dhs 585; the 24 consist of: cakkhu, sota, ghāna, jivhā, kāya, rūpa, sadda, gandha, rasa, itthindriya, purisindriya, jīvitindriya, ha-daya-vatthu, **kāya** - viññatti, vacī - viññatti, ākāsa - dhātu, (rūpassa) lahutā mudutā kammaññatā, upacaya santati jaratā aniccatā, kabalinkār' - āhāra; cp. defn at Nett 73: cātu - mahābhūtikaṃ rūpaṃ catunnaṃ ca mahābhūtānaṃ upādāya rūpassa paññatti. The **rūpakkhandha** shares with the others the qualities of soullessness, evanescence and ill (anattā, anicca, dukkha); e. g. rūpaṃ ca h' idaṃ attā abhaviṣsa, na y' idaṃ rūpaṃ ābadhāya saṃvatteyya Vin i.13, cp. similarly M iii.282 sq.; S iii.66; quoted and expld in detail at Vism 610; rūpaṃ aniccaṃ Vin i.14; M i.228; iii.18 (also expld at Vism 610); S iii.48, 66, 88; rūpe anicc' ānupassanā Ps ii.186 sq. - See also D ii.301; iii.233; Ps i.23, 53, 104; ii.96, 102, 109 (rūpassa ādīnavo); Vbh 1. sq., 12 sq. (in detail); Kvu 11 sq.; Vism 443 sq.; Tikp 33; VbhA 2, 3, 32 sq.=S iii.142 (with var. similes); DhA iv.100. - (c) in the making up of the individuality as such (**nāma-rūpa**), where in contrast with **nāma** (as abstract, logical, invisible or mind - factor) **rūpa** represents the visible (material) factor, resembling **kāya** (cp. phrase nāma-kāya in same sense). The foll. are current defns of **nāma-rūpa**: **nāma**- (**kāya**)=vedanā, saññā, cetanā, phassa, man-asikāra (otherwise citta - sankhārā), **rūpa**(-**kāya**)=cattāro mahā - bhūtā catunnaṃ m - bhūtānaṃ upādāya rūpaṃ (otherwise kāya - sankhārā) S ii.4; iii.59 sq.; Ps i.183; with explns at Vism 558 & VbhA 169. Defined at Nett 15: "ye phassa - pañcamakā dhammā: idaṃ nāmaṃ, yāni pañc' indriyāni rūpāni: idaṃ rūpaṃ, tad ubhayaṃ nāmarūpaṃ viññāṇa - sampayuttaṃ." Discussed in detail also at Vism 562 (=VbhA 173, 174), 587 - 597; cp. DhA 392 (Expos. 500, where "mind - matter" is given as corresp. couple in trsln, do. Cp. 271 sq. "mind and body"). See also

under paṭicca - samuppāda. - 3. various references: D iii.102, 212, 225, 244, 273; M i.84 (Gotamo kāmānaṃ pariññaṃ paññāpeti, rūpā- naṃ, vedanānaṃ); S ii.198; iii.11 (evaṃ - rūpo siyaṃ, evaṃ vedano etc.), 101 (id., & the khandhas); Sn 867, 874, 943, 1037, 1121; Nd1 425; Tikp 36, 38, 54, 262; Vism 625 (uppaj-janaka°). -**ārammaṇa** a visible thing as object Dhs 146, 365; DhsA 310 (cp. Expos. 407). -**āvacara** world of form, sphere of matter (cp. Expos. 67, 216n, 264) PvA 163. -**ūpaga** (satta) (a being) living in (bodily) form It 62; Sn 754. -**ūpajjivī** f. a woman living on her beauty, i. e. a harlot PvA 46, 201. -**ññu** knowing (var.) bodily forms M i.220=A v.347. -**taṇhā** craving after form D ii.309; iii.216, 244, 280; VbhA 179 (in det.). -**dakka** one clever in forms, viz. an artist (accountant?) Miln 344 (in the Dhamma - nagara). -**dhātu** the element of form, material element Vism 486; Nett 32, 97. See above D 2. -**nimitta** sign of form Ps i.92. -**patta** beautiful J i.61. -**pamāṇika** measuring by form (outward appearance), one of the 4 kinds of measurements which the world takes of the Tathāgata (see A ii.71 & Pug 53), viz. rūpa°, ghosa°, lūkha°, dhamma° DhA iii.113; the same four simi- larly at SnA 242. -**pātubhāva** appearance of form (also as °antara° intermediate form) SnA 245. -**bhava** material existence: see above D 2. -**rāga** lust after rebirth in rūpa D iii.234 (+arūpa°); Nett 28 (pañc' indriyāni rūpīni rūpa - rā- gassa padaṭṭhānaṃ. -**rūpa** material form (mutable material quality?) Cpd. 156, doubtful trsln & expln -**saññā** perception of material qualities, notion of form D i.34; ii.112 (expld in det. at Vism 328); iii.224, 244, 253; Nd2 545; DhsA 200 (cp. Expos. 269). -**saññin** perceiving form D iii.260; Ps ii.38; Sn 1113. -**santati** duration of material form Vism 431; VbhA 21. -**samussaya** accumulation of form, complex form ThA 98. -**samāpatti** attainment of beauty J i.406. -**sampatti** beauty J iii.187. -**siri** personal splendour J i.60.

7.6 TWO DIVISIONS of the ENTIRE spectrum of *Jhāna* :: *rūpa-jhāna* & the other is *arūpa-jhāna*

Succinctly, *rūpa-jhāna* or ABSORPTIONS with FORM as BASIS has four stages and the other *arūpa-jhāna* ABSORPTIONS with FORMLESS as BASIS has four stages.

For the **ABSORPTIONS with FORM as the BASIS**, these four stages are -

- *Paṭhamajhāna* or the First Absorption
- *Dutiyajhāna* or the Second Absorption
- *Tatiyajhāna* or the Third Absorption
- *Catutthajhāna* or the Fourth Absorption

For the **ABSORPTIONS with FORMLESS as the BASIS**, these four stages are -

- *ākāś{anañcāyatanam}* or the the dimension of infinite space
- *viññāṇañcāyatanam* or the dimension of infinite consciousness
- *ākīñcaññāyatanam* or the dimension of nothingness
- *nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam* or the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception

Regarding these . . . now I produce here, the translations of Bhante Sujato from Pali under the Creative Commons Zero(CC0 1.0 Universal) from (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>), available at <https://suttacentral.net/?lang=en>, which i have taken from the representations in <https://theravadan.org/> by Ben Lawrence from which the translations are taken -

7.7 Pali suttas related to ABSORPTIONS with FORM as the BASIS

ᐃ

In the *Sāmaññaphalasutta* (The Fruits of the Ascetic Life) of the *Dīgha Nikāya*, is mentioned the following . . .

7.7.1 Paṭhamajhāna / First Absorption

ᐃ

So vivicceva kāmehi, vivicca akusalehi dhammehi savitakkaṃ savicāraṃ vivekaṃ pītisukhaṃ paṭhamaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharati.

Quite secluded from sensual pleasures, secluded from unskillful qualities, they enter and remain in the first absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of seclusion, while placing the mind and keeping it connected.

So imameva kāyaṃ vivekajena pītisukhena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa vivekajena pītisukhena apphutaṃ hoti.

They drench, steep, fill, and spread their body with rapture and bliss born of seclusion. There's no part of the body that's not spread with rapture and bliss born of seclusion.

Seyyathāpi, mahārāja, dakkho nhāpako vā nhāpakantevāsī vā kamsathāle nhāṇiyacuṇṇāni ākiritvā udakena paripphosakaṃ paripphosakaṃ sanneyya, sāyaṃ nhāṇiyapiṇḍi snehānugatā snehaparetā santarabāhirā phuṭā snehena, na ca paggharaṇī;

It's like when a deft bathroom attendant or their apprentice pours bath powder into a bronze dish, sprinkling it little by little with water. They knead it until the ball of bath powder is soaked and saturated with moisture, spread through inside and out; yet no moisture oozes out.

evameva kho, mahārāja, bhikkhu imameva kāyaṃ vivekajena pītisukhena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa vivekajena pītisukhena apphutaṃ hoti.

In the same way, a mendicant drenches, steeps, fills, and spreads their body with rapture and bliss born of seclusion. There's no part of the body that's not spread with rapture and bliss born of seclusion.

Idampi kho, mahārāja, sandiṭṭhikaṃ sāmāññaphalaṃ purimehi sandiṭṭhikehi sāmāññaphalehi abhikkantataraṇca paṇītataraṇca.

This, great king, is a fruit of the ascetic life that's apparent in the present life which is better and finer than the former ones.

7.7.2 Dutiyajhāna / Second Absorption

Ἐ

Puna caparaṃ, mahārāja, bhikkhu vitakkavicārānaṃ vūpasamā ajjhataṃ sampasādanāṃ cetaso ekodibhāvaṃ avitakkaṃ avicāraṃ samādhijaṃ pītisukhaṃ dutiyaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharati.

Furthermore, as the placing of the mind and keeping it connected are stilled, a mendicant enters and remains in the second absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of immersion, with internal clarity and mind at one, without applying the mind and keeping it connected.

So imameva kāyaṃ samādhijena pītisukhena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa samādhijena pītisukhena apphutaṃ hoti.

They drench, steep, fill, and spread their body with rapture and bliss born of immersion. There's no part of the body that's not spread with rapture and bliss born of immersion.

Seyyathāpi, mahārāja, udakarahado gambhīro ubbhidodako tassa nevassa puratthimāya disāya udakassa āyamukhaṃ, na dakkhiṇāya disāya udakassa āyamukhaṃ, na pacchimāya disāya udakassa āyamukhaṃ, na uttarāya disāya udakassa āyamukhaṃ, devo ca na kālena kālaṃ sammādhāraṃ anuppaveccheyya.

It's like a deep lake fed by spring water. There's no inlet to the east, west, north, or south, and the heavens would not properly bestow showers from time to time.

Atha kho tamhāva udakarahadā sītā vāridhārā ubbhijjivā tameva udakarahadaṃ sītena vārinā abhisandeyya parisandeyya paripūreyya paripphareyya, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato udakarahadassa sītena vārinā apphutaṃ assa.

But the stream of cool water welling up in the lake drenches, steeps, fills, and spreads throughout the lake. There's no part of the lake that's not spread through with cool water.

Evameva kho, mahārāja, bhikkhu imameva kāyaṃ samādhijena pītisukhena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa samādhijena pītisukhena apphutaṃ hoti.

In the same way, a mendicant drenches, steepes, fills, and spreads their body with rapture and bliss born of immersion. There's no part of the body that's not spread with rapture and bliss born of immersion.

Idampi kho, mahārāja, sandiṭṭhikaṃ sāmāññaphalaṃ purimehi sandiṭṭhikehi sāmāññaphalehi abhikkantataraṇca paṇītataraṇca.

This too, great king, is a fruit of the ascetic life that's apparent in the present life which is better and finer than the former ones.

7.7.3 Tatiyajhāna / Third Absorption

E

Puna caparaṃ, mahārāja, bhikkhu pītiyā ca virāgā upekkhako ca viharati sato sampajāno, sukhaṇca kāyena paṭisaṃvedeti, yaṃ taṃ ariyā ācikkhanti: ‘upekkhako satimā sukhavihārī’ ti, tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharati.

Furthermore, with the fading away of rapture, a mendicant enters and remains in the third absorption, where they meditate with equanimity, mindful and aware, personally experiencing the bliss of which the noble ones declare, ‘Equanimous and mindful, one meditates in bliss.’

So imameva kāyaṃ nippītikena sukkena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa nippītikena sukkena apphutaṃ hoti.

They drench, steep, fill, and spread their body with bliss free of rapture. There's no part of the body that's not spread with bliss free of rapture.

Seyyathāpi, mahārāja, uppaliniyaṃ vā paduminiyaṃ vā puṇḍarīkīniyaṃ vā appekaccāni uppalāni vā padumāni vā puṇḍarīkāni vā udake jātāni udake saṃvaḍḍhāni udakānuggatāni antonimuggaposīni, tāni yāva caggā yāva ca mūlā sītena vārinā abhisannāni parisannāni paripūrāni paripphuṭāni, nāssa kiñci sabbāvataṃ uppalānaṃ vā padumānaṃ vā puṇḍarīkānaṃ vā sītena vārinā apphutaṃ assa;

It's like a pool with blue water lilies, or pink or white lotuses. Some of them sprout and grow in the water without rising above it, thriving underwater. From the tip to the root they're drenched, steeped, filled, and soaked with cool water. There's no part of them that's not soaked with cool water.

evameva kho, mahārāja, bhikkhu imameva kāyaṃ nippītikena sukkena abhisandeti parisandeti paripūreti parippharati, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa nippītikena sukkena apphutaṃ hoti.

In the same way, a mendicant drenches, steepes, fills, and spreads their body with bliss

free of rapture. There's no part of the body that's not spread with bliss free of rapture.

Idampi kho, mahārāja, sandiṭṭhikaṃ sāmāññaphalaṃ purimehi sandiṭṭhikehi sāmāññaphalehi abhikkantataraṇca paṇītataraṇca.

This too, great king, is a fruit of the ascetic life that's apparent in the present life which is better and finer than the former ones.

7.7.4 Catutthajhāna / Fourth Absorption

☐

Puna caparaṃ, mahārāja, bhikkhu sukhasa ca pahānā dukkhasa ca pahānā, pubbeva somanassadomanassānaṃ atthaṅgamā adukkhamasukhaṃ upekkhāsati pārisuddhiṃ catutthaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharati.

Furthermore, with the giving up of pleasure and pain and the disappearance of former happiness and sadness, a mendicant enters and remains in the fourth absorption, without pleasure or pain, with pure equanimity and mindfulness.

So imameva kāyaṃ parisuddhena cetasā pariyodātena pharivā nisinno hoti, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa parisuddhena cetasā pariyodātena apphutaṃ hoti.

They sit spreading their body through with pure bright mind. There's no part of the body that's not spread with pure bright mind.

Seyyathāpi, mahārāja, puriso odātena vatthena sasīsāṃ pārupitvā nisinno assa, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa odātena vatthena apphutaṃ assa;

It's like someone sitting wrapped from head to foot with white cloth. There's no part of the body that's not spread over with white cloth.

evameva kho, mahārāja, bhikkhu imameva kāyaṃ parisuddhena cetasā pariyodātena pharivā nisinno hoti, nāssa kiñci sabbāvato kāyassa parisuddhena cetasā pariyodātena apphutaṃ hoti.

In the same way, they sit spreading their body through with pure bright mind. There's no part of the body that's not spread with pure bright mind.

Idampi kho, mahārāja, sandiṭṭhikaṃ sāmāññaphalaṃ purimehi sandiṭṭhikehi sāmāññaphalehi abhikkantataraṇca paṇītataraṇca.

This too, great king, is a fruit of the ascetic life that's apparent in the present life which is better and finer than the former ones.

7.8 Pali suttas related to ABSORPTIONS with FORMLESS as the BASIS

☞

In the *Mūlapariyāyasutta* (The Root of All Things) of the *Majjhima Nikāya* . . . , here only a part of it is presented, which refers to the 4 absorptions of *arūpa*! These are marked in **BOLD!**

nibbānaṃ nibbānato abhijānāti;

He directly knows extinguishment as extinguishment.

nibbānaṃ nibbānato abhiññāya nibbānaṃ na maññati, nibbānasmim̐ na maññati, nibbānato na maññati, nibbānaṃ meti na maññati, nibbānaṃ nābhinandati.

Having directly known extinguishment as extinguishment, he does not conceive it to be extinguishment, he does not conceive it in extinguishment, he does not conceive it as extinguishment, he does not conceive that ‘extinguishment is mine’, he does not approve extinguishment.

Taṃ kissa hetu?

Why is that?

‘Pariññātantaṃ tathāgatassā’ti vadāmi.

Because the Realized One has completely understood it to the end, I say.

Tathāgatavasena sattamanayabhūmiparicchedo niṭṭhito.

Translation that i did on this and which is MISSING ::

The one who has walked and won the path of truth as-it-is or yathābhūta . . .

generally, throughly . . .

The best , excellent / Seventh . . .

leading way (fig.) , method, plan, manner, inference, sense meaning, behaviour conduct .

. . .

which is the ground, soil, earth / place, quarter, district / ground, plane, stage, level . . .

for exact determination, circumscription, range, definition / limit, boundary / limitation, restriction / division . . .

brought or come to an end / finished / accomplished / ready / prepared.

Tathāgatopi, bhikkhave, araham sammāsambuddho pathaviṃ pathavito abhijānāti;

The Realized One, the perfected one, the fully awakened Buddha directly knows earth as earth.

pathaviṃ pathavito abhiññāya pathaviṃ na maññati, pathaviyā na maññati, pathavito na maññati, pathaviṃ meti na maññati, pathaviṃ nābhinandati.

Having directly known earth as earth, he does not conceive it to be earth, he does not conceive it in earth, he does not conceive it as earth, he does not conceive that 'earth is mine', he does not approve earth.

Tam kissa hetu?

Why is that?

'Nandī dukkhassa mūlan'ti-

Because he has understood that approval is the root of suffering,

iti viditvā 'bhavā jāti bhūtaṃ jarāmaṇaṃ'ti.

and that rebirth comes from continued existence; whoever has come to be gets old and dies.

Tasmātiha, bhikkhave, 'tathāgato sabbaso taṇhānaṃ khayā virāgā nirodhā cāgā paṭinissaggā anuttaraṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambuddho'ti vadāmi.

That's why the Realized One - with the ending, fading away, cessation, giving up, and letting go of all cravings - has awakened to the supreme perfect awakening, I say.

Āpam . . .pe . . .

He directly knows water . . .

tejam . . .

fire . . .

vāyam . . .

air . . .

bhūte . . .

creatures . . .

deve . . .

gods . . .

pajāpatiṁ . . .

the Progenitor . . .

brahmaṁ . . .

the Divinity . . .

ābhassare . . .

those of streaming radiance . . .

subhakiṇhe . . .

those replete with glory . . .

vehapphale . . .

those of abundant fruit . . .

abhibhuṁ . . .

the Vanquisher . . .

ākāsānañcāyatanam . . .

the dimension of infinite space . . .

viññāṇaṇcāyatanam . . .

the dimension of infinite consciousness . . .

ākīñcaññāyatanam . . .

the dimension of nothingness . . .

nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam . . .

the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception . . .

diṭṭhaṃ . . .

the seen . . .

sutaṃ . . .

the heard . . .

mutaṃ . . .

the thought . . .

viññātaṃ . . .

the known . . .

ekattaṃ . . .

oneness . . .

nānattaṃ . . .

diversity . . .

sabbaṃ . . .

all . . .

nibbānaṃ nibbānato abhijānāti;

He directly knows extinguishment as extinguishment.

nibbānaṃ nibbānato abhiññāya nibbānaṃ na maññati, nibbānasmimṃ na maññati, nibbānato na maññati, nibbānaṃ meti na maññati, nibbānaṃ nābhinandati.

Having directly known extinguishment as extinguishment, he does not conceive it to be extinguishment, he does not conceive it in extinguishment, he does not conceive it as extinguishment, he does not conceive that ‘extinguishment is mine’, he does not approve extinguishment.

Taṃ kissa hetu?

Why is that?

‘Nandī dukkhassa mūlan’ti-

Because he has understood that approval is the root of suffering,

iti veditvā ‘bhavā jāti bhūtassa jarāmarāṇan’ti.

and that rebirth comes from continued existence; whoever has come to be gets old and dies.

Tasmātiha, bhikkhave, ‘tathāgato sabbaso taṇhānaṃ khayā virāgā nirodhā cāgā paṭinissaggā anuttaraṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambuddho’ti vadāmi’”ti.

That’s why the Realized One - with the ending, fading away, cessation, giving up, and letting go of all cravings - has awakened to the supreme perfect Awakening, I say.”

Tathāgatavasena aṭṭhamanayabhūmiparicchedo niṭṭhito.

Translation that i did on this and which is MISSING ::

The one who has walked and won the path of truth as-it-is or yathābhūta . . .

generally, throughly . . .

The best , excellent / Eighth . . .

leading way (fig.) , method, plan, manner, inference, sense meaning, behaviour conduct .

. . .

which is the ground, soil, earth / place, quarter, district / ground, plane, stage, level . . .

for exact determination, circumscription, range, definition / limit, boundary / limitation, restriction / division . . .

brought or come to an end / finished / accomplished / ready / prepared.

Idamavoca bhagavā.

That is what the Buddha said.

Na te bhikkhū bhagavato bhāsitaṃ abhinanduntī.

But the mendicants did not approve what the Buddha said.

In the *Mahāparinibbānasutta* (The Great Discourse on the Buddha’s Quenching) of the *Dīgha Nikāya* . . . under the section of *Parinibbutakathā* or the Fully Quenched . . . here only a part of it is presented, which refers to the 8 absorptions constituting both *rūpa arūpa!* These are marked in **BOLD!**

*Atha kho bhagavā **paṭhamaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji**, paṭhamajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā **dutiyaṃ***

jhānaṃ samāpajji, dutiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, tatiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā catutthaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, catutthajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā ākāsañācāyatanaṃ samāpajji, ākāsañācāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā viññāñācāyatanaṃ samāpajji, viññāñācāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā ākiñcaññāyatanaṃ samāpajji, ākiñcaññāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā nevasaññānāsaññāyatanaṃ samāpajji, nevasaññānāsaññāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā saññāvedayitanirodhaṃ samāpajji.

Then the Buddha entered the **first absorption**. Emerging from that, he entered the **second absorption**. Emerging from that, he successively entered into and emerged from the **third absorption**, the **fourth absorption**, the **dimension of infinite space**, the **dimension of infinite consciousness**, the **dimension of nothingness**, and the **dimension of neither perception nor non-perception**. Then he entered the **cessation of perception and feeling**.

Atha kho āyasmā ānando āyasmantaṃ anuruddhaṃ etadavoca:

Then Venerable Ānanda said to Venerable Anuruddha,

“parinibbuto, bhante anuruddha, bhagavā”ti.

“Honorable Anuruddha, has the Buddha become fully quenched?”

“Nāvuso ānanda, bhagavā parinibbuto, saññāvedayitanirodhaṃ samāpanno”ti.

“No, Reverend Ānanda. He has entered the cessation of perception and feeling.”

Atha kho bhagavā saññāvedayitanirodhasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā nevasaññānāsaññāyatanaṃ samāpajji, nevasaññānāsaññāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā ākiñcaññāyatanaṃ samāpajji, ākiñcaññāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā viññāñācāyatanaṃ samāpajji, viññāñācāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā ākāsañācāyatanaṃ samāpajji, ākāsañācāyatanasamāpattiyā vuṭṭhahitvā catutthaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, catutthajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, tatiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā dutiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, dutiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā paṭthamaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, paṭthamajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā dutiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, dutiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, tatiyajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā catutthaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajji, catutthajjhānā vuṭṭhahitvā samanantarā bhagavā parinibbāyi.

Then the Buddha emerged from the cessation of perception and feeling and entered the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception. Emerging from that, he successively entered into and emerged from the dimension of nothingness, the dimension of infinite consciousness, the dimension of infinite space, the fourth absorption, the third absorption, the second absorption, and the first absorption. Emerging from that, he successively entered into and emerged from the second absorption and the third absorption. Then he entered the fourth absorption. Emerging from that the Buddha immediately became fully extinguished.

Parinibbute bhagavati saha parinibbānā mahābhūmicālo ahosi bhīmsanako salomahaṃso.

Devadundubhiyo ca phalimsu.

When the Buddha was fully quenched, along with the full extinguishment there was a great earthquake, awe-inspiring and hair-raising, and thunder cracked the sky.

Parinibbute bhagavati saha parinibbānā brahmāsahampati imaṃ gātham abhāsi:

When the Buddha was fully quenched, the divinity Sahampati spoke this verse:

“Sabbeva nikkhipissanti,

“All creatures in this world

bhūtā loke samussayaṃ;

must lay down this bag of bones.

Yattha etādiso satthā,

For even a Teacher such as this,

loke appaṭipuggalo;

unrivaled in the world,

Tathāgato balappatto,

the Realized One, attained to power,

sambuddho parinibbuto”ti.

the Buddha was fully quenched.”

Parinibbute bhagavati saha parinibbānā sakko devānamindo imaṃ gātham abhāsi:

When the Buddha was fully quenched, Sakka, lord of gods, spoke this verse:

“Aniccā vata saṅkhārā,

“Oh! Conditions are impermanent,

uppādavayadhammino;

their nature is to rise and fall;

Uppajjitvā nirujjhanti,

having arisen, they cease;

tesaṃ vūpasamo sukho”ti.

their settling is blissful.”

7.9 Pali suttas related to ABSORPTIONS with FORM and FORMLESS as the BASIS

☞

In the *Sāriputtavagga* (Section of Sāriputta) of *Saṃyutta Nikāya* are presented, the descriptions of the 8 eight absorptions, which includes the 4 absorptions of *rūpa* and 4 absorptions of *arūpa*. These are marked in **BOLD!**

7.9.1 Vivekajasutta :: the Sutta on ”in a state which is free from worldly attachment” :: on 1st Absorption

☞

Ekam samayaṃ āyasmā sāriputto sāvattiyāṃ viharati jetavane anāthapiṇḍikassa ārāme.

At one time Venerable Sāriputta was staying near Sāvattī in Jeta’s Grove, Anāthapiṇḍika’s monastery.

Atha kho āyasmā sāriputto pubbaṅhasamayaṃ nivāsetvā pattacīvaramādāya sāvattim piṇḍāya pāvīsi.

Then Venerable Sāriputta robed up in the morning and, taking his bowl and robe, entered Sāvattī for alms.

Sāvattiyāṃ piṇḍāya caritvā pacchābhataṃ piṇḍapātaṭṭikkanto yena andhavanāṃ tenupasāṅkami divāvihārāya.

He wandered for alms in Sāvattī. After the meal, on his return from almsround, he went to the Dark Forest for the day’s meditation,

Andhavanāṃ ajjhogāhetvā aññatarasmim rukkhamūle divāvihāraṃ nisīdi.

plunged deep into it, and sat at the root of a tree to meditate.

Atha kho āyasmā sāriputto sāyanhasamayaṃ paṭisallānā vuṭṭhito yena jetavanāṃ anāthapiṇḍikassa ārāmo tenupasāṅkami.

Then in the late afternoon, Sāriputta came out of retreat and went to Jeta's Grove, Anāthapiṇḍika's monastery.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando āyasmantaṃ sāriputtaṃ dūratova āgacchantaṃ.

Venerable Ānanda saw him coming off in the distance,

Disvāna āyasmantaṃ sāriputtaṃ etadavoca:
and said to him:

“vipasannāni kho te, āvuso sāriputta, indriyāni; parisuddho mukhavaṇṇo pariyodāto.

“Reverend Sāriputta, your faculties are so very clear, and your complexion is pure and bright.

Katamenāyasmā sāriputto ajja vihārena vihāsī”ti?

What meditation were you practicing today?”

*“Idhāhaṃ, āvuso, vivicceva kāmehi vivicca akusalehi dhammehi savitakkaṃ savicāraṃ vivekajaṃ pītisukhaṃ **paṭhamam jhānam** upasampajja viharāmi.*

“Reverend, quite secluded from sensual pleasures, secluded from unskillful qualities, I entered and remained in the first absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of seclusion, while placing the mind and keeping it connected.

Tassa mayhaṃ, āvuso, na evaṃ hoti:

But it didn't occur to me:

*‘ahaṃ **paṭhamam jhānam** samāpajjāmi’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ paṭhamam jhānam samāpanno’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ **paṭhamā jhānā** vuṭṭhito’ ti vā” ti.*

‘I am entering the first absorption’ or ‘I have entered the first absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the first absorption’.’

Tathā hi panāyasmato sāriputtassa dīgharattaṃ ahaṅkāramamaṅkāramānānusayā susamūhatā.

“That must be because Venerable Sāriputta has long ago totally eradicated I-making, mine-making, and the underlying tendency to conceit.

Tasmā āyasmato sāriputtassa na evaṃ hoti:

That's why it didn't occur to you:

“*ahaṃ paṭhamam̐ jhānam̐ samāpajjāmi*”ti vā ‘*ahaṃ paṭhamam̐ jhānam̐ samāpanno*’ti vā ‘*ahaṃ paṭhamā jhānā vuṭṭhito*’ti vā”ti.

‘I am entering the first absorption’ or ‘I have entered the first absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the first absorption’.”

Paṭhamam̐.

the first.

7.9.2 Avitakkasutta :: the Sutta on ”free from thought / where reasonings cease / free from the working of conception” :: on 2nd Absorption

☞

Sāvattthinidānam̐.

At Sāvattthī.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando . . . pe . . . āyasmantaṃ sāriputtaṃ etadavoca:

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta and said to him:

“*vip̐pasannāni kho te, āvuso sāriputta, indriyāni; parisuddho mukhavaṅṅo pariyodāto.*

“Reverend Sāriputta, your faculties are so very clear, and your complexion is pure and bright.

Katamenāyasmā sāriputto ajja vihārena vihāsi”ti?

What meditation were you practicing today?”

“*Idhāhaṃ, āvuso, vitakkavicārānaṃ vūpasamā ajjhataṃ sampasādanaṃ cetaso ekodibhāvaṃ avitakkaṃ avicāraṃ samādhijaṃ pītisukhaṃ dutiyaṃ jhānam̐ upasampajja viharāmi.*

“Reverend, as the placing of the mind and keeping it connected were stilled, I entered and remained in the second absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of immersion, with internal clarity and mind at one, without placing the mind and keeping it connected.

Tassa mayhaṃ, āvuso, na evaṃ hoti:

But it didn’t occur to me:

*‘ahaṃ **dutiyam jhānam** samāpajjāmi’^{ti} vā ‘ahaṃ **dutiyam jhānam** samāpanno’^{ti} vā
‘ahaṃ **dutiyā jhānā** vuṭṭhito’^{ti} vā’^{ti}.*

‘I am entering the second absorption’ or ‘I have entered the second absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the second absorption’.”

Tathā hi panāyasmato sāriputtassa dīgharattaṃ ahaṅkāramamaṅkāramānānusayā susamūhatā.
“That must be because Venerable Sāriputta has long ago totally eradicated I-making, mine-making, and the underlying tendency to conceit.

Tasmā āyasmato sāriputtassa na evaṃ hoti:

That’s why it didn’t occur to you:

*“‘ahaṃ **dutiyam jhānam** samāpajjāmi’^{ti} vā ‘ahaṃ **dutiyam jhānam** samāpanno’^{ti} vā
‘ahaṃ **dutiyā jhānā** vuṭṭhito’^{ti} vā’^{ti}.*

‘I am entering the second absorption’ or ‘I have entered the second absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the second absorption’.”

Dutiyam.

the second.

7.9.3 Pītisutta :: the Sutta on ”emotion of joy, delight, zest, exuberance” :: on 3rd Absorption

☞

Sāvattihinidānaṃ.

At Sāvattihī.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta and said to him:

“vipasannāni kho te, āvuso sāriputta, indriyāni; parisuddho mukhavaṇṇo pariyodāto.

“Reverend Sāriputta, your faculties are so very clear, and your complexion is pure and bright.

Katamenāyasmā sāriputto ajja vihārena vihāsi’^{ti}?

What meditation were you practicing today?”

“Idhāhaṃ, āvuso, pītiyā ca virāgā upekkhako ca vihāsim sato ca sampajāno sukhañca kāyena paṭisaṃvedemi; yaṃ taṃ ariyā ācikkhanti ‘upekkhako satimā sukhavihārī’ ti tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharāmi.

“Reverend, with the fading away of rapture, I entered and remained in the third absorption, where I meditated with equanimity, mindful and aware, personally experiencing the bliss of which the noble ones declare, ‘Equanimous and mindful, one meditates in bliss.’

Tassa mayhaṃ, āvuso, na evaṃ hoti:

But it didn’t occur to me:

‘ahaṃ tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajjāmi’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpanno’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ tatiyā jhānā vuṭṭhito’ ti vā’ ti.

‘I am entering the third absorption’ or ‘I have entered the third absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the third absorption’.”

Tathā hi panāyasmato sārīputtassa dīgharattaṃ ahankāramamañkāramānānusayā susamūhatā.

“That must be because Venerable Sāriputta has long ago totally eradicated I-making, mine-making, and the underlying tendency to conceit.

Tasmā āyasmato sārīputtassa na evaṃ hoti:

That’s why it didn’t occur to you:

“‘ahaṃ tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajjāmi’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ tatiyaṃ jhānaṃ samāpanno’ ti vā ‘ahaṃ tatiyā jhānā vuṭṭhito’ ti vā’ ti.

‘I am entering the third absorption’ or ‘I have entered the third absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the third absorption’.”

Tatiyaṃ.

the third.

7.9.4 Upekkhāsutta :: the Sutta on “looking on”, hedonic neutrality or indifference / zero point between joy & sorrow / disinterestedness / neutral feeling / equanimity.” :: on 4th Absorption

[E]

Sāvattthinidānam.

At Sāvattthī.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta and said to him:

“vippasannāni kho te, āvuso sāriputta, indriyāni; parisuddho mukhavaṇṇo pariyodāto.

“Reverend Sāriputta, your faculties are so very clear, and your complexion is pure and bright.

Katamenāyasmā sāriputto ajja vihārena vihāsī”ti?

What meditation were you practicing today?”

“Idhāhaṃ, āvuso, sukhasa ca pahānā dukkhasa ca pahānā pubbeva somanassadomanassānaṃ atthaṅgamā adukkhamasukhaṃ upekkhāsatiṃpārisuddhiṃ catutthaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharāmi.

“Reverend, with the giving up of pleasure and pain, and the ending of former happiness and sadness, I entered and remained in the fourth absorption, without pleasure or pain, with pure equanimity and mindfulness.

Tassa mayhaṃ, āvuso, na evaṃ hoti:

But it didn't occur to me:

*‘ahaṃ catutthaṃ jhānaṃ samāpajjāmi’ti vā ‘ahaṃ catutthaṃ jhānaṃ samāpanno’ti vā ‘ahaṃ **catutthā jhānā** vutthito’ti vā”ti.*

‘I am entering the fourth absorption’ or ‘I have entered the fourth absorption’ or ‘I am emerging from the fourth absorption’.”

Tathā hi panāyasmato sāriputtassa dīgharattaṃ ahaṅkāramamaṅkāramānānusayā susamūhatā.

“That must be because Venerable Sāriputta has long ago totally eradicated I-making, mine-making, and the underlying tendency to conceit.

Tasmā āyasmato sāriputtassa na evaṃ hoti:

That's why it didn't occur to you:

*“ahaṃ **catutthaṃ jhānaṃ** samāpajjāmi’ti vā ‘ahaṃ **catutthaṃ jhānaṃ** samāpanno’ti*

vā 'aham catutthā jhānā vuṭṭhito'ti vā'ti.

'I am entering the fourth absorption' or 'I have entered the fourth absorption' or 'I am emerging from the fourth absorption'."

Catuttham.

the fourth.

7.9.5 Ākāsānañcāyatanasutta :: the Sutta on "The Dimension of Infinite Space" :: on 5th Absorption

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Sāvattthinidānam.

At Sāvattthī.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta . . .

"idhāham, āvuso, sabbaso rūpasaññānam samatikkamā paṭighasaññānam atthaṅgamā nānattasaññānam amanasikārā ananto ākāsoti ākāsānañcāyatanam upasampajja viharāmi . . . pe . . .

"Reverend, going totally beyond perceptions of form, with the disappearance of perceptions of impingement, not focusing on perceptions of diversity, aware that 'space is infinite', I entered and remained in the dimension of infinite space. . . ." . . .

vuṭṭhitoti vā'ti.

risen (out of), aroused, / having come back from . . . to blow

Pañcamam.

the fifth.

7.9.6 Viññāṇañcāyatanasutta :: the Sutta on "The Dimension of Infinite Consciousness" :: on 6th Absorption

ᐄ

Sāvattthinidānam.

At Sāvattthī.

Addasā kho āyasmā ānando . . . pe . . .

Venerable ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta . . .

*“idhāhaṃ, āvuso, sabbaso ākāsaṇaṅcāyatanaṃ samatikkamma anantaṃ viññāṇanti **viññāṇaṅcāyatanaṃ** upasampajja viharāmi . . . pe . . .*

“Reverend, going totally beyond the dimension of infinite space, aware that ‘consciousness is infinite’, I entered and remained in the dimension of infinite consciousness . . . ” .

. .

vuṭṭhitoti vā”ti.

risen (out of), aroused, / having come back from . . . to blow

Chaṭṭhaṃ.

the sixth.

7.9.7 Ākiñcaññāyatanaṣutta :: the Sutta on ”The Dimension of Nothingness” :: on 7th Absorption

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Sāvattihinidānaṃ.

At Sāvattihī.

Atha kho āyasmā sāriputto . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta . . .

*“idhāhaṃ, āvuso, sabbaso viññāṇaṅcāyatanaṃ samatikkamma, natthi kiñcīti **ākiñcaññāyatana**{m upasampajja viharāmi . . . pe . . .*

“Reverend, going totally beyond the dimension of infinite consciousness, aware that ‘there is nothing at all’, I entered and remained in the dimension of nothingness. . . . ” . . .

vuṭṭhitoti vā”ti.

risen (out of), aroused, / having come back from . . . to blow

Sattamaṃ.

the seventh.

7.9.8 Nevasaññānāsaññāyatana-sutta :: the Sutta on "The Dimension of Neither Perception Nor Non-Perception" :: on 8th Absorption

ᐄ

Sāvattthinidānaṃ.

At Sāvattthī.

Atha kho āyasmā sāriputto . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta . . .

“idhāhaṃ, āvuso, ākiñcaññāyatanaṃ samatikkamma nevasaññānāsaññāyatanaṃ upasampajja viharāmi . . . pe . . .

“Reverend, going totally beyond the dimension of nothingness, I entered and remained in the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception. . . .” . . .

vuṭṭhitoti vā”ti.

risen (out of), aroused, / having come back from . . . to blow

Aṭṭhamāṃ.

the eighth.

7.9.9 Nirodhasamāpattisutta :: the Sutta on "The Attainment of Cessation" :: on 9th Absorption

ᐄ

Sāvattthinidānaṃ.

At Sāvattthī.

Atha kho āyasmā sāriputto . . . pe . . .

Venerable Ānanda saw Venerable Sāriputta . . .

“Idhāhaṃ, āvuso, sabbaso nevasaññānāsaññāyatanaṃ samatikkamma saññāvedayitanirodhaṃ

upasampajja viharāmi.

“Reverend, going totally beyond the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception, I entered and remained in the cessation of perception and feeling.

Tassa mayham, āvuso, na evam hoti:

But it didn’t occur to me:

‘aham saññāvedayitanirodham samāpajjāmi’ ti vā ‘aham saññāvedayitanirodham samāpanno’ ti vā ‘aham saññāvedayitanirodhā vuṭṭhito’ ti vā’ ti.

‘I am entering the cessation of perception and feeling’ or ‘I have entered the cessation of perception and feeling’ or ‘I am emerging from the cessation of perception and feeling.’”

Tathā hi panāyasmato sārīputtassa dīgharattam ahankāramamañkāramānānusayā susamūhatā.

“That must be because Venerable Sāriputta has long ago totally eradicated I-making, mine-making, and the underlying tendency to conceit.

Tasmā āyasmato sārīputtassa na evam hoti:

That’s why it didn’t occur to you:

“‘aham saññāvedayitanirodham samāpajjāmi’ ti vā ‘aham saññāvedayitanirodham samāpanno’ ti vā ‘aham saññāvedayitanirodhā vuṭṭhito’ ti vā’ ti.

‘I am entering the cessation of perception and feeling’ or ‘I have entered the cessation of perception and feeling’ or ‘I am emerging from the cessation of perception and feeling.’”

Navamañ.

the ninth.

8 Nidāna :: also means references; from the Teachings of the Shakyamuni Buddha, in Pali !

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In *Mahānidānasutta* (The Great Discourse on Causation) of the *Dīgha Nikāya*, are 6 sections, of which, i have mentioned 3 over here, and that too only two are reproduced here for completeness. Sections 2, 3 & 4 are on Self or *atta*.

8.1 Paṭiccasamuppāda :: on Dependent Origination

However, *for brevity*, i quote . . . *imasmim sati*, in . . . *Bahudhātukasutta* (Many Elements), *Majjhima Nikāya* (115 Middle Discourses), regarding . . . *qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'?*

"Kittāvataṅga pana, bhante, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalā bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti?"

"But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'?"

"Idhānanda, bhikkhu evaṃ pajānāti :

"It's when a mendicant understands:

imasmim sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati,

'When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.

imasmim asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati, yadidaṃ -

When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases.

That is :

avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā,

Ignorance is a condition for impressions.

saṅkhārapaccayā viññānaṃ,

Impressions are conditions for consciousness.

viññānapaccayā nāmarūpaṃ,

Consciousness is a condition for name and form.

nāmarūpapaccayā saḷāyatanam,

Name and form are conditions for the six sense fields.

saḷāyatanapaccayā phasso,

The six sense fields are conditions for contact.

phassapaccayā vedanā,

Contact is a condition for feeling.

vedanāpaccayā taṇhā,

Feeling is a condition for craving.

taṇhāpaccayā upādānam,

Craving is a condition for grasping.

upādānapaccayā bhavo,

Grasping is a condition for continued existence.

bhavapaccayā jāti,

Continued existence is a condition for rebirth.

jātipaccayā jarāmarāṇam sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā sambhavanti.

Rebirth is a condition for old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress to come to be.

Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti.

That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.

Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho,

When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.

saṅkhāranirodhā viññānanirodho,

When choices cease, consciousness ceases.

viññāṇanirodhā nāmarūpanirodho,

When consciousness ceases, name and form cease.

nāmarūpanirodhā saḷāyatanirodho,

When name and form cease, the six sense fields cease.

saḷāyatanirodhā phassanirodho,

When the six sense fields cease, contact ceases.

phassanirodhā vedanānirodho,

When contact ceases, feeling ceases.

vedanānirodhā taṇhānirodho,

When feeling ceases, craving ceases.

taṇhānirodhā upādānanirodho,

When craving ceases, grasping ceases.

upādānanirodhā bhavanirodho,

When grasping ceases, continued existence ceases.

bhavanirodhā jātinirodho,

When continued existence ceases, rebirth ceases.

jātinirodhā jarāmaṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā nirujjhanti.

When rebirth ceases, old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress cease.

Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti.'

That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.'

Ettāvataṃ kho, ānanda, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū'ti alaṃvacanāyā'ti.

That's how a mendicant is qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'.”

8.2 **Sattaviññāṇaṭṭhiti** :: on the Planes of Consciousness

Satta kho, ānanda, viññāṇaṭṭhiyo, dve āyatanāni.

Ānanda, there are **seven planes of consciousness** and **two dimensions**.

Katamā satta?

What seven?

Santānanda, sattā nānattakāyā nānattasaññino, seyyathāpi manussā, ekacce ca devā, ekacce ca vinipātikā.

There are sentient beings that are diverse in body and diverse in perception, such as human beings, some gods, and some beings in the underworld.

Ayaṃ paṭhamā viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **first plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā nānattakāyā ekattasaññino, seyyathāpi devā brahmakāyikā paṭhamābhiniḍḍattā.

There are sentient beings that are diverse in body and unified in perception, such as the gods reborn in the Divinity's host through the first absorption.

Ayaṃ dutiyā viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **second plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā ekattakāyā nānattasaññino, seyyathāpi devā ābhassarā.

There are sentient beings that are unified in body and diverse in perception, such as the gods of streaming radiance.

Ayaṃ tatiyā viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **third plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā ekattakāyā ekattasaññino, seyyathāpi devā subhakiṇhā.

There are sentient beings that are unified in body and unified in perception, such as the gods of universal beauty.

Ayaṃ catutthī viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **fourth plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā sabbaso rūpasaññānaṃ samatikkamā paṭighasaññānaṃ atthaṅgamā nānattasaññānaṃ amanasikārā 'ananto ākāso'ti ākāsañācāyatanūpagā.

There are sentient beings that have gone totally beyond perceptions of form. With the disappearance of perceptions of impingement, not focusing on perceptions of diversity, aware that 'space is infinite', they have been reborn in the dimension of infinite space.

Ayaṃ pañcamī viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **fifth plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā sabbaso ākāsañācāyatanāṃ samatikkamma 'anantaṃ viññāṇaṃ'ti viññāṇañācāyatanūpagā.

There are sentient beings that have gone totally beyond the dimension of infinite space. Aware that 'consciousness is infinite', they have been reborn in the dimension of infinite consciousness.

Ayaṃ chaṭṭhī viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **sixth plane of consciousness**.

Santānanda, sattā sabbaso viññāṇañācāyatanāṃ samatikkamma 'natthi kiñci'ti ākiñcaññāyatanūpagā.

There are sentient beings that have gone totally beyond the dimension of infinite consciousness. Aware that 'there is nothing at all', they have been reborn in the dimension of nothingness.

Ayaṃ sattamī viññāṇaṭṭhiti.

This is the **seventh plane of consciousness**.

Asaññasattāyatanāṃ nevasaññānāsaññāyatanameva dutiyaṃ.

Then there is the **dimension of non-percipient beings**, and secondly, the **dimension of neither perception nor non-perception**.

Tatrānanda, yāyaṃ paṭhamā viññāṇaṭṭhiti nānattakāyā nānattasaññino, seyyathāpi manussā, ekacce ca devā, ekacce ca vinipātikā.

Now, regarding these seven planes of consciousness and two dimensions,

Yo nu kho, ānanda, tañca pajānāti, tassā ca samudayaṃ pajānāti, tassā ca atthaṅgamaṃ pajānāti, tassā ca assādaṃ pajānāti, tassā ca ādīnavaṃ pajānāti, tassā ca nissaraṇaṃ pajānāti, kallaṃ nu tena tadabhinanditun”ti?

is it appropriate for someone who understands them - and their origin, disappearance, gratification, drawback, and escape - to take pleasure in them?”

“No hetam, bhante” . . . pe . . .

“No, sir.”

“tatrānanda, yamidaṃ asaññasattāyatanam.

Yo nu kho, ānanda, tañca pajānāti, tassa ca samudayaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca atthaṅgamaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca assādaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca ādīnavaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca nissaraṇaṃ pajānāti, kallaṃ nu tena tadabhinanditun”ti?

“No hetam, bhante”.

“Tatrānanda, yamidaṃ nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam.

Yo nu kho, ānanda, tañca pajānāti, tassa ca samudayaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca atthaṅgamaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca assādaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca ādīnavaṃ pajānāti, tassa ca nissaraṇaṃ pajānāti, kallaṃ nu tena tadabhinanditun”ti?

“No hetam, bhante”.

“Yato kho, ānanda, bhikkhu imāsañca sattannaṃ viññāṇaṭṭhitinam imesañca dvinnam āyatanānam samudayañca atthaṅgamañca assādañca ādīnavañca nissaraṇañca yathābhūtam viditvā anupādā vimutto hoti, ayam vuccatānanda, bhikkhu paññāvimutto.

“When a mendicant, having truly understood the origin, disappearance, gratification, drawback, and escape regarding these seven planes of consciousness and these two dimensions, is freed by not grasping, they’re called a mendicant who is freed by wisdom.

8.3 **Aṭṭhavimokkha** :: on the Eight Liberations

Aṭṭha kho ime, ānanda, **vimokkhā**.

Ānanda, there are these **eight liberations**.

Katame aṭṭha?

What eight?

Rūpī rūpāni passati

Having physical form, they see forms.

ayaṃ paṭṭhamo vimokkho.

This is the **first liberation**.

Ajjhattaṃ arūpasaññī bahiddhā rūpāni passati,

Not perceiving form internally, they see forms externally.

ayaṃ duttiyo vimokkho.

This is the **second liberation**.

Subhanteva adhimutto hoti,

They're focused only on beauty.

ayaṃ tatiyo vimokkho.

This is the **third liberation**.

*Sabbaso rūpasaññānaṃ samatikkamā paṭighasaññānaṃ atthaṅgamā nānattasaññānaṃ amanasikārā
'ananto ākāso'ti ākāsañācāyatanaṃ upasampajja viharati,*

Going totally beyond perceptions of form, with the disappearance of perceptions of impingement, not focusing on perceptions of diversity, aware that 'space is infinite', they enter and remain in the dimension of infinite space.

ayaṃ catuttho vimokkho.

This is the **fourth liberation**.

*Sabbaso ākāsañācāyatanaṃ samatikkamma 'anantaṃ viññāṇa'ti viññāṇañcāyatanaṃ
upasampajja viharati,*

Going totally beyond the dimension of infinite space, aware that 'consciousness is infinite', they enter and remain in the dimension of infinite consciousness.

ayaṃ pañcama vimokkha.

This is the **fifth liberation**.

Sabbaso viññāṇañcāyatanam samatikkamma ‘natthi kiñcī’ ti ākiñcaññāyatanam upasampajja viharati,

Going totally beyond the dimension of infinite consciousness, aware that ‘there is nothing at all’, they enter and remain in the dimension of nothingness.

ayaṃ chaṭṭha vimokkha.

This is the **sixth liberation**.

Sabbaso ākiñcaññāyatanam samatikkamma nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam upasampajja viharati,

Going totally beyond the dimension of nothingness, they enter and remain in the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception.

ayaṃ sattama vimokkha.

This is the **seventh liberation**.

Sabbaso nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam samatikkamma saññāvedayitanirodham upasampajja viharati,

Going totally beyond the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception, they enter and remain in the cessation of perception and feeling.

ayaṃ aṭṭhama vimokkha.

This is the **eighth liberation**.

Ime kho, ānanda, aṭṭha vimokkhā.

These are the **eight liberations**.

Yato kho, ānanda, bhikkhu ime aṭṭha vimokkhe anulomampi samāpajjati, paṭilomampi samāpajjati, anulomapaṭilomampi samāpajjati, yatthicchakam yadicchakam yāvaticchakam samāpajjatipi vuṭṭhātipi.

When a mendicant enters into and withdraws from these eight liberations - in forward order, in reverse order, and in forward and reverse order - wherever they wish, whenever they wish, and for as long as they wish;

Āsavānañca khayā anāsavaṃ cetovimuttiṃ paññāvimuttiṃ diṭṭheva dhamme sayam abhiññā sacchikatvā upasampajja viharati, ayaṃ vuccatānanda, bhikkhu ubhatobhāgavimutto.

and when they realize the undefiled freedom of heart and freedom by wisdom in this very life, and live having realized it with their own insight due to the ending of defilements, they're called a mendicant who is freed both ways.

Imāya ca, ānanda, ubhatobhāgavimuttiyā aññā ubhatobhāgavimutti uttaritarā vā pañīatarā vā natthī”ti.

And, Ānanda, there is no other freedom both ways that is better or finer than this.”

Idamavoca bhagavā.

That is what the Buddha said.

Attamano āyasmā ānando bhagavato bhāsitaṃ abhinandīti.

Satisfied, Venerable Ānanda approved what the Buddha said.

8.4 Anupubbanirodhasutta :: on Progressive Cessations

in the *Anupubbanirodhasutta* (on the Progressive Cessations), of *Sattāvāsavagga* (Abodes of sentient beings), of *Aṅguttara Nikāya* . . .

“Navayime, bhikkhave, anupubbanirodhā.

“Mendicants, there are these **nine progressive cessations**.

Katame nava?

What nine?

Paṭhamam jhānam samāpannassa kāmasaññā niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the first absorption**, sensual perceptions have ceased.

dutiyam jhānam samāpannassa vitakkavicārā niruddhā honti;

For someone **who has attained the second absorption**, the **placing of the mind and keeping it connected** have ceased.

tatiyam jhānam samāpannassa pīti niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the third absorption, rapture has ceased.**

catuttham jhānam samāpannassa assāsapassāsā niruddhā honti;

For someone **who has attained the fourth absorption, breathing has ceased.**

ākāsānañcāyatanam samāpannassa rūpasaññā niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the dimension of infinite space, the perception of form has ceased.**

viññāṇañcāyatanam samāpannassa ākāsānañcāyatanasaññā niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the dimension of infinite consciousness, the perception of the dimension of infinite space has ceased.**

ākīñcaññāyatanam samāpannassa viññāṇañcāyatanasaññā niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the dimension of nothingness, the perception of the dimension of infinite consciousness has ceased.**

nevasaññānāsaññāyatanam samāpannassa ākiñcaññāyatanasaññā niruddhā hoti;

For someone **who has attained the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception, the perception of the dimension of nothingness has ceased.**

saññāvedayitanirodham samāpannassa saññā ca vedanā ca niruddhā honti.

For someone **who has attained the cessation of perception and feeling, perception and feeling have ceased.**

Ime kho, bhikkhave, nava anupubbanirodhā”ti.

These are the **nine progressive cessations.**”

8.5 Kīṭāgirisutta :: at Kīṭāgiri :: on 7 NOBEL ones who still have work to with diligence

In the *Kīṭāgirisutta* (At Kīṭāgiri), of the *Majjhima Nikāya*, is the description of the **7 NOBEL ones** who still have work to with diligence. ONLY a section of this sutta is being reproduced here and for further details one needs to delve into the sutta.

Nāham, bhikkhave, sabbesaṃyeva bhikkhūnaṃ ‘appamādena karaṇīyaṃ’ ti vadāmi;

Mendicants, I don't say that all these mendicants still have work to do with diligence.

na panāhaṃ, bhikkhave, sabbesaṃyeva bhikkhūnaṃ ‘na appamādena karaṇīyaṃ’ ti vadāmi.

Nor do I say that all these mendicants have no work to do with diligence.

Ye te, bhikkhave, bhikkhū arahanto khīṇāsavā vusitavanto katakaraṇīyā ohitabhārā anupattasatthā parikkhīṇabhavasāmyojanā sammadaññāvimuttā, tathārūpānāhaṃ, bhikkhave, bhikkhūnaṃ ‘na appamādena karaṇīyaṃ’ ti vadāmi.

I say that mendicants don't have work to do with diligence if they are perfected, with defilements ended, having completed the spiritual journey, done what had to be done, laid down the burden, achieved their heart's goal, utterly ended the fetter of continued existence, and become rightly freed through enlightenment.

Taṃ kissa hetu?

Why is that?

Kataṃ tesāṃ appamādena.

They've done their work with diligence.

Abhabbā te pamajjiturū.

They're incapable of being negligent.

Ye ca kho te, bhikkhave, bhikkhū sekkhā appattamānasā anuttaraṃ yogakkhemaṃ patthayamānā viharanti, tathārūpānāhaṃ, bhikkhave, bhikkhūnaṃ ‘appamādena karaṇīyaṃ’ ti vadāmi.

I say that mendicants still have work to do with diligence if they are trainees, who haven't achieved their heart's desire, but live aspiring to the supreme sanctuary from the yoke.

Taṃ kissa hetu?

Why is that? Thinking:

Appeva nāmime āyasmanto anulomikāni senāsanāni paṭisevamānā kalyāṇamitte bhajamānā indriyāni samannāyamānā-

‘Hopefully this venerable will frequent appropriate lodgings, associate with good friends, and control their faculties.

yassatthāya kulaputtā sammadeva agārasmā anagāriyam pabbajanti, tadanuttaram - brahmacariyapariyosānam diṭṭheva dhamme sayam abhiññā sacchikatvā upasampajja vihareyyunti.

Then they might realize the supreme culmination of the spiritual path in this very life, and live having achieved with their own insight the goal for which gentlemen rightly go forth from the lay life to homelessness.’

Imam kho aham, bhikkhave, imesam bhikkhū nam appamādaphalam sampassamāno ‘appamādena karaṇīyan’ti vadāmi.

Seeing this fruit of diligence for those mendicants, I say that they still have work to do with diligence.

Sattime, bhikkhave, puggalā santo samvijjamānā lokasmiṃ.

Mendicants, these seven individuals are found in the world.

Katame satta?

What seven?

Ubhatobhāgavimutto, paññāvimutto, kāyasakkhi, diṭṭhippatto, saddhāvimutto, dhammānusārī, saddhānusārī.

One freed both ways, one freed by wisdom, a direct witness, one attained to view, one freed by faith, a follower of teachings, and a follower by faith.

8.6 **Āhuneyyasutta** :: **Nāthavagga** :: on 10 WORTHY ones

In the **Āhuneyyasutta** (10 Worthy ones), of the **Nāthavagga** (Protector), of the **Ānguttara Nikāya**, is the description of the 10 WORTHY ones.

“Dasayime, bhikkhave, puggalā āhuneyyā pāhuneyyā dakkhiṇeyyā añjalikaraṇīyā anuttaram puññakkhettaṃ lokassa.

“Mendicants, these ten individuals are worthy of offerings dedicated to the gods, worthy of hospitality, worthy of a religious donation, worthy of greeting with joined palms, and are the supreme field of merit for the world.

Katame dasa?

What ten?

Tathāgato araham sammāsambuddho, paccekabuddho, ubhatobhāgavimutto, paññāvimutto, kāyasakkhī, diṭṭhippatto, saddhāvimutto, saddhānusārī, dhammānusārī, gotrabhū -

A Realized One, a perfected one, a fully awakened Buddha; an Independent Buddha; one freed both ways; one freed by wisdom; a direct witness; one attained to view; one freed by faith; a follower by faith; a follower of teachings; a lamb of the flock.

ime kho, bhikkhave, dasa puggalā āhuneyyā . . . pe . . . anuttaram puññakkhettaṃ lokassā”ti.

These are the ten individuals who are worthy of offerings dedicated to the gods, worthy of hospitality, worthy of a religious donation, worthy of greeting with joined palms, and are the supreme field of merit for the world.”

9 Nidāna :: also means references; regarding important books related to Shakymuni Buddha's Teachings !

Here it is needed to refer to these important books which might help in the journey, as one meditates and looks through for important points that might aid in the journey. It would be good to have a collection of the same, in case you are interested in deeper aspects of the teachings of the Buddha!

These books contain deeper aspects of study of MIND-MATTER and also have Bhūta, Aṇu, Kalāpas, Dhatū, (s)Khandha.

9.1 General

- ☒ Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma by Dhammajoti (2002)
- ☒ The Manuals of Dhamma by Sayadaw (1999)
- ☒ The Path of Purification : Visuddhimagga by Buddhaghosa and Bhikkhu (1956)
- ☒ The Path of Serenity and Insight : An explanation of the Buddhist Jhānas by Gunaratana (1985)
- ☒ A Manual of Abhidhamma : Being : Abhidhammattha Sangha of Bhadanta Anuruddhācariya by Nārada (1956)
- ☒ A Comprehensive Manual of Abhidhamma : The Abhidhammattha Sangha of Bhadanta Ācariya Anuruddha by Bodhi (1993)
- ☒ Guide Through the Abhidhamma Piṭaka by Nyanatiloka (1938/71)
- ☒ Chanting for Meditators : A monthly Schedule from Myanmar by Ānandajoti (2016)
- ☒ Discourses on Satipaṭṭhāna Sutta by Goenka (1999)
- ☒ Mahāsatipaṭṭhāna Sutta by Institute (1985)
- ☒ Dhammacakkappavattana Sutta : The First Sermon of the Buddha by Weragoda et al. (UR)
- ☒ In the Stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings by Sinha (2025a)
- ☒ Rummaging the teachings of Jetsun Milarepa : From a ruthless murderer to an enlightened master by Sinha (2025b)

9.2 Abhidhamma Piṭaka

- ☒ The Expositor (Atthasālinī) : Buddhaghosa's Commentary on the Dhammasaṅgīhī, the First Book of Abhidhamma Piṭaka, by Tin et al. (1920a)
- ☒ The Expositor (Atthasālinī) : Buddhaghosa's Commentary on the Dhammasaṅgīhī, the Second Book of Abhidhamma Piṭaka, by Tin et al. (1920b)
- ☒ Conditional Relations (Paṭṭhana) : Being Vol. 1 of the Chatthasangayana Text of the Seventh Book of the Abhidhamma Piṭaka, by Sayadaw and Nyun (1969a)
- ☒ Conditional Relations (Paṭṭhana) : Being Vol. 2 of the Chatthasangayana Text of the Seventh Book of the Abhidhamma Piṭaka, by Sayadaw and Nyun (1969b)
- ☒ The Book of Analysis (Vibhaṅga), by (Seṭṭhila)

- ☒ The Book of Pairs (Yamaka), by Sayadaw et al. (1969)
- ☒ Discourse on Elements (Dhātukathā), by Sayadaw and Nyun (1962)
- ☒ Points of Controversy OR Subjects of Discourse : Being A translation of the Kathāvatthu from the Abhidhamma-pitaka, by Aung and Davids (1915)
- ☒ Designation of Human Types (Puggala-Paññatti), by Law (1915)

10 The experience i had :: Elucidating through an image

10.1 Experience # 1

A question i asked in Physics ? i appreciate what you are recognized for in the field of Physics, HOWEVER . . . Has ANYONE of you EVER in LIFE, . . . EXPERIENCED an ATOM *Aṇu* (Pali / Sanskrit) in your PHYSICAL BODY *Kāya* (Pali / Sanskrit) and MIND *Citta* (Pali / Sanskrit) ?

if you ASK me how ??? the ANSWER is . . . ∅ IN the STILLNESS of AWARENESS, as the BODY and MIND sat STIL for LONG . . . Beloved Mother NATURE . . . REVEALED the EXPERIENCE of ATOM with my BODY-MIND complex!

Regarding the EXPERIENCE

∅ It cannot be PUT in WORDS . . . NEVERTHELESS . . . SUCH was the LEVEL of STILLNESS in those moments, that the ATOM itself REVEALED or CAME TO AWARENESS in FULL FORCE . . . with ENERGY RADIATING from it . . . that i COULD FEEL my WHOLE MIND being FOCUSED WITHOUT EFFORT . . . on ONE ATOM in the WHOLE PHYSICAL BODY . . . for a FRACTION of A SECOND or so . . .

∅ The ATOM CAME . . . INTO AWARENESS, . . . *Udaya* (Pali / Sanskrit) PERSISTED for SOMETIME . . . and THEN MOVED AWAY . . . *Vyaya* (Pali / Sanskrit)

∅ i DID NOT HOLD ON . . . to the ATOM . . . i LET it GO . . . Because HOLDING ON i.e. *Upadana* (Pali) leads to MISERY i.e. *Dukkha* (Pali / Sanskrit) and its REALIZATION *Pañña* (Pali) leads to RELEASE or LIBERATION *Vimutti* (Pali) . . . as my BELOVED Mother Nature WORKS by HER WILL in full COMMAND in SILENCE!

The image in fig. 62 was created using the free GNU Image Manipulation Program or the GIMP software package available @ <https://gimp.org>, depicts the experience that i had for a moment, the duration of which i do not know off! Before hand, DO NOT go by the colour that it was WHITE in colour. Have used the CONTRAST to show what it was, while experiencing the atomic particle. SO if i say, that the BLACK background is my CLEAN AWARENESS to whatever DEGREE of PURITY and REFINEMENT, THEN in that PURITY of AWARENESS, the ATOMIC particle CAME to AWARENESS, NATURALLY, AUTOMATICALLY and WITHOUT EFFORT, . . . PERSISTED for some time and then MOVED AWAY! It was NOT SOLIDIFIED, but RADIATING with ENERGY . . . as it GRIPPED MY whole ATTENTION! The WHOLE MIND was AUTOMATICALLY FOCUSED on the ATOMIC particle, AS LONG AS it was there in AWARENESS! Thus the BLURRY WHITE SCINTILLATING ATOMIC particle REVEALED itself, PERSISTED and PASSED off . . . leaving behind a BEAUTIFUL experience, in the STILLNESS of AWARENESS!

10.2 Experience # 2

During one of the 10-day silence retreats @ Vipassana meditation center in Bodh Gaya, Bihar, India, such was the depth of meditation, that coming out of the meditation hall, as i walked through the gravel laid pathway slowly, IN the STILLNESS of AWARENESS, as the eyes moved from one to another in Beloved Mother Nature, be it a leaf, or a few gravel stones or the trunk of a tree or the adjacent walls of the single story building, . . .

Figure 62: A PICTORIAL representation of the EXPERIENCE of the ATOMIC particle! Please go through the MEANING of the COLOUR used in the image!

the ENTIRE VISION was TEEMING with FINEST GRANULAR particles of LIFE itself . . . EACH ONE VIBRATING and RADIATING ENERGY in its VICINITY, in its own frequency! SUCH was the experience, that there WAS DISSOLUTION of BARRIER which PUTS a WALL or SHEATH in the MIND, . . . that this is INTERNAL and that is EXTERNAL.

CONTORTED within in mind-heart, ONE sees ALL CONTORTIONS outside . . . CLEANSED within, ONE sees ALL CLEANLINESS outside . . .

Further, as one advances in the journey of meditations, one gets CLEANSED within, from time to time. THAT CLEANSING is SUCH that there is REFINEMENT of AWARENESS. ONE has AWARENESS, but it is NOT REFINED! It is CORRUPTED by DEFILEMENTS such that ONE CANNOT perceive the FINER ASPECTS of LIFE and Beloved Mother Nature!

Regarding external and internal . . . here i add the Pali words for elucidation of representations of external and internal, for reference!

As per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in Pali for **internal** -

- * **Ajjhatta** (adj. - n.) [cp. Sk. adhyātma, cp. attā], **that which is personal, subjective, arises from within** (in contrast to any-thing outside, objective or impersonal); as adv. & °interior, personal, inwardly (opp. **bahiddhā bāhira** etc. **outward, out-**

wardly); Cp. ajjhattika & see Dhs. trsl. 272. - D i.37 (subjective, inward, of the peace of the 2nd jhāna), 70 = A ii.210; v.206 (inward happiness. a. sukkaṃ = niyakajjhataṃ at- tano santāne ti attho DA i.183 cp. DhsA 169, 338, 361); S i.70, 169; ii..27 (kathaṃ kathī hoti is in inward doubt), 40 (sukkaṃ dukkhaṃ); iii.180 (id.); iv.1 sg. (āyatanāni), 139, 196; v.74 (thitaṃ cittaṃ ajjhataṃ susaṅghitaṃ suvimuttaṃ a mind firm, inwardly well planted, quite set free), 110, 143, 263, 297, 390; A i.40 (rūpasāññī), 272 (kāmacchanda etc.); ii.158. (sukhadukkaṃ), 211; iii.86 (cetosaṃatha), 92 (vūpasantaṃcitta); iv.32 (sankhittaṃ), 57 (itthindriyaṃ), 299 (cittaṃ), 305 (rūpasāññī), 360 (cetosaṃatha), 437 (vūpasantaṃcitta); v 79 sq., 335 sq. (sati); It 39 (cetosaṃatha inward peace), 80, 82, 94; J i.045 (chātajjhata with hungry insides); v.338 (id.); Ps i.76 (cakkhu etc.); Dhs 161 (= attano jātaṃ DhsA 169), 204, 1044; Pug 59; Vbh 1 sq. (khandhā), 228 (sati), 327 (paññā), 342 (arūpasāññī). - adv. °m inwardly, personally (in contrast - pair ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhā vā; see also cpd. °bahiddhā) A i.284; ii.171; iv.305; v.61; Sn 917 (= upajjhayassa vā ā ācariyassa vā te guṇā assū ti Nd1 350). -**cintin thought occupied with internal things** Sn 174, 388.- **bahiddhā** inside & **outside**, personal - external, mutual, interacting S ii.252 sq.; iii.47; iv.382; Nd2 15; Dhs 1049 etc. (see also bahiddhā).

- * **Abbhantara** (adj.) [abhi + antara; abhi here in directive function = towards the inside, in there, with - in, cp. abhi i.1 a] = **antara, i. e. internal, inner, being within or between**; nt. °m **the inner part, interior, interval** (also as ° -) Vin i.111 (satt° with interval of seven); A iv.16 (opp. bāhira); Dh 394 (id.); Th 1, 757 (°āpassaya lying inside); J iii.395 (°amba the inside of the Mango); Miln 30 (°e vāyo jivo), 262, 281 (bāhir - abbhantara dhana); DhA ii.74 (adj. c. gen. being among; v. l. abbhantare). - Cases used adverbially: instr. abbhantarena in the meantime, in between DhA ii.59. loc. abbhantare in the midst of, inside of, within (c. gen. or - °) J i.262 (rañño), 280 (tuyhaṃ); DhA ii.64 (v. l. antare), 92 (sattavass°); PvA 48 (= anto).
- * **Abbhantarima** (adj.) [superl. formation fr. abbhantara in contrasting function] internal, inner (opp. bāhirima) Vin iii.149; J v.38.
- * **Okkamati** [o + kamati fr. kram] **lit. to enter, go down into, fall into. fig. to come on, to develop, to appear in** (of a subjective state). It is strange that this important word has been so much misunderstood, for the English idiom is the same. We say G he went to sleep , without meaning that he went anywhere. So we may twist it round and say that G sleep overcame him , without meaning any struggle. The two phrases mean exactly the same - **an internal change, or development, culminating in sleep**. So in Pali niddā okkami sleep fell upon him, Vin i.15; niddaṃ okkami he fell on sleep, asleep, DhA i.9; PvA 47. At It 76 we hear that a dullness developed (dubbhaṇṇiyaṃ okkami) on the body of a god, he lost his radiance. At D ii.12; M iii.119 a god, on his rebirth, entered his new mother's womb (kucchim okkami). At D ii 63 occurs the question G if consciousness were not to develop in the womb? (viññāṇaṃ na okkamissatha) S v.283 G abiding in the sense of bliss ' (sukha - saññaṃ okkamitvā). See also Pug 13 = 28 (niyāma okk°, G he enters on the Path '). - Caus. okkāmeti to make enter, to bring to S iv.312 (saggamaṃ). - pp. okkanta. See also avakkamati.

* **Mano & Mana(s)** (nt.) [Vedic *manah*, see etym. under *maññati*] I. Declension. Like all other nouns of old *s* - stems *mano* has partly retained the *s* forms (cp. *cetaḥ*

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ceto) & partly follows the *a* - declension. The form *mano* is found throughout in cpds. as *mano*^o, the other *mana* at the end of cpds. as *mana*^o. From stem *manas* an adj. *manasa* is formed and the der. *mānasa* & *manassa* (-^o). - nom. *mano* freq.; & *manas* Dh 96, acc. *mano* Sn 270, 388; SnA 11, and freq.; also *manas* Sn 659=A ii.3; v.171=Nett 132; Sn 678; Cp i.85; Vism 466; gen. dat. *manaso* Sn 470, 967; Dh 390 (*man-* aso *piya*); Pv ii.111 (*manaso piya=manasā piya* PvA 71); instr. *manasā* Sn 330, 365, 834 (m. *cintayanto*), 1030; M iii.179; Dh 1; Pv ii.97 (m. *pi cetaye*); also *manena* DhA i.42; DhsA 72; abl. *manato* S iv.65; DhA i.23; Vism 466; loc. *manasmiṃ* S iv.65; *manamhi* Vism 466; also *mane* DhA i.23,

manasi (see this in compn *manasi karoti*, below). - II. Meaning: mind, thought D iii.96, 102, 206, 226, 244, 269, 281; S i.16, 172; ii.94; M iii.55; A iii.443; v.171; Sn 77, 424, 829, 873; Dh 116, 300; Sdhp 369. - 1. *Mano* represents the intellectual functioning of consciousness, while *viññāṇa* represents the field of sense and sense - reaction ("perception"), and *citta* the subjective aspect of consciousness (cp. Mrs. Rh. D. Buddhist Psychology p. 19) - The rendering with "mind" covers most of the connotation; sometimes it may be translated "thought." As "mind" it embodies the rational faculty of man, which, as the subjective side in our relation to the objective world, may be regarded as a special sense, acting on the world, a sense adapted to the rationality (reasonableness, *dhamma*) of the phenomena, as our eye is adapted to the visibility of the latter. Thus it ranges as the 6th sense in the classification of the senses and their respective spheres (the *āyatana*ni or relations of subject and object, the *ajjhakkāni* & the *bāhirāni*: see *āyatana* 3). These are: (1) *cakkhu* (eye) which deals with the sight of form (*rūpa*); (2) *sota* (ear) dealing with the hearing of sound (*sadda*); (3) *ghāṇa* (nose) with the smelling of smells (*gandha*); (4) *jivhā* (tongue), with the tasting of tastes (*rasa*); (5) *kāya* (touch), with the touching of tangible objects (*phoṭṭhabba*); (6) *mano*, with the sensing (*viññāya*) of rational objects or cognisables (*dhamma*). Thus it is the *sensus communis* (Mrs. Rh. D. Buddh. Psych. 140, 163) which recognises the world as a "mundus sensibilis" (*dhamma*). Both sides are an inseparable unity: the mind fits the world as the eye fits the light, or in other words: *mano* is the counterpart of *dhammā*, the subjective *dh*. *Dhamma* in this sense is the rationality or lawfulness of the Universe (see *dhamma* B. 1), Cosmic Order, Natural Law. It may even be taken quite generally as the "empirical. world" (as Geiger, e. g. interprets it in his *Pali Dhamma* p. 80 - 82, pointing out the substitution of *vattu* for *dhamma* at Kvu 126 sq. i. e. the material world), as the world of "things," of phenomena in general without specification as regards sound, sight, smell, etc. - *Dhamma* as counterpart of *mano* is rather an abstract (pluralistic) representation of the world, i. e. the phenomena as such with a certain inherent rationality; *manas* is the receiver of these phenomena in their abstract meaning, it is the abstract sense, so to speak. Of course, to explain *manas* and its function one has to resort to terms of materiality, and thus it happens that the term *viññāṇi*, used of *manas*, is also used of the 5th sense, that of touch (to which *mano* is closely related, cp. our E. expressions

of touch as denoting rational, abstract processes: warm & cold used figuratively; to grasp anything; terror - stricken; deeply moved feeling > Lat. *palpare* to palpitate, etc.). We might say of the mind "sensing," that *manas* "senses" (as a refined sense of touch) the "sensibility" (*dhamma*) of the objects, or as Cpd. 183 expresses it "cognizable objects." See also *kāya* II.; and *phassa*. - 2. In Buddhist Psychological Logic the concept *mano* is often more definitely circumscribed by the addition of the terms (*man* -)*āyatana*, (*man* -)*indriya* and (*mano* -)*dhātu*, which are practically all the same as *mano* (and its objective correspondent *dhammā*). Cp. also below No. 3. The additional terms try to give it the rank of a category of thought. On *mano* - *dhātu* and *m* - *āyatana* see also the discourse by S. Z. Aung. Cpd. 256 - 59, with Mrs. Rh. D.'s apt remarks on p. 259. - The position of *manas* among the 6 *āyatanas* (or *indriyas*) is one of control over the other 5 (pure and simple senses). This is expressed e. g. at M i.295 (commented on at DhsA 72) and S v.217 (*mano nesaṃ gocara - visayaṃ pac- canubhoti*: *mano* enjoys the function - spheres of the other senses; cp. Geiger, *Dhamma* 81; as in the *Sāṅkhya*: Garbe, *Sāṅkhya Philosophie* 252 sq.). Cp. Vin i.36; "ettha ca te *mano* na ramittha rūpesu saddesu atho rasesu." - 3. As regards the relation of *manas* to *citta*, it may be stated, that *citta* is more substantial (as indicated by translation "heart"), more elemental as the seat of emotion, whereas *manas* is the finer element, a subtler feeling or thinking as such. See also *citta*2 I., and on rel. to *viññāṇa* & *citta* see *citta*2 IV. 2b. In the more popular opinion and general phraseology however *manas* is almost synonymous with *citta* as opposed to body, *cittaṃ iti pi mano iti pi* S ii.94. So in the triad "thought (i. e. intention) speech and action" *manas* interchanges with *citta*: see *kāya* III. - The formula runs *kāyena vācāya manasā*, e. g. M iii.178 (*sucar- itaṃ caritvā*); Dh 391 (*natthi dukkaṭaṃ*), cp. Dh 96; *santaṃ tassa manasā, santā vācā ca kamma ca*. Besides with *citta*: *kāyena vācāya uda cetasā* S i.93, 102; A i.63. *rakkhitena k. vācāya citta* S ii.231; iv.112. - It is further combd with *citta* in the scholastic (popular) definition of *manas*, found in identical words at all Cy. passages: "mano" is "cittaṃ mano mānasasā hadayaṃ, paṇḍaram, man - āyatanasā... mano - viññāṇa - dhātu" (mind sensibility). Thus e. g. at Nd1 3 (for *mano*), 176 (id.); Nd2 494 (which however leaves out *cittaṃ* in exegesis of Sn 1142, 1413, but has it in No. 495 in exegesis of Sn 1039); Dhs 6 (in defn of *citta*), 17 (of *man*' in- *driyaṃ*), 65 (of *man* - *āyatanasā*), 68 (of *mano* - *viññāṇa* - *dhātu*). - The close relation between the two appears further from their combn in the formula of the *ādesanā-pāṭihāriyaṃ* (wonder of manifestation, i. e. the discovery of other peo- ples' thoughts & intentions), viz. *evam pi te mano ittham pi te mano iti pi te cittaṃ*: "so & so is in your mind. . . so & so are your emotions"; D i.213= iii.103=A i.170. - At S i.53 both are mutually influenced in their state of unsteadiness and fear: *niccaṃ uttaraṃ idaṃ cittaṃ* (heart), *niccaṃ ubbiggaṃ idaṃ mano* (mind). The same relation (*citta* as instrument or manifestation of *mano*) is evident from J i.36, where the pas- sage runs: *sīho cittaṃ pasādesi. Sathā tassa manasā oloketva vyākāsi* . . . At PvA 264 *mano* (of Pv iv.71) is expld by *cit- taṃ*; *pīti mano* of Sn 766 (glad of heart) expld at SnA 512 by *santuṭṭha - citto*; *nibbānamanaso* of Sn 942 at SnA 567 by *nibbāna - ninna - citto*. In the phrase *yathā-manena* "from his heart," i. e. sincerely, voluntarily DhA i.42, *mano* clearly acts as *citta*. - 4. Phrases: *manasā uppādeti* to make up one's mind, to resolve DhA ii.140 (cp. *citt*' *uppāda*); *manasā*

karoti: (a) to fix one's mind upon, to give thought to, find pleasure or to delight in (loc.) J iv.223 (rūpe na manam kare=itthi - rūpe nimittam na gaṇḥeyyāsi C. Cp. the simi- lar & usual manasi - karoti in same sense); vi.45 (Pass. gīte karute mano); (b) to make up one's mind DhA ii.87; manam gaṇhāti to "take the mind," take the fancy, to please, to win approval J iv.132; DhA ii.48. - III. °mana: dhamm - ud- dhacca - viggahita° A ii.157 (read °mano for °manā); sankil- iṭṭha - manā narā Th 2, 344; atta° pleased; gedhita° greedy Pv ii.82; dum° depressed in mind, sad or sick at heart D ii.148; S i.103; Vin i.21; A ii.59, 61, 198; Th 2, 484; J i.189; opp. sumana elated, joyful Pv ii.948 (=somanassajāta PvA 132); pīti° glad or joyful of heart Sn 766 (expld by tuṭṭha - mano, haṭṭha - mano, attamano etc. at Nd1 3; by santuṭṭha - citto at SnA 512). - IV. manasi-karoti (etc.) to fix the mind intently, to bear in mind, take to heart, ponder, think upon, consider, recognise. - 1. (v.) pres. 1st pl. °karoma Vin i.103; imper. 2nd sg. °karohi, often in formula "suṇāhi sād- hukam m. - k." "harken and pay attention" D i.124, 157, 249; cp. M. i.7; A i.227; pl. 2nd °karotha A i.171; D i.214 (+vi- takketha); Pot. °kareyyātha D i.90 (tam attham sādhu kam k.); ppr. °karonto DhsA 207; ger. °katvā A ii.116 (aṭṭhikatvā+... ohitasoto suṇāti); Pv iii.25 (a°=anāvajjetvā PvA 181); VvA 87, 92; PvA 62; grd.°kātabba Vism 244, 278; DhsA 205; aor. manas-ākāsi M ii.61; 2nd pl. (Prohib.) (mā) manasākattha D i.214; A i.171. Pass. manasi - kariyati Vism 284. - 2. (n.) manasikāra attention, pondering, fixed thought (cp. Cpd. 12, 28, 40, 282) D iii.104, 108 sq., 112, 227 (yoniso), 273 (ayoniso); M i.296; S ii.3 (cetanā phasso m.); iv.297 (sabba - nimittānam a° inattention to all outward signs of allurements); Nd1 501 (ayoniso); Vbh 320, 325, 373 (yoniso), 425; Vism 241 (paṭikkūla°); VbhA 148 (ayoniso), 248 sq. (as regards the 32 ākāras), 251 (paṭikkūla°), 255 (n'ātisīghato etc.), 270 (ayoniso), 500; DhA ii.87 (paṭikkūla°); DhsA 133. - sammā manasikāram anvāya by careful pondering D i.13, 18. As adj. (thoughtful) at ThA 273. - The defn of m. at Vism 466 runs as follows: "kiriya - kāro, manamhi kāro m. purima - man- ato visadisam manam karoti ti pi m. Svāyam: ārammaṇa - paṭipādako vīthi - paṭipādako javana - p.° ti ti - ppakāro." - Cpds.: - kusalatā proficiency in attention D iii.211; - kosalla id. VbhA 56 (in detail), 224, 226 sq.; Vism 241 (ten- fold), 243 (id., viz. anupubbato, nātisīghato, nātisāṇikato etc.); PvA 63 (yoniso°); - vidhāna arrangement of attention VbhA 69, 71; - vidhi rule or form of attention Vism 278 (eightfold, viz. gaṇanā, anubandhanā, phusanā, ṭhapanā, sallakhaṇā, vi- vaṭṭanā, pārisuddhi, tesaṇ ca paṭipassanā ti). - The composition form of manas is mano°, except before vowels, when man' takes its place (as man - āyatana VbhA 46 sq.). **-dhātu element of apprehension, the ideational faculty** (cp. Dhs. trsl. 129, 2p. 119, 120; and p. 2lxxxv sq.) Dhs 457 sq.; Vbh 14, 71, 87 sq., 144, 302; Vism 488; VbhA 80, 81, 239 (physio- logical foundation), 405; DhsA 263, 425; KhA 53. **-viññāṇa** representative cognition, rationality Vism 489; VbhA 150 (22 fold); DhsA 304, cp. Dhs. trsl. 170 (2p. 157); - dhātu (element of) representative intellection, mind cognition, the 6th of the viññāṇadhātus or series of cognitional elements corresponding to and based on the 12 simple dhātus, which are the **external & internal** sense - relations (=āyatanāni) Dhs 58; Vbh 14, 71, 87, 89, 144, 176 and passim. See also above II. 3 and discussions at Dhs. trsl. 132 (2p. 122) & introd. p. 53 sq.; Cpd. 1232, 184.

- * **Vāta** [Vedic vāta, of vā; cp. Sk. vāti & vāyati to blow, vāyu wind; Lat. ventus, Goth. winds=wind; Ohg. wājan to blow, Oir. feth air; Gr. α ῑ μ ι to blow, ῑ α ῑ τ η ζ wind, Lith. áudra storm etc.] wind. There exists a common distinction of winds into 2 groups: **"internal" and "external" winds**, or the ajjhakkā vāyo - dhātu (wind category), and the bāhirā. They are discussed at Vbh 84, quoted at MA 30, 31, and expld in detail at VbhA 70 sq.; Vism 350. The bāhirā also at Nd2 562, and in poetical form at S iv.218. - The internal winds (see below 2) comprise the foll.: uddhangamā vātā, adhogamā, kucchisayā, koṭṭhāsasayā, angam - ang' - ānusārino, satthakā, khurakā, uppalakā, assāso, passāso, i. e. all kinds of winds (air) or drawing pains (rheumatic?) in the body, from hiccup, stitch and stomach - ache up to breathing. Their complement are the external winds (see below 1), viz. puratthimā vātā, pacchimā, uttarā, dakkhiṇā (from the 4 quarters of the sky), sarajā arajā, sītā uṇhā, parittā adhimattā, kāḷā, verambha°, pakkha°, supañña°, tālavanta°, vidhūpana. ° These are characterized according to direction, dust, temperature, force, height & other causes (like fanning etc.). - 1. wind (of the air) S iv.218 (vātā ākāse vāyanti); Sn 71, 348, 591 (vāto tūlaṃ va dhamsaye), 622, 1074; J i.72; Pug 32; Vism 31. adhimatta v. S iv.56; mahā° S ii.88; A i.136, 205; ii.199; iv.312; veramba° (winds blowing in high regions: upari ākāse S ii.231) A i.137; Th 1, 598; J vi.326. - 2. "winds" of the body, i. e. pains caused by (bad) circulation, sometimes simply (uncontrolled) movements in the body, sometimes rheumatic pains, or sharp & dragging pains in var. parts of the body Nett. 74. Also applied to certain humours, supposed to be caused by derangements of the "winds" of the body (cp. Gr. χ υ μ ό ζ; or E. slang "get the wind up"), whereas normal "winds" condition normal health: Pv ii.61 (tassa vātā bālīyanti: bad winds become strong, i. e. he is losing his senses, cp. PvA 94: ummāda - vātā). - anga° pain in the limbs (or joints), rheumatism Vin i.205; udara° belly ache J i.393, 433; DhA iv.129; kammaja° birth - pains Vism 500; kucchi° pains in the abdomen (stomach) VbhA 5; piṭṭhi° pains in the back ibid. - 3. (fig.) atmosphere, condition, state; or as pp. (of vāyati) scented (with), full of, pervaded (by), at Vin i.39 (vijana° pervaded by loneliness, having an atmosphere of loneliness; Kern. Toev. s. v. vāta wrongly "troop, crowd." The same passage occurs at D iii.38, where Rh. D., Dial. iii.35, trsls "where the breezes from the pastures blow"; with expln vijana=vrjana [see vajati], hardly justified. In same connection at A iv.88); Miln 19 (isi° - parivāta scented with an atmosphere of Sages; Rh. D. differently: "bringing down the breezes from the heights where the Sages dwell"; forced). - On vāta in similes see J.P.T.S. 1907, 135. **-ābādha "wind disease," internal pains (not rheumatism)** Vin i.205; Miln 134; Vism 41.
- * **Vātika** (adj.) [fr. vāta 2, cp. *Sk. vātakin Halāyudha ii.451] connected with the winds (humours) of the body, having bad circulation, suffering from internal trouble, rheumatic (?) Miln 135, 298.

Again, as per the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by **Davids and Stede (1921-1925)** OR the online Pali dictionary @ Univ. of Chicago, the following are the words in Pali for **external** -

- * **Bāhira** (adj.) [fr. bahi, as Sk. bāhya fr. bahis, cp. also bāhiya] 1. **external**, outside (opp. abbhantara inside), outer, foreign D ii.75; A iv.16; Dh 394 (fig. in meaning of 2); J i.125 (antara° inside & outside); 337 (out of office, out of favour, of ministers);

vi.384 (bāhiraṃ karoti to turn out, turn inside out); Pv iv.11 (nagarassa b.); Miln 281 (°abbhantara dhana); VvA 68 (°kittibhāva fact of becoming known outside). - santara° (adj.) [=sa - antara] including the inward & outward parts D i.74; A iii.25; Th 1, 172; J i.125. - 2. external to the individual, objective (opp. ajjhattika subjective) M iii.274 (cha āyatanā); J iv.402 (°vatthum ayācitvā ajjhattikassa nāmaṃ gaṇhāti); Dhs 674 (cp. trsl. p. 207); Vbh 13; Miln 215; Vism 450. - 3. heretical, outsider in religious sense, non - Buddhist, freq. applied to the Brahmanic religion & their practice (samaya) Kvu 251 (+puthujjana - pakkhe ṭhita); DhA iii.378 (=mana, i. e. Bhagavato sāsanaṭo bahiddhā). - Cases as adv. bāhirato from outside, from a foreign country J i.121; bāhire outside (the Buddhist order) Dh 254.

- * **Bāhiratta** (nt.) [abstr. fr. bāhira] being outside (of the individual), **externality** Vism 450.
- * **Bāhirima** (adj.) [fr. bāhira, compar. - adversative formation] outer, **external**, outside Vin iii.149 (b. māna **external** measure; opp. abbhantarima); J v.38 (opp. abbhantarima).

10.3 Experience # 3

There is a pond, where i was sitting next to . . . under a tree in the evening time, with the sun setting and sky crystal clear. Eyes closed and MEDITATION happened . . . AS IF my WIFE . . . Silence . . . enveloped me COMPLETELY in the STILLNESS of AWARENESS . . . Don't know how much time has passed, HOWEVER, when the eyes opened the same above experience, as mentioned in Experience # 2 happened! LOVE in its PURITY in STILLNESS of AWARENESS was REFLECTED in heart . . . in the WATER, in the STONES, in the TREES, in the SKY . . . ALL PERMEATING with LIFE and LIFE itself IS LOVE! One DOES NOT HAVE to DO ANYTHING! Just SIT STILL and BE . . . as REFINEMENT will happen, Beloved Mother NATURE will show LOVE that LIFE IS . . . NOTHING to do! . . . In STILLNESS . . . PURE LOVE will be EXPERIENCED! The heart was ENGLUFED with PURE LOVE . . . with NO-ONE in the VICINITY and MIND was ERASED for a few moments!

11 An ANECDOTE :: of the Buddha

11.1 Paraphrased, with limited grasping that i have . . .

Many passed by and saw Siddhartha, who was now the Buddha! They came to him and enquired about him . . .

- * Φ "Are you a god?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * Φ "Are you god's reincarnation?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * Φ "Are you a celestial being?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * Φ "Are you a wizard?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * Φ "Are you a saint?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * Φ "Are you a sage?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * IRRITATED . . . Φ "Are you a man or not?"
- * the Buddha Φ No!
- * in ANGER . . . Φ "THEN what are you?"
- * the Buddha Φ i am AWARENESS!

Siddhartha had FINALLY REALIZED or AWAKENED who he was . . . and his TRUE NATURE. The CULMINATION of the journey from Hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha to Buddha . . . the FULLY BLOSSMED one . . . "i am awareness!" . . . LIFE's property is AWARENESS! and IN that STILLNESS of AWARENESS . . . he knew he was LIFE ITSELF EXPRESSED in FULL MAGNANIMITY of IMMACULATE PERFECTION . . . HAMMERED through birth, after birth, after birth . . . for UNCOUNTABLE AEONS, BEFORE the FINAL life, in which he RENOUNCED everything and MERGED back into the ABSOLUTE TRUTH, ERAZING all limited IDENTIFICATIONS in EXISTENCE, in Beloved Mother Nature in PARINIRVANA!

Further, Φ when does realization or awakening happen? and Φ where does this realization and awakening happen ?

That when is when the being has meditated over life times . . . and purified and worked through in existence . . . and where does this realization / awakening happen . . . In AWARENESS! LIFE has AWARENESS and that AWARENESS is SO IMMACULATE and REFINED that ONE moment in SPACE and TIME . . . that FULL BLOSSOMING happens in existence! Long, long journey . . . into the realms of the Absolute truth . . .!

11.2 The original, as it is, in the Doṇa-sutta, of Cakkavagga, of Aṅguttara Nikāya

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zero/1.0/), available at <https://suttacentral.net/?lang=en>, which i have taken from the representations in <https://theravadan.org/> by Ben Lawrence from which the translations are taken -

Ekam samayaṃ bhagavā antarā ca ukkaṭṭhaṃ antarā ca setavyaṃ addhānamaggappaṭipanno hoti.

At one time the Buddha was traveling along the road between Ukkaṭṭhā and Setavyā,

Doṇopi sudamā brāhmaṇo antarā ca ukkaṭṭhaṃ antarā ca setavyaṃ addhānamaggappaṭipanno hoti.

as was the brahmin Doṇa.

Addasā kho doṇo brāhmaṇo bhagavato pādesu cakkāni sahasārāni sanemikāni sanābhikāni sabbākāraparipūrāni;

Doṇa saw that the Buddha's footprints had thousand-spoked wheels, with rims and hubs, complete in every detail.

disvānassa etadahosi:

It occurred to him,

“acchariyaṃ vata bho, abbhutaṃ vata bho.

“Oh lord, how incredible, how amazing!

Na vatimāni manussabhūtaṃ padāni bhavissanti”ti.

Surely these couldn't be the footprints of a human being?”

Atha kho bhagavā maggā okkamma aññatarasmim rukkhamūle nisīdi pallaṅkam ābhujitvā ujum kāyaṃ paṇidhāya parimukhaṃ satim upaṭṭhapetvā.

The Buddha had left the road and sat at the root of a tree cross-legged, setting his body straight, and establishing mindfulness in his presence.

Atha kho doṇo brāhmaṇo bhagavato padāni anugacchanto addasa bhagavantaṃ aññatarasmim rukkhamūle nisinnaṃ pāsādikam pāsādanīyaṃ santindriyaṃ santamaṇasaṃ uttamadamathasamathamappattaṃ dantaṃ guttaṃ samyatindriyaṃ nāgam.

Then Doṇa, following the Buddha's footprints, saw him sitting at the tree root - impressive and inspiring, with peaceful faculties and heart, attained to the highest self-control and serenity, like an elephant with tamed, guarded, and controlled faculties.

Disvāna yena bhagavā tenupasaṅkami; upasaṅkamitvā bhagavantam etadvoca:

He went up to the Buddha and said to him:

“Devo no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi”ti?

“Sir, might you be a god?”

“Na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, devo bhavissāmi”ti.

“I will not be a god, brahmin.”

“Gandhabbo no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi”ti?

“Might you be a centaur?”

“Na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, gandhabbo bhavissāmi”ti.

“I will not be a centaur.”

“Yakkho no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi”ti?

“Might you be a spirit?”

“Na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, yakkho bhavissāmi”ti.

“I will not be a spirit.”

“Manusso no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi”ti?

“Might you be a human?”

“Na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, manusso bhavissāmi”ti.

“I will not be a human.”

“Devo no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi”ti, iti puṭṭho samāno:

“When asked whether you might be a god, centaur, spirit, or human :

’na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, devo bhavissāmi’ti vadesi.

you answer that you will not be any of these.

’Gandhabbo no bhavaṃ bhavissāmi’ti, iti puṭṭho samāno:

“When asked whether you might be a signer / musician :

'na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, gandhabbo bhavissāmi'ti vadesi.

you answer that you will not be any of these.

'Yakkho no bhavaṃ bhavissati'ti, iti puṭṭho samāno:

“When asked whether you might be a spirit or ogre or dryad or ghost or spook :

'na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, yakkho bhavissāmi'ti vadesi.

you answer that you will not be any of these.

'Manusso no bhavaṃ bhavissati'ti, iti puṭṭho samāno:

“When asked whether you might be a human :

'na kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, manusso bhavissāmi'ti vadesi.

you answer that you will not be any of these.

Atha ko carahi bhavaṃ bhavissati'ti?

So what then might you be?”

'Yesaṃ kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, āsavānaṃ appahīnattā devo bhaveyyaṃ, te me āsavā pahīnā ucchinnamūlā tālāvattukatā anabhāvaṅkatā āyatim anuppādadhammā.

“Brahmin, if I had not given up defilements I might have become a god . . . a centaur . . . a spirit . . . or a human. But I have given up those defilements, cut them off at the root, made them like a palm stump, obliterated them so they are unable to arise in the future.

Yesaṃ kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, āsavānaṃ appahīnattā gandhabbo bhaveyyaṃ . . . yakkho bhaveyyaṃ . . . manusso bhaveyyaṃ, te me āsavā pahīnā ucchinnamūlā tālāvattukatā anabhāvaṅkatā āyatim anuppādadhammā.

“Brahmin, if I had not given up defilements I might have become a singer / musician . . . spirit or ogre or dryad or ghost or spook . . . or a human. But I have given up those defilements, cut them off at the root, made them like a palm stump, obliterated them so they are unable to arise in the future.

Seyyathāpi, brāhmaṇa, uppalaṃ vā padumaṃ vā puṇḍarīkaṃ vā udake jātaṃ udake

saṃvaḍḍham udakā accuggamma tiṭṭhati anupalittam udakena;

Suppose there was a blue water lily, or a pink or white lotus. Though it sprouted and grew in the water, it would rise up above the water and stand with no water clinging to it.

evamevaṃ kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, loke jāto loke saṃvaḍḍho lokaṃ abhibhuyya viharāmi anupalitto lokena.

In the same way, though I was born and grew up in the world, I live having mastered the world, unsullied by the world.

Buddhoti maṃ, brāhmaṇa, dhārehi.

Remember me, brahmin, as a Buddha.

Yena devūpapatyassa,

I could have been reborn as a god,

gandhabbo vā vihaṅgamo;

or as a centaur flying through the sky.

Yakkhattaṃ yena gaccheyyaṃ,

I could have become a spirit,

manussattañca abbaje;

or returned as a human.

Te mayhaṃ āsavā khiṇā,

But I've ended those defilements,

viddhastā vinaḷīkatā.

they're blown away and mown down.

Puṇḍarīkaṃ yathā vaggu,

Like a graceful lotus,

Toyena nupalippati;

to which water does not cling,

Nupalippāmi lokena,

the world doesn't cling to me,

Tasmā buddhosmi brāhmaṇā”ti.

and so, brahmin, I am a Buddha.”

12 The long preparation before experience :: Āṇāpāna & Vipassanā / vipasāyanā process

Āṇāpāna or the observation of the flow of the natural breath, is a fundamental step, before entering the field of Vipassanā, as the Buddha imparted. These methods have existed and with stood the test of time for past 2600 years, since the passing of the Buddha. In this article, i document steps to practice the Anapana and Vipassana meditations, which i had the opportunity to practice and observe in my own mind-body complex. As the meditations continued, i was able to grasp of the few issues and have it up in the form of steps. Explanations of these steps are separately mentioned on my webpages @ [Link to Anapana process](#) and [Link to Vipassana process](#), respectively. However, here i have consolidated the contents of the two webpages and have also added slightly additional information, necessary to go through the details. In my limited grasp, i think these might be helpful for those who wish to practice at home, also. IT HAS BEEN HEARD : In the Dhajagga Paritta Chant from [Thanissaro \(2016\)](#) (under [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0](#)) the following is quoted - **Pali** : *Svakkhato bhagavata dhammo, Sanditthiko akaliko chipasiko, Opanayiko paccattam veditabbo vinnuhiti* (**English** : The Dhamma is well-expounded by the Blessed One, to be seen here and now, timeless, inviting all to come and see, pertinent, to be seen by the observant for themselves).

12.1 Anapana process

HUMAN BODY NOT HINDU, MUSLIM, CHRISTIAN, BUDDHIST, SIKH, PARSI, TAO, ETC ... NO? UNFORTUNATELY, THE BUDDHA TAUGHT THE PROCESS OF ANAPANA OR OBSERVATION OF THE NATURAL BREATH AS IT IS OR YATHA-BHUTA!

12.1.1 The Buddha before awakening, on anapana

I produce here, the translations of Bhante Sujato from Pali under the Creative Commons Zero from [Link to CC0 1.0 Universal](#), available at <https://suttacentral.net/?lang=en>; They have been represented in <https://theravadan.org/> from which the translations are taken) - On the topic of *anapana*, the Buddha expresses his views as follows, in the Samyutta Nikaya 54.8, Padipopamasutta (The Simile of the Lamp) -

- * **Pali** : "Anapanassatisamadhi, bhikkhave, bhavito bahulikato mahapphalo hoti mahanisamso. **English** : "Mendicants, when immersion due to mindfulness of breathing is developed and cultivated it's very fruitful and beneficial.
- * **Pali** : Ahampi sudam, bhikkhave, pubbeva sambodha anabhisambuddho bodhisattova samano imina viharena bahulam viharami. **English** : Before my awakening-when I was still unawakened but intent on awakening-I too usually practiced this kind of meditation.
- * **Pali** : Tassa mayham, bhikkhave, imina viharena bahulam viharato neva kayo kilamati na cakkhuni; **English** : And while I was usually practicing this kind of meditation neither my body nor my eyes became fatigued.
- * **Pali** : anupadaya ca me asavehi cittam vimucci. **English** : And my mind was freed from defilements by not grasping.

Further, **in support of the practice of *anapana***, the Buddha states the following in Majjhima Nikaya 118, Anapanassatisutta (Mindfulness of Breathing) -

- * **Pali** : *Anapanassati, bhikkhave, bhavita bahulikata cattaro satipatthane paripureti.*
English : Mindfulness of breathing, when developed and cultivated, fulfills the four kinds of mindfulness meditation.
- * **Pali** : *Cattaro satipatthana bhavita bahulikata satta bojjhange paripurenti.* **English** : The four kinds of mindfulness meditation, when developed and cultivated, fulfill the seven awakening factors.
- * **Pali** : *Satta bojjhanga bhavita bahulikata vijjavimuttim paripurenti.* **English** : And the seven awakening factors, when developed and cultivated, fulfill knowledge and freedom.

Regarding the **four kinds of meditation**, the Buddha expounds the same in Samyutta Nikaya 47.1, Ambapalisutta (In Ambapali's Mango Grove) -

- * **Pali** : *"Ekayanvayam, bhikkhave, maggo sattanam visuddhiya sokaparidevanam samatikkamaya dukkhadomanassanam atthangamaya nayassa adhigamaya nibbanassa sacchikiriyaya, yadidam-cattaro satipatthana.* **English** : "Mendicants, the four kinds of mindfulness meditation are the path to convergence. They are in order to purify sentient beings, to get past sorrow and crying, to make an end of pain and sadness, to discover the system, and to realize extinguishment.
- * **Pali** : *Katame cattaro?* **English** : What four?
- * **Pali** : *Idha, bhikkhave, bhikkhu kaye kayanupassi viharati atapi sampajano satima, vineyya loke abhijhadomanassam;* **English** : It's when a mendicant meditates by observing an aspect of the body-keen, aware, and mindful, rid of covetousness and displeasure for the world.
- * **Pali** : *vedanasu vedananupassi viharati atapi sampajano satima, vineyya loke abhijhadomanassam;* **English** : They meditate observing an aspect of feelings-keen, aware, and mindful, rid of covetousness and displeasure for the world.
- * **Pali** : *citte cittanupassi viharati atapi sampajano satima, vineyya loke abhijhadomanassam;* **English** : They meditate observing an aspect of the mind-keen, aware, and mindful, rid of covetousness and displeasure for the world.
- * **Pali** : *dhammesu dhammanupassi viharati atapi sampajano satima, vineyya loke abhijhadomanassam.* **English** : They meditate observing an aspect of principles-keen, aware, and mindful, rid of covetousness and displeasure for the world.
- * **Pali** : *Ekayanvayam, bhikkhave, maggo sattanam visuddhiya sokaparidevanam samatikkamaya dukkhadomanassanam atthangamaya nayassa adhigamaya nibbanassa sacchikiriyaya, yadidam-cattaro satipatthana"ti.* **English** : The four kinds of mindfulness meditation are the path to convergence. They are in order to purify sentient beings, to get past sorrow and crying, to make an end of pain and sadness, to discover the system, and to realize extinguishment."

Finally, regarding the **seven factors of awakening**, in Digha Nikaya 33, Sangitisutta (Reciting in Concert), the Buddha talks about the *Satta bojjhanga* (Seven awakening factors) -

- * **Pali** : *satisambojjhango, dhammavicayasambojjhango, viriyasambojjhango, pitisambojjhango, passaddhisambojjhango, samadhisambojjhango, upekkhasambojjhango.*

English : mindfulness, investigation of principles, energy, rapture, tranquility, immersion, and equanimity.

Figure 63: Pictorial representation of Anapana process

Figure 63, shows pictorial representation of Anapana. For background detail and advanced level, on the Anapana process, please read through the article titled **Anapana (observing the flow of natural breath) & establishing in the present moment @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/v562c>**. The following are the steps in detail for the Anapana process. **Steps to Anapana for daily practice (follow this in serial order). This is fundamental. Please stick to this! -**

- * **1** - Don't put effort to put attention on the breath in the beginning.
- * **2** - Sit and be still & let the stillness of awareness take over you.
- * **3** - In the stillness of awareness, after a few moments, the flow of the breath appears. The breath comes in and then it goes out.
- * **4** - Do not force to take the next breath or be in a hurry for the next breath.
- * **5** - Let the body take the next breath. You just be still and wait for the body to take the next breath.
- * **6** - Thus sitting till, let the nature of breath unfold in awareness, as it is (i.e yathabhuta). However, whether breath is going in, coming out or there is a period of no breath, keep attention at one point within the nostrils.
- * **6.a Advanced** - At the junction of the eye brows, where the nose starts, keeping the eyes closed with body absolutely still and attention on a fixed point within the nasal area at the junction, the flow of the breath comes to awareness. Important aspect is that there is no force or control on the breath irrespective of its flow.
- * **Step 6.b Advanced** - As the observation of the flow of breath at this point becomes sharper and intense, it leads to dissolution of mind. Constant observation leads to a stage of absorption or in Hindi what they call as kumbhaka in which the individual mind merges with the flow of the natural air around the point of observation and loses its individual identity.

- * **Step 6.c Advanced** - Depending on the impressions of the individual mind this state of kumbhaka or absorption can happen for long duration also. It is as if the individuality has been erased from existence.
- * **Step 6.d Advanced** - Also, as one becomes adept in the practice of anapana one starts observing the rise of breath and the subsiding of the breath and thus the impermanence of each breath.
- * **Step 6.e Advanced** - Between two breaths, there is a deep state of peace. But this again comes to observation with natural practice.
- * **Step 7** - Comfort/discomfort, in mind, body, heart, let it be, as it is (yatha-bhuta).
- * **Step 8** - Continue this for one hour daily.
- * **Step 9** - If needed and free, increase the duration of practice.
- * **Step 10** - Finally, one breath at a time.
- * **Step 11** - Sometimes only, just mentally ask yourself - "Am i able to feel/observe the pace of the ingoing/outgoing breath?"

Further, read the article on **Grasping the principles of anicca (impermanence), dukkha (sorrow/misery), anatta (non-self), suññata (emptiness) & tathagata (the one who has gone by as it is or yathabhuta) via anapana** @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/x7djz>.

12.1.2 Even the **breath is impermanent (annica)** . . .

As one observes the natural flow of breath (i.e anapana), one grasps the phenomena of impermanence as the breath rises, reaches a peak and then falls off. As one practices regularly and consistently, it comes to one's awareness that the breath becomes slow and subtle and eventually sometimes stops. This is a state of suspension and impressions in the mind literally are not there or are negligible. The mind becomes calm and purified. At a later stage, even the mind dissolves. Thus the principle of impermanence (annica) is grasped. Dukkha (sorrow/suffering) is considering the impermanent as permanent and holding on to it. And all this arises from ego or self identity. Slowly the ego also dissolves . . .

It takes time to reach the above state and requires sustained, long practice of observing the flow of breath.

12.1.3 **Convergence of the mind to the pace of the breath**

Speed creates delusion! Usually, the mind, in normal day to day activity, is running. The speed of the mind doesn't even match the speed of the breath. Since there is a mismatch between the two, all sorts of disturbances is observed in behaviour in thoughts, words and action. It has been observed that when the pace of the mind and pace of the breath, remains synchronized, there is calmness in the mind-body complex. With the practice of anapana, as the running mind converges to the pace of the breath, there is a gradual slow down of the mind and it starts to come into the present moment. In that present moment, there is the dissolution of the past and the future. Further, there comes a stage when the speed of the mind converges with the speed of the breath. Over a long period of convergence, there will be times when the mind dissolves into emptiness. The configuration

of the cosmos, at that present moment, to whatever degree, one gets a glimpse off. That interconnectedness is reflected in awareness . . .

12.1.4 Anapana (observing the natural breath as it is), calms, concentrates, purifies and . . .

cools the mind. Deep impressions in the mind of many life times get eradicated as one practices anapana properly. The body also heals slowly and steadily with continuous practice of anapana. Mental afflictions and diseases also get eradicated. What happens is, as one keeps observing the natural flow of the breath (i.e no control over the breath), the speed/pace of the minds starts converging to the speed/pace of the breath. As the practice of this observation deepens, the mind becomes crystal clear like the still water were the mud has settled down. There will be times, when the mind will dissolve.

HASTEN SLOWLY AND YE SHALL SOON ARRIVE. - Jetsun Milarepa I produce here, the translations of Bhante Sujato from Pali under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0 1.0 Universal) from (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>), available at <https://suttacentral.net/?lang=en>; They have been represented in <https://theravadan.org/> from which the translations are taken) - In Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu, Poṭṭhilattheravatthu it is recorded

- * **Pali** : *Yogā ve jāyatī bhūri.*,. **English** : From meditation springs wisdom,
- * **Pali** : *ayogā bhūrisāṅkhayo;*. **English** : without meditation, wisdom ends.
- * **Pali** : *Etam dvedhāpatham nātvā.*,. **English** : Knowing these two paths -
- * **Pali** : *bhavāya vibhavāya ca;*. **English** : of progress and decline -
- * **Pali** : *Tathāttānam niveseyya.*,. **English** : you should conduct yourself
- * **Pali** : *yathā bhūri pavaddhati.* **English** : so that wisdom grows.

In, Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinguishment, it is recorded -

- * **Pali** : *Yo imasmim dhammavinaye.*,. **English** : Whoever meditates diligently,
- * **Pali** : *appamatto vihassati;*. **English** : in this teaching and training,
- * **Pali** : *Pahāya jātisaṃsāram.*,. **English** : giving up transmigration through rebirths,
- * **Pali** : *dukkhassantaṃ karissatī*”ti.. **English** : will make an end to suffering.”
- * **Pali** : ‘*ye te, bhante, ahesuṃ atītamaddhānam arahanto sammāsambuddhā, sabbe te bhagavanto pañca nīvaraṇe pahāya cetaso upakkilese paññāya dubbalīkaṇaṇe catūsu satipaṭṭhānesu supatiṭṭhitacittā sattabojjhaṅge yathābhūtaṃ bhāvetvā anuttarāṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambujjhimsu.* **English** : ‘All the perfected ones, fully awakened Buddhas - whether past, future, or present - give up the five hindrances, corruptions of the heart that weaken wisdom. Their mind is firmly established in the four kinds of mindfulness meditation. They correctly develop the seven awakening factors. And they wake up to the supreme perfect awakening.’

12.2 Vipassana process

HUMAN BODY NOT HINDU, MUSLIM, CHRISTIAN, BUDDHIST, SIKH, PARSİ, TAO, ETC . . . NO? UNFORTUNATELY, THE BUDDHA TAUGHT THE PROCESS OF VIPASSANA

Figure 64: Pictorial representation of Vipassana process. It has deeper meaning, when taken in the context of the explanation given below.

OR WATCHING AS IT IS OR YATHA-BHUTA! Figure 64, shows pictorial representation of Vipassana.

12.2.1 Anupaschyana and the way to do it

-

Anupaschyana means **watch, observation**. But who is observing? It is not the me, the ego that observes. It is the awareness in which the phenomena comes into light. How? As the lotus flower rests gently on the surface of a pond, so also the human body should sit still. What happens when one does this? The lotus rests gently and is still, however, the happenings like the flow of nutrition, flow of water etc occur naturally and spontaneously. Similarly, as the human body sits still, gradually and naturally, the body (**kaya**), the sensations (**vedana**) in the body, the flow of mind (**citta**) and the continuous germination, rise, reaching a peak, fall and dissolution of any phenomena (**dhamma**), comes to awareness. As one sits still, gradually, it comes to one's awareness that the life within, is separate from this samsara, nature and one's own mind, body, ego and intellect. That life is untouched and unblemished.

Technical details -

- * First, **let the essence of the meaning behind the words** (say kayanupaschyana), settle or get absorbed in the being. It is like you put a candy in the mouth and without chewing the flavour of the candy starts spreading in the whole taste buds naturally and spontaneously. So just say kayanupaschyana, to yourself and let the essence of the word spread through the being that is you.
- * Next, **when one says** kayanupaschyana, automatically the body come to awareness. **The grip of the body on the life** within you comes to awareness.
- * **There are two, (say) kaya and the grip of (say) kaya**. Kaya will come to awareness and then if you keep the watch and remember that the grip of kaya is holding on to the life within, automatically, the grip loosens its affect!

- * **Slowly and steadily** the body and its intricacies start coming to awareness.
- * **Since the entire body is connected, slowly and steadily the entire interconnected nature of the body itself comes to awareness. However, this is a long process.** Don't expect the experience of the entire body coming to awareness in one moment or shot.
- * **As the practice of watching continues persistently and patiently,** the kaya or whole body will come to awareness.
- * **Initially it will be very uncomfortable to watch and one won't be able to sit still** ... but do not be discouraged. This is because one's mind is not acclimated to watching the body. It is a natural process and you need to give time to yourself.
- * Sit everyday one hour and watch.
- * Again, **as the lotus flower sits gently on the surface of a pond and the happenings of the flow of nutrients and the gentleness of the petals occur naturally,** so also human body must sit still and in the stillness of awareness, let the body reveal itself in awareness.
- * **There is no effort. It is effortless as one sits still** and kayanupaschyana happens . . .
- * **Kaya or body is like a river.** The cells are germinating, sustaining and dying while moving in the river as waves. Thus one has to **watch the river called body flow as one sits still . . . You will not watch! The awareness that is there in the life within you will watch.**
- * **Don't hold the flowing river, as you sit still! Watch the flow, fast, slow, crashing, drifting etc . . .** You sit beside the river and watch the flow of the river . . .
- * **The same with vedananupaschyana and chittanupaschyana ...**

Practice the below in serial order, daily. (Breaks are ok!)

12.2.2 Stages of Vipassana for daily practice (This is long time taking process)

kayanupaschyana In the **first one hour of watch** (anupaschyana), **sit and listen** to what the body (**kaya**) says to one's awareness. **Sit still and let the processes of the body come to awareness (that is what it meant by listening here and not any sound).** They are happening without one's knowledge, however, during the first watch in stillness of awareness, let the body reveal itself to one's awareness. It is going to be uncomfortable, but endure and watch. After an hour of watch with **adhitthana** (self determination), break the posture and relax for a few minutes.

Finer technical details - When i say watch the body or listen to the body, there are steps in it.

- * As stated above, sit still. In the stillness of awareness, let the following happen . . .
- * **DO NOT** apply force to watch or listen to the body. Just as the lotus flower rests gently on the surface of the pond, so also, let the body sit still.
- * Discomfort is arising, heaviness of the body, stiffness in the body, stress in the body, lightness in the body, anything - **JUST ACKNOWLEDGE** the state of the body **AS IT IS (yatha bhuta)** . **NEITHER** there is acceptance of the state of the body **NOR** there is rejection of the state of the body. Let the **RIVER CALLED BODY FLOW**

as mother nature wants it to flow. **Just watch the flow and DO NOT CONTROL** the flow.

- * This flow is called as **Diurnal rhythms** (or biological process/rhythm or daily pattern of activity, physiology, and behavior that follows a roughly 24-hour cycle, often synchronized with the day-night cycle) and more specifically **Circadian rhythms** (the specific kind of diurnal rhythm which can persist even without external cues). In **CHAPTER 1 - Neuroendocrinology of Reproduction**, by Donald K. Clifton, Robert A. Steiner, of Yen & Jaffe's Reproductive Endocrinology (Sixth Edition) (Editors - Jerome F. Strauss and Robert L. Barbieri, ISBN - 978-1-4160-4907-4, URL - <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9781416049074000012>), it states that - **to be classified as circadian**, a diurnal rhythm must be synchronized to environmental cues, but not driven by them. This means that the rhythm should persist for a period of approximately 24 hours in the absence of any environmental cues and should use environmental cues, when they are available, to synchronize itself to the time of day. A number of organs throughout the body display intrinsic circadian rhythmicity, but most of these are synchronized to a "master clock" that resides in the Suprachiasmatic nucleus.
- * **Also, simultaneously, the breath will also be flowing in and out.** Again, **DO NOT** control the flow of the breath. **Just watch the flow of the breath as it comes in and as it goes out.** So for example, you feel heaviness in the body and you find it difficult to breath, then **LET IT BE! JUST ACKNOWLEDGE!** In the stillness of awareness let the **CONDITIONING** of the breath and the body **AS IT IS** (yatha bhuta). Here **CONDITIONING** is called **Paccaya (conditions) in Abhidhammapitaka**. For more deeper aspects on **Paccaya**, read the article @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/fp9sy>.
- * **REMEMBER**, in the stillness of awareness, **let the attention be on the body, while the breath keeps flowing.**

For an article on Diurnal rhythms, please refer to the manuscript published in 1947 in **Cambridge University Press** in the journal of **Epidemiology & Infection**, titled - **Variation, diurnal and over longer periods of time, in blood haemoglobin, haematocrit, plasma protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, and blood chloride**; available @ [Link to article on CUP](#).

Note - This LET IT BE! JUST ACKNOWLEDGE! i.e neither acceptance, nor rejection ...

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- * **Pali** : *Phassadvayam sukhadukkhe upekkhe.* **English** : Look with equanimity at the duality of pleasant and painful contacts,
- * **Pali** : *Anānuruddho aviruddha kenaci.* **English** : without favoring or opposing anything.

vedananupaschyana Then in the **second one hour of watch** (anupaschyana), **sit and listen** to what the sensations (**vedana**) says to one's awareness. **Sit still and let the processes of the sensations come to awareness.** Again, during the second watch in stillness of awareness, let the sensations reveal itself to one's awareness. After the second hour of watch with **adhithana** (self determination), break the posture and relax for a few minutes.

chittanupaschyana Next, in the **third one hour of watch** (anupaschyana), sit and listen to what the mind (**chitta**) says to one's awareness. Sit still and let the processes of the mind come to awareness. Again, during the third watch in stillness of awareness, let the mind reveal itself to one's awareness. After the third hour of watch with adhithana (self determination), break the posture and relax for a few minutes.

Finer technical details - When i say watch the chitta or listen to the chitta, there certain tips for it.i reproduce a sections (from the below article) titled -

- * **The way out** . . . The first step is to acknowledge from one's own heart, the state of the mind, irrespective of whatever the quality, modification, impression or pattern of the mind. Such and such is the state of the mind! Do not fight the mind. The greater the fight, the deeper the trouble. It is not possible to change the pattern, impressions or modifications of mind so easily. It is like a wild elephant. But there is a way out. Once the acknowledgement has happened, the acceptance of the state of the mind has happened, the mind beings to calm down and the same mind comes back to the natural flow of the breath. It converges to the pace of the breath, instead of running amuck. As the observation of the natural flow of the breath (i.e. anapana) increases in duration, day after day, first, the mind calms, cools down and gets purified. How does it get purified? As the practice of observation of the natural breath continues, the mental contents that is the patterns, impressions and the modifications of the mind start coming up to awareness. Irritation or other kinds of sensations happen in the mind-body complex, related to the surfacing of a particular pattern, impression and modification. The mind is bound to revolt. In these moments, the key is to be still, neither accepting, nor rejecting . . . In the stillness of awareness, let the phenomena in the mind evolve as it germinates, rises, reaches a peak, falls off and dissolves. Let it happen as nature takes its own course, but be still. The stillness of awareness is the key. This grip of the mind and its contents, let it arise and let it go off in its own accord. In the stillness of awareness, let the observation happen, without tampering or wanting to change the flow of mind. Whatever be the content of the mind, let it come out, whether the experience one has to go through in awareness, is pleasant, unpleasant or neutral. It is deep surgical operation that is happening. So be brave and face your own mind. Next, as one progresses on a daily basis via practice of deep meditations, there will come stages where the mind will be purified, with not patterns, impressions or modifications in it. It will be like a clean empty glass bowl. But you can't keep on holding the bowl. That is another stressful situation. One has to let go of the purified mind also. Otherwise arrogance will develop - "Oh! I have a purified mind. I am such a great being to have reached such a stage." Have a purified mind, but don't get attached to it. In the advanced stages of meditations, the purified mind dissolves after long practice. It is then, that the grip of mind is lost on the awareness

and the life and the experience or glimpses of the formless truth is experienced. But it is a long journey, spread over many lifetimes. However, in between, glimpses of absolute truth do come to experience, even for a few moments, as one continues on meditations regularly. So patience and persistence will go hand in hand. Also, when one begins of this journey, one has to initially guard the mind. Vipassana meditations are for serious practitioners only. Detailed references regarding mind can be found in the Abhidhamma Pitaka

- * **An example of the way to practice** - Suppose lust for anger arises in mind, either because of past impression of an event or because one has observed something in the present moment. Irrespective of the cause, anger has arisen in the mind. Now what to do? It has arisen. There are two things. One is, to roll in with the anger that has arisen in the mind. Get entangled with it and continue to roll it in for as long as its intensity persists. The second thing is, which is tough, is be aware that anger has arisen. Acknowledge - "Anger has arisen in mind!". Be with the intensity of anger, but don't roll with it, like rolling in mud. Just observe the grip of anger on your own mind, body, intellect, ego, and on the life within you. Be still and in the stillness of awareness, observe this grip of anger. The key is that during these moments, just BE STILL and observe. Neither reject it, nor accept it. Just a gentle awareness. See, how this grip pulls you and the life within you, in one direction or the other. This grip germinates, arises, reaches a peak, falls and dissolves. As you observe this phenomena and the grip it has on your life and awareness, it slowly and steadily leaves you. As you let go of this grip of anger, beyond the storm of anger is immense peace. As the practice of observation expands in day to day life, you will see that the fire arises, reaches a peak and then falls off. One can repeat the same procedure for the afflictions of mind that include delusion, doubts, trauma, anxiety, frustration, fear, wickedness, lust for sex, money, fame, power, progeny, etc, to name a few. The following figure 1 which might help is grasping the idea.
- * **If you steer the muddy water, it will become more muddier!** You have to let go of the stick with which you are steering the water and let the mud in the water settle down by itself. All you can do is watch patiently. The mind is like the water! See figure 65 below for getting a glimpse of the abstract idea.

For greater details read article on **The afflictions of mind and a way out** @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/>

In all the three watches, be a silent spectator, in the stillness of awareness, irrespective of the quality of experience. Repeat the 3 watches, each of one hour, daily. If it can be done in continuity, the better the depth of meditation. It is not easy, but it is not impossible also. Sustained practice over years, as one follows the schedule daily, will help in the advancement in grasping the subtler dimensions of truth. Also, such sittings will be beneficial for mind-body complex, as one starts tuning into the rhythms of nature. Purification of mind-body complex will happen daily, which is a requirement for advancement into the higher dimensions of absolute truth. Thus strict engagement in 4 hours of meditation daily, will be extremely beneficial. **This is only for serious practitioners and one has to develop one's time period of the watches, slowly. It will not happen in one day. By personal experience, one can test if such sittings are beneficial**

Figure 65: Mind stirs! If you steer the muddy water, it will become more muddier! You have to let go of the stick with which you are steering the water and let the mud in the water settle down by itself. All you can do is watch patiently.

to oneself or not. For details and advanced level, please read the article on **Vipassana** @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/s7ary>.

The way of suchness . . . Any event, just observe the corresponding sensation within the body. The sensation, **as it is (i.e yatha bhuta)**. That is vedananupaschayana. Many of the events which have impression in the mind, come up, when one observes the suchness of the sensations within the body. With practice one is able to free oneself from the deep impressions and one feels lighter. Similarly, as the body comes to awareness, one watches the nature of body **as it is**; i.e kayanupaschyana and when the flow of mind comes to awareness, one watches the mind and its flow, **as it is**; i.e chittanupaschyana. That is the way of suchness . . .

In, Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu, Aniccalakkhanavattu, -

- * **Pali** : *"Sabbe sankhārā aniccā"ti*, **English** : All conditions are impermanent,
- * **Pali** : *yadā paññāya passati*; **English** : when this is seen with Insight-wisdom (i.e vipassana panna),
- * **Pali** : *Atha nibbindati dukkhe*, **English** : one grows weary of suffering,
- * **Pali** : *esa maggo visuddhiyā*. **English** : this is the path to purity.

in, Dukkhalakkhanavattu, -

- * **Pali** : *"Sabbe sankhārā dukkhā"ti*, **English** : All conditions are suffering
- * **Pali** : *yadā paññāya passati*; **English** : when this is seen with Insight-wisdom (i.e vipassana panna),
- * **Pali** : *Atha nibbindati dukkhe*, **English** : one grows weary of suffering,
- * **Pali** : *esa maggo visuddhiyā*. **English** : this is the path to purity.

in Anattalakkhanavattu, -

- * **Pali** : *"Sabbe dhammā anattā"ti*, **English** : All things are not-self,

- * **Pali** : *yadā paññāya passati*; **English** : when this is seen with Insight-wisdom (i.e vipassana panna),
- * **Pali** : *Atha nibbindati dukkhe*, **English** : one grows weary of suffering,
- * **Pali** : *esa maggo visuddhiyā*. **English** : this is the path to purity.

In, Poṭṭhilaṭṭheravatthu -

- * **Pali** : *Yogā ve jāyati bhūri*, **English** : From meditation springs wisdom,
- * **Pali** : *ayogā bhūrisaṅkhayo*; **English** : without meditation, wisdom ends.
- * **Pali** : *Etaraṃ dvedhāpathaṃ nātvā*, **English** : Knowing these two paths -
- * **Pali** : *bhavāya vibhavāya ca*; **English** : of progress and decline -
- * **Pali** : *Tathāttānaṃ niveseyya*, **English** : you should conduct yourself
- * **Pali** : *yathā bhūri pavaḍḍhati*. **English** : so that wisdom grows.

In, Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinguishment -

- * **Pali** : *Yo imasmim dhammavinaye*, **English** : Whoever meditates diligently,
- * **Pali** : *appamatto vihassati*; **English** : in this teaching and training,
- * **Pali** : *Pahāya jātsaṃsāraṃ*, **English** : giving up transmigration through rebirths,
- * **Pali** : *dukkhassantaṃ karissati*”’ti. **English** : will make an end to suffering.”
- * **Pali** : ‘*ye te, bhante, ahesuṃ atītamaḍḍhānaṃ arahanto sammāsambuddhā, sabbe te bhagavanto pañca nīvaraṇe pahāya cetaso upakkilese paññāya dubbalīkaṇe catūsu satipaṭṭhānesu supatiṭṭhitacittā sattabojjhaṅge yathābhūtaṃ bhāvetvā anuttaraṃ sammāsambodhiṃ abhisambujjhimsu*. **English** : ‘All the perfected ones, fully awakened Buddhas - whether past, future, or present - give up the five hindrances, corruptions of the heart that weaken wisdom. Their mind is firmly established in the four kinds of mindfulness meditation. They correctly develop the seven awakening factors. And they wake up to the supreme perfect awakening.’

13 Physics of Atoms and their experiments in modern era

13.1 Atoms . . . its representations

The first 3 figures in fig. 66, 67 and 73 represent the general classification of atom, the schematic diagram of the atom as basics and Bohr's Model of atom, respectively.

Figure 66: A representation of the classification of atoms into types and their subclasses or isotopes. Source - Commons (2025a)

13.2 Ernest-Rutherford Scattering experiments

Fig. 68 represents the experiment by Geiger & Marsden, which confirmed that the Rutherford model of the atom was correct instead of the Thomson model. If the later was correct, the all the α particles would have passed through the foil with minimal scattering. On the other hand, they found that a small fraction of the α particles experienced strong deflection.

Observed in a cloud chamber, fig. 69 is a snapshot that depicts a 5.3 MeV α particle track from a ^{210}Pb source (1) undergoes Rutherford scattering (2), deflecting by an angle of about 30° . It then scatters once again (3), and finally comes to rest in the gas. The target nucleus recoils, leaving a short track (2), with all measurements in centi-meter scale.

Fig. 70, shows the schematic representation of a head-on collision between an α particle and an atom. The radius of the atom is on the order of 10^{-10}m and the minimum stopping distance is on the order of 10^{-14}m .

Figure 67: A schematic representation of Atom with its nucleus, proton, neutron and electron.
Source - Commons (2023b)

Fig. 71, shows the schematic representation of the concentration of the nucleus using the head-on collision that was used in Rutherford in Rutherford (1911). The mathematical formulation that guides this energy potential to radius of atom is depicted by Rutherford in his above paper by -

$$\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = NeE \cdot \left(\frac{1}{b} - \frac{3}{2R} + \frac{b^2}{2R^3} \right) \quad (1)$$

were, m is the mass of α particle i.e $6.64424 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} = 3.7273 \times 10^9 \text{ eV}/c^2$, v is the initial velocity i.e $2 \times 10^7 \text{ m/s}$, N is the charge of the nucleus (now the atomic number), e is the elementary charge, E is the charge of an α particle, b the turning point distance and R is the radius of the atom.

Finally, fig. 72, represents the geometry of Rutherford's scattering formula based on the a diagram in Rutherford (1911). The α particle is the green dot, which is a hyperbola with O as its centre, while S is its external focus. The atomic nucleus in red is located at S . A is the apsis, which is the point of closest approach. b is the impact parameter, the lateral distance between the α particle's initial trajectory and the nucleus.

Figure 68: A schematic representation of Geiger-Marsden experiment confirming the veracity of the Thomson and Rutherford models of atom. Source - [Commons \(2024b\)](#)

Figure 69: Observation of α particle scattering in a cloud chamber. Source - Commons (2023a)

Figure 70: Head on collision experiment of Rutherford. Source - Commons (2024d) from Rutherford (1911)

Figure 71: Concentration of nucleus represented by the Potential energy diagram for Rutherford's model for atom. Source - Commons (2026f) from Rutherford (1911)

Figure 72: The hyperbolic trajectory in the repulsive force near the center of the atom. Source - Commons (2026g) from Rutherford (1911)

13.3 Neils-Henrik-David-Bohr experiments

In fig. 73, is presented the Bohr's model of the Hydrogen atom (i.e $Z = 1$) or a Hydrogen-like ion ($Z > 1$), where the negatively charged electron to an atomic shell encircles a small, positively charged atomic nucleus and where an electron jumps between orbits, is accompanied by an emitted / absorbed amount of electromagnetic energy ($h\nu$) [Sallhofer and Lakhtakia \(1996\)](#). Orbits on which electron may travel in Grey Circle(s); Radius increases as n^2 (n being principal quantum number); Transition $3 \rightarrow 2$, produces the 1st line of the Balmer series & for Hydrogen ($Z = 1$) it results in a photon of wavelength 656 nano-meter (depicted by red light).

Figure 73: A representation of the Bohr's Model of atom Source - [Commons \(2026b\)](#)

13.4 Geiger-and-Marsden Scattering theory model

Fig. 74, was used by Geiger and Marsden in [Geiger and Marsden \(1913\)](#), to conduct a series of experiments to verify the Rutherford's equation, experimentally. The figure shows the 3D generation of the apparatus used by Geiger and Marsden to measure how the scattering pattern varied in relation to the thickness of the foil, the atomic weight of the material, and the velocity of the α particles. The rotating disc had 6 holes which be covered with foil.

Figure 74: Graphical construction of the apparatus by Geiger & Marsden. Source - [Commons \(2024a\)](#) from [Geiger and Marsden \(1913\)](#)

14 **Nidāna** :: also means references; regarding important books related to Physics!

It would be good to have a collection of the same, in case you are interested in deeper aspects of Physics! These are fundamental books that will help build the base in Physics to start with.

- ☒ [Buddhist cosmology : Philosophy & Origins](#) by [Sadakata \(1997\)](#)
- ☒ [Physics :: Part 1](#) by [Resnick and Halliday \(1960a\)](#)
- ☒ [Physics :: Part 2](#) by [Resnick and Halliday \(1960b\)](#)
- ☒ [Feynman's tips on physics : a problem-solving supplement to the Feynman lectures on physics](#) by [Feynman et al. \(2006\)](#)
- ☒ [Godel, Escher, Bach : an eternal golden braid](#) by [Hofstadter \(1999\)](#)

Figure 75: From pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment)!

15 From theory, to practice, to attainment . . . :: i.e from pariyatti, to patipatti, to pativedha!

Pariyatti or theoretical knowledge - There is a way to read the scriptures that records the teachings of the ancient ones, be it any path. First one meditates. Say you meditated for a 5 days. Then the next two days you pick up a text that you want to acquire knowledge from. After you have read a few pages, then again meditate. In the stillness of awareness and the depths of the meditation the essence of the knowledge written in words might appear in your awareness and your being might absorb that knowledge. This is a long process. **There are 3 stages of acquiring knowledge** in the higher dimensions of truth & the spiritual realm, i.e - (1) **Suta-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom acquired by listening. Listening can be through any of the senses. (2) **Cinta-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom acquired via mental chewing of the knowledge. As you chew the chewing gum, so also your mind starts chewing the knowledge, yet the knowledge/wisdom is not completely absorbed. (3) Finally, **Bhavana-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom is absorbed in your being. That knowledge settles in your heart also, firmly. **One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . .**

So you move from pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment). One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . .

Fools study voraciously to amass as much information as possible, whether it gets digested or not is not the issue, and will vomit it out in front of everyone to show something. Spiritual debates have the characteristics where one party tries to debate with the other and defeat the other party. Not that it is not useful, but whether knowledge has

settled in a being is a vastly different matter. It takes long time to grasp the truths from the abstract dimension . . .

Figure 75, depicts the process which needs to be done continuously, life, after life, after life . . .

16 **BOTTOM LINE**

the **QUALITY** of **QUESTION** you **ASK . . . TELLS VOLUMES** about your **LEVEL!**
Meditate . . . and live with a clean heart and straightened mind . . . as much as possible!
Beloved Mother Nature **will reveal to you what you NEED to know . . . IRRESPECTIVE**
of race, religion, gender, nationality, culture . . . etc

Lastly, **MODERN science and EDUCATION** might be **ADVANCED** in materialism with
a **SHORT 5 year PhD Program . . .**

HOWEVER, the ANCIENT system of study and meditation HAMMERED through WHOLE
LIFE is SOMETHING else . . . and the ANCIENT ones have HAMMERED through . .
. life, after life, after life . . .

As **RAW COAL** gets **HAMMERED** by Beloved Mother Nature in **HEAT and PRES-**
SURE, while BURRIED under the EARTH, and AGES pass before a NATURAL PER-
FECTED DIAMOND appears in EXISTENCE . . . so ALSO, you NEED to HAMMER
OUT . . . life, after life, after life . . .

17 REMEMBER

YOU alone have to walk the path and the TEACHER is there to GUIDE you! YOU EXAMINATION will be taken BY MOTHER NATURE . . . FAILURE DOES NOT MEAN EVERYTHING is LOST. . . . YOU WILL GET THE NEW LIFE to begin with AGAIN!

Tumhehi kiccaṃ ātappaṃ, akkhātāro tathagātā.

You alone . . .

have to put . . .

the ardour, zeal, exertion . . .

this . . . the one who relates, a speaker, preacher, story

was said by the one who has won through to the truth . . . or has seen / crossed over the path as-it-is . . . i.e yathā-bhūta!

Paṭipanna pamokkhanti jhāyino māra-bandhanā

(having) followed or following up, reaching, going along or by (i. e. practising), entering on, obtaining . . .

delighting / very pleased / in joy of . . .

in patience / forbearance / forgiveness . . .

i.e getting released / deliverance / discharged . . .

wins . . .

from the bonds of . . .

Mara.

as stated by the Buddha, in the *Maggavaggo* (30.276), of the *Dhammapada*, in *Khuddakanikāya* or the Minor Collection in *Suttapiṭaka*.

18 About me . . .

i CANNOT reveal the identity of beings who have told this . . . to me . . . DIRECTLY, . . . HOWEVER, IF you have GONE through this article on HERMIT Sumedha, titled - **Chapter # 2 : From hermit Sumedha to Siddhartha • The journey of a thousand li commenced with a single step : 千里之行始于足下- 老子, Lao Tzu • A journey of four incalculable aeons plus a hundred thousand aeons** @ <http://osf.io/8hn5e/files/g8bdc> . . .

i hereby state the following, on this **DAY : 2026-06-30 @ Time : 01:40:29 hrs**, that -

"i am the NEW HERMIT Sumedha, in existence, in Beloved Mother Nature!"

. . . approximately 2500 years, AFTER the passage of my BELOVED Teacher, the Shakyamuni Buddha. The REST . . . you can CONNECT the DOTS from the ABOVE article.

Further, IN CASE you GRASPED this . . . paragraph . . . from section on Loka . . . that is . . .

To reiterate, in Dhammajoti (2002)'s work on *Sarvāstivāda Abhidharma*, Bhikkhu K.L. Dhammajoti quotes *Abhidharma-mahā-vibhāṣa-sāstra* regarding *atom*, on page 260 the following -

Seven of these *paramāṇu-s* constitute an *aṇu* - the finest among all *rūpa-s* perceivable by the eye and visual consciousness. *[However,] this [aṇu] can be seen by only three types of eyes: 1. the divya-caḅṣus, 2. the eye of a Universal Monarch (cakravartin), 3. the eye of a bodhisattva in his last birth.*

and me being the NEW HERMIT Sumedha . . .

MIGHT have . . .

1. the *divya-caḅṣus*,
2. the *eye of a Universal Monarch (cakravartin)*,
3. the *eye of a bodhisattva* in his last birth.

based on the experiential knowledge of the glimpse of atom! . . .

19 It has been heard . . . :: An Anecdote

- ☒ Siddhartha, the Shakyamuni Buddha, after FULL Liberation, WAS HESITANT to teach! He remained SILENT! . . . It has been heard that the HEAVANS TREMBLED and some approached the Buddha who was sitting in SILENCE!
- ☒ They requested him to speak . . .
- ☒ The Buddha said - those who know, . . . know without my saying, . . . and those who do not know, . . . will never know, even if I speak . . . thus I am silent!
- ☒ Everyone went away as it was true!
- ☒ But then after a few days . . . they came back and said - Buddha, what you say is true ! HOWEVER, there are a few in existence, who are on the verge of liberation, of enlightenment. ON the BORDERLINE. For them you speak . . .
- ☒ the Buddha said - What you say is correct, but if i speak, the WHOLE ARMY will rise . . . WHO WILL be UP AGAINST me and i will be KILLED in NO time! AND NEITHER do i have anything to FIGHT for!
- ☒ It is said that the ENTIRE existence . . . CAME together . . . to SUPPORT the Buddha, and said - YOU SPEAK! We will make the way for you . . .
- ☒ the Buddha said - ok!
- ☒ Thus, OUT of COMPASSION for a FEW, . . . Siddhartha, the Buddha EXTENDED his LIFE . . . for the NEXT (say) 40 years and started teaching and speaking . . . THOUGH it was NOT a REQUIREMENT! His journey was OVER, 40 years BACK!
- ☒ The Buddha . . . HESITATES . . . NOT out of DOUBT or or FEAR or any NEGATIVE . . . BUT to see IF YOU ARE EVEN DESERVING or NOT !!! otherwise it is just a WASTAGE of time that cannot be returned!

Figure 76: There is a STILLNESS in the GAZE of a tiger! Source - Commons (b)

Figure 77: Waiting in HESITATION! . . . in STILLNESS . . . whether to act or not! And when the ACTION is taken . . . the intention is ALWAYS RIGHT! Source - Commons (c)

20 The Buddha HESITATES . . . :: As in STILLNESS a Tiger / Tigress HESITATES before taking action !

Here are presented a few images of tiger / tigress, who MIGHT HESITATE LONG . . . before TAKING any action. THAT hesitation is NOT out of FEAR, or DOUBT or any negative . . . With respect to the Buddha himself, he HESITATED . . .

Fig. 76 shows the STILLNESS that is there in the GAZE of a tiger and fig. 77 shows the HESITATION . . . the WAIT . . . The Buddha WAITS . . . whether to ACT or NOT! And when the ACTION is taken . . . the intention is ALWAYS RIGHT!

21 Dedication

To the universal order of the countless Buddhas
who have walked the path to fully liberated state
and rendered the greatest help
to the mankind, to over come the apparant
universal misery in life and death.

Dedicated also to the countless unacknowledged seen
and unseen forces in the Nature which shapes
one life after the other.

i bow down to all . . .
the past, the present and the future . . .

- from the NEW HERMIT Sumedha

Bhavatu Sabba Mangalam
May all beings be happy

Figure 78: One-Horned Rhino is the pride of Kaziranga National Park, Assam, India. Here with a few Mynas sitting on the top and having a free ride as represented in [Commons \(f\)](#)

22 *Khaggavisāṇasutta* of the *Sutta Nipāta* :: Like a horned Rhinoceros, wander/live alone !

NOTE - i will replacing this with my personal translation, at a LATER date! FOR now . . . the *Khaggavisāṇasutta* [Like a horned Rhinoceros, wander/live alone!], of *Uragav-*

agga, of *Sutta Nipāta*, of *Khuddakanikāya*, is been used (Translated from the Pali by Thanissaro Bhikkhu). Free to distribute and reproduce and available @ <https://www.hermitary.com/solitude/rhinoceros.html> (©1997) Access to Insight (BCBS Edition), 30 November 2013 Retrieved from <http://www.accesstoinsight.org/tipitaka/kn/snp/snp.1.03.than.html> released under CC BY-NC 4.0 Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International @ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>

22.1 The Sutta

*“Sabbesu bhūtesu nidhāya daṇḍam,
Aviheṭṭhayaṃ aññatarampi tesam;
Na puttamiccheyya kuto sahāyaṃ,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Renouncing violence for all living beings,
harming not even a one,
you would not wish for offspring,
so how a companion?
Wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Saṃsaggajātassa bhavanti snehā,
Snehanvayaṃ dukkhamidaṃ pahoti;
Ād{inavaṃ snehajaṃ pekkhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

For a sociable person there are allurements;
on the heels of allurement, this pain.
Seeing allurement’s drawback,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Mitte suhajje anukampamāno,
Hāpeti attham paṭibaddhacitto;
Etaṃ bhayaṃ santhave pekkhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

One whose mind is enmeshed in sympathy
for friends and companions,
neglects the true goal.
Seeing this danger in intimacy,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Vaṃso visālova yathā visatto,
Puttesu dāresu ca yā apekkhā;
Vaṃsakka{irova asajjamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Like spreading bamboo, entwined,
is concern for offspring and spouses.
Like a bamboo sprout, unentangling,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Migo araṇṇamhi yathā abaddho,
Yenicchakaṃ gacchati gocarāya;
Viññū naro seritaṃ pekkhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

As a deer in the wilds, unfettered,
goes for forage wherever it wants:
the wise person, valuing freedom,
wanders alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Āmantanā hoti sahāyamajjhe,
Vāse thāne gamane cārikāya;
Anabhijjhitaṃ seritaṃ pekkhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

In the midst of companions – when staying at home,
when going out wandering – you are prey to requests.
Valuing freedom,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Khiḍḍā rat{i hoti sahāyamajjhe,
Puttesu ca vipulaṃ hoti pemaṃ;
Piyavippayogaṃ vijjucchamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

There is sporting and love in the midst of companions,
and abundant fondness for offspring.
Feeling disgust at the prospect of parting from those who would be dear,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Cātuddiso appaṭigho ca hoti,
Santussamāno itar{i itarena;
Parissayānaṃ sahitaṃ achambh{i,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Without resistance in all four directions,
content with whatever you get,
enduring troubles with no dismay,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Dussaṅgahā pabbajitāpi eke,
Atho gahaṭṭhā gharamāvasantā;
Apposukko paraputtesu hutvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

They are hard to please, some of those gone forth,
as well as those living the household life.
Shedding concern for these offspring of others,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Oropayitvā gihibyañjanāni,
Sañchinnapatto yathā koviḷāro;
Chetvāna v{īro ghibandhanāni,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Cutting off the householder’s marks [hair and beard],
like a kovilara tree
that has shed its leaves,
the prudent one, cutting all household ties,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Sace labhetha nipakaṃ sahāyaṃ,
Saddhiṃ caraṃ sādhuviḥāridh{īraṃ;
Abhibhuyya sabbāni parissayāni,
Careyya tenattamano satīmā”.*
*“No ce labhetha nipakaṃ sahāyaṃ,
Saddhiṃ caraṃ sādhuviḥāridhīraṃ;
Rājāva raṭṭhaṃ vijitaṃ pahāya,
Eko care mātaṅgaraññeva nāgo”.*
*“Addhā pasaṃsāma sahāyasampadaṃ,
Seṭṭhā samā sevitabbā sahāyā;
Ete aladdhā anavajjabhojī,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

If you gain a mature companion,
a fellow traveler, right-living and wise,
overcoming all dangers
go with him, gratified, mindful.
If you don’t gain a mature companion,
a fellow traveler, right-living and wise,
wander alone like a king renouncing his kingdom,
like the elephant in the Matanga wilds, his herd.
We praise companionship – yes!
Those on a par, or better, should be chosen as friends.

If they are not to be found, living faultlessly,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Disvā suvaṇṇassa pabhassarāni,
Kammāraputtēna suniṭṭhitāni;
Saṅghaṭṭamānāni duve bhujasmim,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Seeing radiant bracelets of gold,
well-made by a smith,
clinking, clashing, two on an arm,
wander alone like a rhinoceros

*“Evaṃ dutṭiyena sahā mamassa,
Vācābhilāpo abhisajjanā vā;
Etaṃ bhayaṃ āyatiṃ pekkhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

[*Thinking* :] ”In the same way, if I were to live with another,
there would be careless or abusive talk.”

Seeing this future danger,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Kāmā hi citrā madhurā manoramā,
Virūparūpena mathenti cittaṃ;
Ādḍinavaṃ kāmagaṇesu disvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Because sensual pleasures, elegant, honeyed, & charming,
bewitch the mind with their manifold forms –
seeing this drawback in sensual strands –
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Ītṭi ca gaṇḍo ca upaddavo ca,
Rogo ca sallaṅca bhayaṅca metaṃ;
Etaṃ bhayaṃ kāmagaṇesu disvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

”Calamity, tumor, misfortune,
disease, an arrow, a danger for me.”
Seeing this danger in sensual strands,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Sḍitaṅca uḥhaṅca khudaṃ pipāsaṃ,
Vātātape ḍarṃsasarīsape ca;*

*Sabbānipetāni abhisambhavitvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Cold and heat, hunger and thirst,
wind and sun, horseflies and snakes:
enduring all these, without exception,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Nāgo va yūthāni vivajjayitvā,
Sañjātakhandho padum{i uḷāro;
Yathābhirantaṃ viharaṃ araṇṇe,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

As a great white elephant, with massive shoulders,
renouncing his herd,
lives in the wilds wherever he wants,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Aṭṭhānataṃ saṅgaṇikāratassa,
Yaṃ phassaye sāmāyikaṃ vimuttiṃ;
Ādiccabandhussa vaco nisamma,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

”There’s no way that one delighting in company
can touch even momentary release.”
Heeding the Solar Kinsman’s words,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Dīṭṭh{i visūkāni upātivatto,
Patto niyāmaṃ paṭiladdhamaggo;
Uppannaṇāṇomhi anaṇṇaneyyo,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

[*Thinking* :] Transcending the contortion of views,
the sure way attained, the path gained,
[*realizing* :] ”Unled by others, I have knowledge arisen,”
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Nillolupo nikkuho nippipāso,
Nimmakkho niddhantakasāvamoho;
Nirāsayo sabbaloke bhavitvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

With no greed, no deceit, no thirst, no hypocrisy –
delusion and blemishes blown away –

with no inclinations for all the world, every world,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Pāpaṃ saḥāyaṃ parivajjayetha,
Anatthadassiṃ visame nivṛṭṭhaṃ;
Sayaṃ na seve pasutaṃ pamattaṃ,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Avoid the evil companion,
disregarding the goal, intent on the out-of-tune way.
Don't take as a friend someone heedless and hankering.
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Bahussutaṃ dhammadharaṃ bhajetha,
Mittaṃ uḷāraṃ paṭibhānavantaṃ;
Aññāya atthāni vineyya kaṅkhaṃ,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Consort with one who is learned, who maintains the Dhamma,
a great and quick-witted friend.
Knowing the meanings, subdue your perplexity,
[then] wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Khiḍḍaṃ ratiṃ kāmasukhaṅca loke,
Analaṅkaritvā anapekkhamāno;
Vibhūsaṇaṭṭhānā virato saccavād{i,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Free from longing, finding no pleasure in the world's sport,
love, or sensual bliss, abstaining from adornment,
speaking the truth,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Puttaṅca dāraṃ pitaraṅca mātaraṃ,
Dhanāni dhaññāni ca bandhavāni;
Hitvāna kāmāni yathodhikāni,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Abandoning offspring, spouse, father, mother,
riches, grain, relatives,
and sensual pleasures altogether,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Saṅgo eso parittamettha sokhyaṃ,
Appassādo dukkhamettha bhiyyo;*

*Gaḷo eso iti ñatvā matīmā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

”This is a bondage, a baited hook. There is little happiness here,
next to no satisfaction, all the more suffering and pain.”
Knowing this, circumspect,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Sandālayitvāna samyojanāni,
Jālaṃva bhetvā salilambucār{i;
Aggīva daḍḍhaṃ anivattamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Shattering fetters,
like a fish in the water tearing a net,
like a fire not coming back to what is burnt,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Okkhittacakkhu na ca pādalo,
Guttindriyo rakkhitamānasāno;
Anavassuto aparīḍayhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Eyes downcast, not footloose,
senses guarded, with protected mind,
not oozing – not burning – with lust,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Ohārayitvā gihibyañjanāni,
Sañchannapatto yathā pārīchatto;
Kāsāyavatto abhinikkhamitvā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Taking off the householder’s marks [lay clothing],
like a coral tree that has shed its leaves,
going forth in the ochre robe,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Rasesu gedhaṃ akaraṃ alolo,
Anaññapos{i sapadānacārī;
Kule kule appaṭibaddhacitto,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Showing no greed for flavors, not careless,
going from house to house for alms,

with mind not enmeshed in this family or that,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Pahāya pañcāvaraṇāni cetaso,
Upakkilese byapanujja sabbe;
Anissito chetva sinehadosaṃ,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Abandoning barriers to awareness,
expelling all defilements – all –
non-dependent, cutting aversion, allurements,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Vipīṭṭhikatvāna sukhaṃ dukhañca,
Pubbeva ca somanassadomanassaṃ;
Laddhānupekkhaṃ samathaṃ visuddhaṃ,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Turning your back on pleasure and pain,
as earlier with sorrow and joy,
attaining pure equanimity, tranquility,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Āraddhaviṛiyo paramatthapattiyā,
Al{inacitto akusītavutti;
Daḥhanikkamo thāmbalūpapanno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

With persistence aroused for the highest goal's attainment,
with mind not smeared, not lazy in action,
firm in effort, with steadfastness and strength arisen,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Paṭisallānaṃ jhānamariṇcamāno,
Dhammesu niccaṃ anudhammacār{i;
Ādīnavaṃ sammasitā bhavesu,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Not neglecting seclusion, absorption,
constantly living the Dhamma in line with the Dhamma,
comprehending the danger in states of becoming,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Taṇhakkhayaṃ patthayamappamatto,
Aneḷamūgo sutavā sat{imā;*

*Saṅkhātadhammo niyato padhānavā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Intent on the ending of craving and heedful,
learned, mindful, not muddled, certain –
having reckoned the Dhamma and striving,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“S{ihova saddesu asantasanto,
Vātova jālamhi asajjamāno;
Padumaṁva toyena alippamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Not startled, like a lion, at sounds.
Not snared, like the wind in a net.
Not smeared, like a lotus in water:
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Sīho yathā dāṭhabalī pasayha,
Rājā migānaṁ abhibhuyya cār{i;
Sevetha pantāni senāsanāni,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Like a lion – forceful, strong in fang,
living as a conqueror, the king of beasts –
resort to a solitary dwelling.
Wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Mettaṁ upekkhaṁ karuṇaṁ vimuttiṁ,
Āsevamāno muditañca kāle;
Sabbena lokena avirujjhamāno,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

At the right time consorting
with the release through good will, compassion, appreciation, equanimity,
unobstructed by all the world, any world,
wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Rāgañca dosañca pahāya moham,
Sandālayitvāna saṁyojanāni;
Asantaṁ j{ivitasāṅkhayamhi,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

Having let go of passion, aversion, delusion;
having shattered the fetters;
undisturbed at the ending of life,

wander alone like a rhinoceros.

*“Bhajanti sevanti ca kāraṇatthā,
Nikkāraṇā dullabhā ajja mittā;
Attatthapaññā asuc{i manussā,
Eko care khaggavisāṇakappo”.*

People follow and associate for a motive.
Friends without a motive these days are rare.
They are shrewd for their own ends, and impure.
Wander alone like a rhinoceros.

22.2 Additional Note

This is advanced level! Many will NOT like it and DO NOT be reckless! Life after life, maturity will dawn as one unfolds and evolves as one moves in the journey into the realms of the absolute truth. Further, it might look MEAN for many, however, if you look deeper, that solitude and alone/seclusion time is needed for going within. The journey is within. Sitting in company, will not help! You need to dive within and purify your own heart and straighten your own mind. Also, if one observes the life of Buddha, in The Jataka, many a lives, he lived as an ascetic after finishing the duties of life and used to meditate in secluded places. That gave him depth and he practiced life after life. To be alone is not easy and your mind and body should be able to absorb the shock of the harsh realities of life! You need to introspect and ask yourself - Am i ready for this? Again and again ask this to yourself! It is NOT a show! The journey is NOT easy, however, many walk the path!

22.3 Siddhartha Gautama

The **Four Sights** that **caused the fire** to raise itself within Siddhartha to **search for the truths of life**, in his final life! **Siddhartha saw four things** he had never seen before, in that life. **His eyes, both of mind and heart, were covered by his own father**, the Sakya King Suddhodana, in an effort to dissuade him from his journey. His own father, became his biggest obstacle, in the beginning of life of his life, as the great hermit Asita, studying the child's birth, announced that Siddhartha would become a **great king (chakravartin)** or a **great religious leader!** **Those four sights, shocked** Siddhartha, the Prince of Sakya and **something shook within his heart!** **As if someone was shaking him up to wake up and see the reality of life, as it is!**

- ☐ The first sight - **old man**. Siddhartha had never seen old age before and enquired his chariot driver, Channa, about what he was looking at. **Channa briefed that when people get older they physically decline and Siddhartha too would become old one day.**

Figure 79: Stages of life! There is birth, childhood, youth, middle age, old age and death! All in one tree of life, say in a human body!

- ☒ The second sight - **disease**. Next, Siddhartha saw a diseased person by the side of the road. Looking at the diseased body, he became upset as he had never seen anyone who was ill before. **Channa said that, as life progresses, people do get ill and Siddhartha was not above the law of nature.**
- ☒ The third sight - **dead body being carried away**. On enquiry Siddhartha, **Channa explained that everyone dies eventually and Siddhartha too would die one day.**
- ☒ The fourth sight - **a holy man/ascetic walking by**. Looking at him, Siddhartha became curious, and asked Channa what did that mean. **Channa said, the man was in search of the truths of life.**

Fig. 79 depicts stages of life as well as Siddhartha's above reflections in the depth of the sensitivity, he possessed!

22.4 Sensitivity of Siddhartha Gautama

There was sensitivity in the heart of Siddhartha, the Prince. Just looking of external symbols, shook his heart and he felt it and pondered - All i have will go one day and though i am born a prince, i have not learnt anything in life. Is this all? What is the truth of life and is there freedom? That raging fire set ablaze his heart, to search for what he was looking for, for many uncountable life times before!

Finally, Siddhartha entered the jungles of Uruvela, now Bodh Gaya, Bihar, India, and **practiced**, first as an ascetic carrying out austerities. He tortured himself to the core in that search for the truths of life, sometimes living on a grain of rice. **And then one day**, it has been heard, that while trying to drink water from the river, the body dropped, as he fainted due to extreme weakness. **When consciousness returned**, he sat by and pondered where was this search leading to? **At that moment**, it has been heard that a **musician was teaching his pupil** on a passing boat - **"Do not tighten the cord too much, that it will snap. And if you leave the cord too slack, the music won't play!"** It is said that this teaching, course corrected him, as he **grasped** that **NOT in extremes, was the way**. Then he **broke** the vow of austerities and he accepted a bowl of rice pudding from a village girl, named Sujata. **That was the beginning of the culmination of the journey of life times . . .** What followed through is history!

In that context, in accordance of the above poetry, that Siddhartha **had to live/wander alone and practice**, until Nirvana transpired, Enlightenment happened and he crossed the stage of full liberation or Buddhahood! **You can't always walk alone, but you should make an endeavour to have a reclusive life, daily, where you dive within in meditation. Have a source of livelihood, yet practice everyday alone.** The journey is long, over lifetimes . . . It is **NOT EASY to renounce!** It is **NOT even easy to renounce the thought patterns in the mind, renouncing physically might be more tough**, given the harshness of nature, **if your body and mind is not developed!** **And this development, strength and endurance develops, life after life. It is natural evolution . . .** So **DO NOT be reckless, just by reading things. Again and again**, from your own heart ask yourself! What does your heart say? . . .

Life is not a game! Meet nuns, monks, lay in the sangha, those walking the path, **and continue** on your journey of life! **Gauge yourself, and take it slow . . . This is not a competition! Everyone will evolve in her/his own time! Learn and inspire others, if you can!**

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